

Inherit

First INHERIT Assessment & Monitoring Framework / D3.1

WP3 – T3.1, T3.2, T3.3, T3.4, T3.5

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D3.1 – First INHERIT Assessment and Monitoring Framework

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Abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Description
AC	Acoustic Comfort
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
AQ	Air Quality
AR	Augmented Reality
BIM	Building Information Model
BoM	Bill of Materials
BoQ	Bill of Quantities
CDD	Cooling Degree Days
CEN	European Committee for Standardisation (French: Comité Européen de Normalisation)
CH	Cultural Heritage
D	Deliverable
DB	Database
DD	Degree Days
DHW	Domestic Hot Water
DT	Digital Twin
EC	European Commission
EI	Energy Intensity
EP	Energy Performance
EPB	Energy Performance of Buildings
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
EU	European Union
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GWP	Global Warming Potential
H-BIM	Heritage/Historic Building Information Model
HDD	Heating Degree Days
HP	Highly Protected
HVAC	Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning
ICCROM	International Centre for the Study of the Preservation and Restoration of Cultural Property
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IEA	International Energy Agency
IEQ	Indoor Environmental Quality

D3.1 – First INHERIT Assessment and Monitoring Framework

Acronym	Description
IoT	Internet of Things
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
JRC	Joint Research Centre (from the European Commission)
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCA	Life-Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Cost
LCCA	Life Cycle Cost Analysis
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LRV	Light Reflectance Value
M	Month
MCDA	Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis
NEB	New European Bauhaus
NPV	Net Present Value
nZEB	Nearly Zero Energy Buildings
OEC	Operational Energy Costs
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
PPP	Public-Private Partnership
PPPP	Public-Private-People Partnership
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
s	Service
SPP	Simplified Payback Period
SRI	Smart Readiness Indicator
T	Task
TBS	Technical Building System
TI	Technical Inspection
TC	Thermal Comfort
TMI	Total Material Input
TMO	Total Material Output
TWC	Total Water Consumption
UI	User Interface
UNESCO	United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organisation
UX	User Experience
VC	Visual Comfort
VR	Virtual Reality
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

The INHERIT project aims to develop a systematic methodology for sustainable, inclusive and resource-efficient cultural heritage (CH) solutions. Covering individual buildings to city-level environments, it addresses the entire life cycle of heritage buildings, including design, renovation, monitoring, operation, management, preservation and maintenance. Given Europe’s diverse range of historic buildings, INHERIT focuses on tailored renovation strategies and targeted policies to enhance energy efficiency, sustainability, inclusiveness and resource efficiency while preserving the unique cultural heritage value.

Work Package 3 aims to deliver a “Framework for assessment and monitoring of CH, and catalogue of solutions towards sustainability and resource-efficiency”. One primary objective is to establish a standardised EU approach for digitally-based **Technical Inspections** (TI) using a multi-dimensional H-BIM model. This includes developing a TI methodology, leveraging digital technologies and standards to evaluate the state of heritage buildings and plan actions for their sustainable use. Key inspection areas include foundations, structures, façades, roofs, installations, biodegradation, water tightness, accessibility and functional behaviour.

Another significant objective is to develop a comprehensive **framework** for assessing and monitoring CH buildings. This framework evaluates CH buildings across four pillars: energy performance and indoor environmental quality; resource efficiency, circularity and life-cycle costs; resilience to climate and human-made hazards; and accessibility, inclusiveness, openness and socioeconomic sustainability. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are defined for ongoing evaluation and monitoring. To support this objective, a **web-based application** will be developed for multi-dimensional assessment of CH buildings, allowing facility managers and inspectors to input KPI data and visualise metrics.

Additionally, a detailed catalogue of tailored solutions for CH buildings will be created under WP3. This **INHERIT Hub of Measures** will be an inventory of solutions organised by building components. The measures are categorised based on the INHERIT pillars, TI headings, and building life cycle phases, with detailed datasheets provided for each measure.

Finally, a methodology to analyse heritage value and assess **financial sustainability and potential risks** will also be defined to support CH buildings’ preservation. The methodology will review and categorise the measures from the INHERIT Hub based on cost-effectiveness and acceptance.

The framework developed within WP3 will be implemented in the eight pilots of the project, aligning with the New European Bauhaus values, and serve for both *ex-ante* and *ex-post* evaluation of the INHERIT services in the pilots.

This deliverable is the first of three consecutive reports for WP3, and sets the foundation for future work in INHERIT, outlining the initial assessment and monitoring framework for CH buildings. The ongoing development and refinement of this framework will ensure that heritage buildings across Europe are preserved and utilized efficiently, aligning with contemporary sustainability and inclusiveness standards. The deliverable documents the work developed up to date in the tasks of the work package 3, thus, it is an ongoing work that will be further developed and applied to the project pilots.

1. Introduction

The INHERIT project is driven by the need to develop sustainable, inclusive and resource-efficient solutions for cultural heritage (CH) buildings. These buildings, which vary significantly in age, construction methods and architectural styles, present unique challenges that necessitate tailored approaches to ensure their preservation while adapting them to modern needs. The project's overarching goal is to address these challenges by enhancing the sustainability of CH buildings while maintaining their cultural significance.

To achieve this, INEHRIT aims to establish a systematic methodology towards sustainable, inclusive and resource-efficient cultural heritage (CH) solutions. The project focuses on enabling socially innovative and economically viable interventions at various urban levels (from individual buildings to entire neighbourhoods or cities). This approach covers all stages of the heritage-built environment's life cycle, including design, renovation, monitoring, operation, management and maintenance. Given the diverse nature of the historic building stock, which encompasses structures from different periods, construction methods and architectural styles, differentiated renovation strategies and targeted policies are essential. These strategies should promote energy efficiency, sustainability, inclusiveness and resource efficiency, while preserving cultural heritage value.

In alignment with these goals, the primary objective of this deliverable is to present a comprehensive framework for the assessment and monitoring of CH buildings. This framework is complemented by a catalogue of solutions aimed at enhancing sustainability and resource efficiency. The deliverable elaborates on these objectives through the five tasks outlined in Work Package 3, each addressing critical aspects necessary for effective preservation and renovation of CH buildings.

Building on these objectives, INHERIT delves into the conservation potential of heritage buildings across various European countries. This investigation involves establishing comprehensive technical inspection protocols and assessing criteria across different thematic areas. The project will evaluate a range of potential interventions for CH buildings, considering architectural, regulatory and technical constraints inherent to their historical value. Additionally, it will analyse the social acceptance and financial viability of these interventions, culminating in the development of a catalogue of tailored, cost-effective solutions for CH buildings. The outcomes will support the practical implementation of the New European Bauhaus (NEB) values and working principles, ensuring that sustainability and cultural preservation are integrated into modern architectural and urban development practices.

These objectives, part of the **Scientific Layer** of the INHERIT methodology (see Figure 1), aim to evaluate and improve buildings energy and resource-efficiency, climate resilience, and inclusiveness, starting from the stakeholders' expectations and needs.

D3.1 – First INHERIT Assessment and Monitoring Framework

Figure 1: INHERIT methodology integrating societal, scientific and technological processes

Thus, the present **deliverable 3.1 (D3.1)** “First INHERIT Assessment and Monitoring Framework” is the first version of the INHERIT assessment and monitoring framework, which includes progress on all five tasks but in varying degrees of depth, depending on the progress. The **reporting plan** for the current deliverable and subsequent two more versions (D3.2 and D3.3) of the INHERIT Assessment and Monitoring Framework deliverables is included in Table 1.

Table 1: WP3 Tasks reporting through the Assessment and Monitoring deliverables

	Task 3.1	Task 3.2	Task 3.3	Task 3.4	Task 3.5
D3.1	Technical Inspection of CH buildings: EU common understanding and expert knowledge.	Assessment and monitoring framework in the four pillars: macro-objectives and set of KPIs detailed.	Approach (and minimum viable product) to the web-based application, specifications and assessment for tool implementation.	Initial conservation measures documented through developed templates.	Approach to the task: methodology with initial literature review on financing schemes.
D3.2	Technical Inspection of CH buildings: practical approach and digital skills required.	Refinements and updates in the framework. Normalisation and scoring of the indicators across pillars.	Development of mock-ups and first version of the web application for the assessment framework	Enriched list of conservation measures documented (new/additional measures in the template).	Detailed methodology and criteria under the evaluated aspects: analysis of cost-effectiveness, risk and acceptance of measures.
D3.3	Technical Inspection integrated into a collaborative H-BIM model.	Refinements and updates (if any) in the framework.	Final version of the tool.	Final (consolidated) measures described in the template – Consolidated catalogue	Results of the assessment carried out in the Hub of measures (from T3.4).

This work is connected to the decision support services being developed in the INHERIT project and their demonstration across the eight pilot sites. The studies under WP3 provide the essential technical foundation that informs the development of the services in WP4, ensuring that they are aligned with the specific needs and constraints of cultural heritage buildings. Additionally, the social engagement activities in WP2, including stakeholder involvement through Social Labs and the Multi-Stakeholder Forum, are closely linked to the methodologies established in WP3. These activities help ensure that the technical solutions are socially accepted, inclusive and tailored to the diverse cultural contexts represented by the pilots. The continuous feedback loop between WP3, WP4 and WP5 allows for the iterative refinement of both the decision support services and the practical interventions being tested in the pilots, ultimately contributing to the successful replication and scaling of the INHERIT solutions.

The following Table 2 summarises the services (s.0 to s.10) in relation to the Heritage Building life cycle phase and indicates the pilots where they will be demonstrated, either as a complete service or in a later stage as early replication.

Table 2: INHERIT pilots and services relation

Heritage Building Lifecycle	INHERIT services	Demonstration and Validation								
		Pilot 1 Croatia	Pilot 2 France	Pilot 3 Greece	Pilot 4 Latvia	Pilot 5 Poland	Pilot 6 Spain	Pilot 7 Sweden	Pilot 8 Turkey	
	Smartification & Data Exchange Platform	s.0								
Design & Renovation	Interactive screen use & AR-VR interfaces	s.1					Repl.			
	Modelling & simulation environment	s.2						Repl.		
	Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	s.3				Repl.		Repl.		Repl.
Monitoring, operation & management	Indoor environmental quality & comfort optimisation	s.4	Repl.	Repl.						
	Energy forecasting & data-driven intelligent management	s.5			Repl.					
	Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real-time monitoring	s.6					Repl.			
	Real-time insights on activity and mobility patterns	s.7								Repl.
Preservation & maintenance	Preventive maintenance with H-BIM	s.8		Repl.						
	GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance	s.9				Repl.				
	Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios	s.10								Repl.

1.1. Background

As the energy transition moves forward, there is a need to enhance and strengthen the interaction between the climate neutrality target and the aim of protecting World Heritage properties for future generations. Even though World Heritage properties are generally well-researched, their role and relation to their wider cultural, social, environmental and economic context is still too often overlooked. Cultural built heritage should be protected from further deterioration through the

process of refurbishment, revitalization, and adaptive reuse following contemporary requirements (UNESCO, 2009 [01]). Currently, approximately 35% of EU buildings are over 50 years old, and nearly 75% of the building stock is energy inefficient. Within the EU, existing building stock can be renovated to achieve energy and CO₂ savings of 5-6% and 5%, respectively. Because of recent codes and standards, today's built structures use only half the energy that structures from the 1980s did. As can be seen, there is significant potential for improvement in the energy efficiency of these buildings (European Commission, 2019 [02]). For these reasons, it is necessary to develop a comprehensive framework for assessing and monitoring energy upgrades to cultural heritage buildings.

Because of their important role in the cultural history and also in the energy transition, there have been several studies that have investigated different methods and solutions to decarbonise cultural heritage buildings.

Polo López et al. considered the importance of cultural heritage and used a risk-benefit analysis to study the installation of solar panels on a Scottish castle's roof in accordance with EN-16883:2017's heritage guidelines (Polo López et al., 2021 [03]).

Besen and Boarin investigated energy upgrades alongside with seismic assessment in three heritage buildings in New Zealand in accordance with the EN 16247-2 and EN-16883:2017 (Besen and Boarin, 2023 [04]). Though the study considers technical, seismic and energy aspects, it does not include any attempts to improve accessibility for people with disabilities.

Güleroğlu et al. has stressed the importance of the cost of energy upgrades and looked into the case of an energy retrofit of a CH building in Turkey using Life Cycle Cost Analysis (LCCA) to assess the energy and cost of retrofit measures and selecting the most suitable retrofit package using the cost-optimal criterion (Güleroğlu et al., 2020 [05]).

Polo Lopez et al. studied the energy retrofit in three case studies, evaluating the measures using assessment charts such as registration and descriptive, solutions proposed and global energy assessment charts (Polo López et al., 2021 [03]). There are still gaps in this method's detailed analysis of retrofit measures, including those related to accessibility and climate change resilience.

Ramos et al. identified the importance of the cost viability of energy upgrades and night ventilation strategies, using a 6-step methodology for the energy retrofit of heritage buildings, applying it to a Catholic church in Cadiz (Ramos et al., 2019 [06]).

Franco and Mauri place a high value on energy efficiency and heritage conservation, approaching the methodology of a thorough building survey and evaluation, identifying solutions that are compatible with conservation, and a performance study of these to nZEB standards, applying it to a historic building in Genoa (Franco and Mauri, 2024 [07]).

Lucchi used quality performance indicators for environmental performance evaluation in 50 museum cases from various European countries in order to compare quality levels and identify weaknesses (Lucchi, 2017 [08]). Even if the energy assessment component of CH buildings has received considerable attention, there are gaps in the areas of accessibility and climate adaptation.

Shehata et al. pointed out the importance of stakeholder participation in the CH building energy retrofit process by applying the 3-Ts methodology, which includes the definition of tasks, the targets and the tools, applying it to heritage villas in Egypt (Shehata et al., 2024 [09]).

Through an energy and financial evaluation, Milone et al. emphasised the distinctions between Best Allowed Technology and Available Best Technology for the energy retrofit of a historic building in Sicily (Milone et al., 2015 [10]).

Blecich et al. compared eight energy retrofit packages and combinations in a Croatian castle, considering energy savings, NPV (Net Present Value) and SPP (Simplified Payback Period), but leaving significant gaps in accessibility and climate resilience aspects (Blecich et al., 2016 [11]).

Magrini and Franco's research used the ITACA tool, a rating system for the detailed energy audit of energy retrofit measures in CH buildings, to assess and improve the sustainability of a 16th century CH building through energy performance refurbishment (Magrini and Franco, 2016 [12]).

Ruggeri et al.'s research resulted in the development of a scoring-based decision support system to determine the best case scenario for energy upgrades in Italian buildings, based on environmental benefits, economic efficiency, indoor environmental conditions improvement, and cultural heritage protection and preservation (Ruggeri et al., 2020 [13]). Finally, Egusquiza et al. emphasised the importance of protecting cultural heritage in energy retrofit projects, using a method for assessing the sustainability of energy-saving measures at the historic urban level that is based on the application of the concept of heritage impact assessment at multiple scales, and comparing 77 different retrofit measures (Egusquiza et al., 2018 [14]).

Beyond the risk and energy assessment methodologies discussed above, tools to facilitate the CH buildings assessments such as the HiBERatlas have been developed. HiBERatlas¹ (Eurac Research, 2021) is a database of best practices for energy retrofitting heritage buildings with a focus on cultural preservation. Each example building includes important details such as its construction, heritage assessment, building material specifications, energy efficiency, building services and comfort, and renovation solutions and products. It provides useful information on technical issues and decision-making processes; however, it is mainly an informative tool and it does not provide a multidimensional assessment of CH buildings.

Despite significant progress in understanding the framework for assessing and monitoring energy upgrades in heritage buildings, several critical gaps remain. Investigating through the literature review, **it is clear that there are significant gaps in the assessment frameworks, such as accessibility for people with disabilities, the lack of climate resiliency aspects, and the existence of a web-tool that provides the necessary support for decision-making processes** regarding comprehensive assessments of cultural heritage buildings and detailed analysis for each individual case.

In order to fill in these gaps, the present study aims to provide a new and integrated framework for the assessment and monitoring of energy renovation of cultural heritage buildings based on four pillars: 1) Energy Efficiency and IEQ, 2) Resource efficiency, circularity and LCC, 3) Climate resilience and human-made hazards, and 4) Accessibility, inclusion, transparency and socio-economic sustainability. The first two pillars cover and largely reinforce existing assessment frameworks while pillar 3 fills the gap of resilience of heritage buildings to climate change and natural disasters. Since monumental constructions bare great importance and contain history of previous generations that should be passed to the ones to come, it is imperative to take special precautions, which would prevent the deterioration of the structures. Another novelty of the INHERIT assessment framework of this study is the accessibility. According to Ruiz-Rodrigo et al., 16% of the world's population has

¹ <https://hiberatlas.eurac.edu/de/willkommen-bei-uns-1.html>

a disability and the results of their survey showed that visitors to historical heritage places experienced problems related to obstacles and impact on participation, disabling accessibility and heritage meaning. Cultural heritage buildings were built accessibility standards and the rights of people with disabilities were established. Many of these venues are not equipped for a disabled person to have easy access to. This is why it is essential to guarantee the possibility of visiting historic heritage; it not only makes it possible to develop and sustain certain activities but also contributes to the forging of identity (Ruiz-Rodrigo et al., 2024 [15]).

Another significant finding of this study is the integrated web-based application, which will facilitate the multidimensional assessment of CH sites using the INHERIT assessment and monitoring framework. It will enable facility managers and inspectors to enter data about CH sites and provide a dashboard with metrics and indicators tailored to the needs of various stakeholders. The resulting application will include important tools such as an application for the smart readiness indicator, as well as an open access platform containing all relevant data elements for CH sites. Overall, the innovation of the INHERIT assessment framework is that it covers the entire renovation process from the organisation and structuring of controls to the definition of key performance indicators, from the creation of a hub of measures, their economic viability and, finally, the development of an easy-to-use tool to facilitate the overall evaluation.

1.2. Objective

To address the knowledge gap in the field of cultural heritage buildings and support decision-making in preservation and renovation practices, this study presents a comprehensive framework for the assessment and monitoring of CH buildings. Additionally, it provides a catalogue of solutions designed to enhance sustainability and resource efficiency. This framework is articulated through the five tasks within the work package 3, each targeting critical elements of the preservation and renovation process. The challenges associated with retrofitting cultural heritage buildings, such as the need to reconcile historical value with energy efficiency and navigate complex regulatory requirements, highlight the importance of innovative frameworks and solutions that can balance preservation and sustainability (Panakaduwa et al., 2024 [16]; Dias Pereira et al., 2021 [17]).

The first task focuses on developing a detailed technical inspection methodology for CH buildings. By leveraging advanced digital technologies, it aims to thoroughly analyse the condition of heritage buildings before any intervention. This includes evaluating foundations, structure, façades, roofs, installations, biodegradation, accessibility and functional behaviour. It is crucial for planning effective prevention, monitoring, management, maintenance and renovation actions that balance sustainability with heritage preservation. The insights gained will be integrated into a multidimensional H-BIM collaborative model, setting the foundation for future digital twin applications.

Building on the technical inspection methodology, the second task aims to develop a comprehensive framework for assessing and monitoring CH buildings. The framework covers four key pillars, including energy performance and indoor environmental quality; resource efficiency, circularity and life-cycle cost; climate resilience and human-made hazards; and accessibility, inclusiveness and socio-economic sustainability. By defining procedures and key performance indicators for these areas, the framework facilitates ongoing evaluation and monitoring. This robust assessment methodology will be applied in INHERIT pilots, providing valuable data for both initial and follow-up evaluations.

To support the implementation of the assessment and monitoring framework, the third task will create a web-based application. This tool will allow facility managers and inspectors to input data related to the defined KPIs and visualise metrics through an interactive dashboard. By integrating existing tools, such as the Smart Readiness Indicator, and aligning with the project's data platform, this application will ensure seamless access to relevant data. This facilitates efficient decision-making and management of CH sites.

The fourth task involves developing a comprehensive catalogue of viable, acceptable and affordable solutions for CH buildings. This inventory will consider the purpose of retrofits, historical value and structural and technical constraints. It will include smart applications and cost-effective solutions categorised according to the four pillars of the assessment and monitoring framework. This Hub of measures will serve as a preliminary selection tool for evaluating potential interventions, supporting further service development and usability testing.

The last task focuses on reviewing and categorising potential interventions from the INHERIT Hub based on their cost-effectiveness and acceptance. This will contribute to capacity building and training activities aimed at upskilling heritage energy advisors, ensuring the long-term sustainability of interventions.

By addressing these objectives through the outlined tasks, this deliverable aims to enhance the conservation potential of heritage buildings across Europe. The resulting framework and solutions will not only improve the energy efficiency and resilience of these buildings, but also ensure their accessibility and inclusiveness, thereby supporting the broader goals of the INHERIT project and the New European Bauhaus values.

1.3. Deliverable structure

The document is structured in the following sections:

- **Section 1**, current section, **introduces** the INHERIT project, and presents the WP3 objectives and concept, as well as the present study. It includes a subsection with the **background (1.1)**, where a literature review has been included to better justify the need for the framework and the overall work in this work package, the **objective (1.2)**, where the rationale of the project and the need of this work is explained. Finally, it includes the **Deliverable structure (1.2)**.
- **Section 2** focuses on the **Technical Inspection methodology** for cultural heritage buildings. It includes a subsection devoted to analyse the **current situation of EU cultural heritage buildings (2.1)**, as well as a subsection for the **European framework (2.2)**, which analyses the specifications on conservation and intervention in heritage buildings, with an analysis of the key points from the expert knowledge. Finally, it includes an overview of the **landscape of European standardisation (2.3)**, which is in turn complemented by further information in **Annex 1**; and the **initial conclusions** to consider for the TI methodology **(2.4)** from this first report. This section is related to the Task 3.1 "INHERIT heritage resource-efficient technical inspection".
- **Section 3** includes the **assessment and monitoring framework**, with an introduction of it and then a subsection is devoted to each pillar: **Pillar 1** on Energy Performance and IEQ **(3.1)**, **Pillar 2** on Resource efficiency, circularity and LCC **(3.2)**, **Pillar 3** on Resilience to climate and human-made hazards **(3.3)**, and **Pillar 4** on Accessibility, inclusiveness, openness and

socioeconomic sustainability (3.4). Each of these subsections include the macro-objectives and a general description of the pillar and the list of KPIs defined to evaluate and monitor it, while in **Annex 2**, **Annex 3**, **Annex 4** and **Annex 5** there is a subsection for each KPI where they are detailed, including a definition, objective, assessment criteria, references and examples, where needed. This section is related to the Task 3.2 “INHERIT assessment and monitoring framework”.

- **Section 4** is devoted to the **web-based application for the multi-dimensional assessment**. It includes the **specifications of the web-based application (4.1)**, including the business requirements, the steps for the design of the tool, the calculation method, as well as an example scenario for the score card that will be shown as result of the calculation. It also includes the **assessment for the tool implementation (4.2)**, with an example of the data structure. This section is related to the Task 3.3 “Web-based application for multi-dimensional assessment”.
- **Section 5** is about the **INHERIT Hub of measures**, where the methodology to gather the measures is explained. The initial **list of measures (5.1)** is included, with initial information collected and the first classification of them according to the key elements of a building. The **measure datasheet (5.2)** is also presented as a template where to gather the input about each measure, that will form the INHERIT catalogue. This section is related to the Task 3.4 “INHERIT Hub of measures inventory for efficient, inclusive, resilient and low-emission CH”.
- **Section 6** introduces the approach to the **financial sustainability and risk assessment methodology**, which includes the approach to the assessment of the cost-efficiency, financial risk and social acceptance of the Hub of measures. It also includes a subsection with an initial literature review on **financing schemes for CH (6.1)**. This section is related to the Task 3.5 “Financial sustainability and risk assessment methodology for sustainable and inclusive CH”.
- **Section 7** provides the **conclusions** of the document.
- **Section 8** includes the **references** of the whole deliverable.
- **Annex 1** presents the **Landscape of European standardisation for Technical Inspection**. This annex is complementary to section 2, and includes both the analysis of CEN and ISO general framework, as well as the Spanish standards.
- **Annex 2** includes the details for the **KPIs in the Pillar 1** (Energy Performance and Indoor Environmental Quality). This annex is complementary to section 3 (specifically, section 3.1), including a subsection for the detailed explanation of each of the 14 KPIs.
- **Annex 3** includes the details for the **KPIs in the Pillar 2** (Resource efficiency, circularity and Life Cycle Cost). This annex is complementary to section 3 (specifically, section 3.2), including a subsection for the detailed explanation of each of the 8 KPIs.
- **Annex 4** includes the details for the **KPIs in the Pillar 3** (Resilience to climate and human-made hazards). This annex is complementary to section 3 (specifically, section 3.3), including a subsection for the detailed explanation of each of the 5 KPIs.
- **Annex 5** includes the details for the **KPIs in the Pillar 4** (Accessibility, inclusiveness, openness and socioeconomic sustainability). This annex is complementary to section 3 (specifically, section 3.4), including a subsection for the detailed explanation of each of the 9 KPIs.

2. Technical Inspection methodology

This task pursues to 1) develop a methodology to carry out technical inspections in cultural heritage sites as well as 2) conduct an **in-depth analysis of the digital technologies** that can be used effectively to **gain precise knowledge of the state of conservation of heritage buildings** prior to any intervention and to plan actions for prevention, monitoring, management, maintenance and rehabilitation of buildings for their more efficient and sustainable (re)use, bearing in mind the ICCROM's² means for heritage care.

The Technical Inspection will be carried out under **six main headings** in order to structure the methodology and make it easier and more coherent, considering as a reference other similar inspection processes in the construction sector.

These headings will be:

1. Foundations and structures
2. Façades and roofs
3. Installations
4. Biodegradation, water tightness and beauty
5. Accessibility
6. Functional behaviour (intelligent domotic/ inmotoc system)

In the course of the development and research process, some of these points are likely to be integrated or undergo minor modifications in order to optimise the usability of the TI and according to the needs resulting from the development of the H-BIM model (INHERIT Service s.8).

The inspection will be aimed from the initial stages to strike the complex **balance between sustainable** building performance (environmental impact, budget, time) and **heritage values** preservation (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Technical Inspection balance between sustainable building performance and heritage values preservation

² <https://www.iccom.org/projects/preventive-conservation>

2.1. Current situation of EU cultural heritage buildings

The development of a comprehensive methodology for the Technical Inspection of heritage buildings is essential for ensuring effective maintenance, which in turn helps to **slow down** their **degradation**. Building on existing literature and the four categories of heritage documentation data proposed by Khalil et al., this methodology should integrate expert knowledge in the **technical diagnosis** and **analysis** of potential **pathologies** specific to historic buildings. These pathologies often depend on the **construction techniques** and **materials** used, as well as other contributing factors. Additionally, the methodology should systematically collect data on the buildings' conservation status over time, enabling **informed decisions for preventive, corrective or intervention** actions. This approach promotes sustainable, efficient and cost-effective management of heritage buildings (Khalil et al., 2020 [18]).

Owners or managers of heritage assets will gain an in-depth understanding of this method, **facilitating decision-making** on the programming of future interventions and the ranking of the importance of each intervention for cost-effective maintenance.

This study will build on the results of the ITEHIS project³, which explored innovative and digital technologies to develop a methodology for the inspection of historic buildings for public use, with the collaboration of companies with expertise in the conservation of cultural heritage.

The conservation and management of European heritage assets present significant challenges for both owners and public administrations, given the **high costs** and **complex planning** required. Developing a TI methodology to assess the state of conservation of these buildings focuses on a **preventive maintenance** approach. This methodology aims to **identify** potential issues or pathologies **early on**, which, if left unaddressed, would lead to significantly higher restoration costs, aligning with Ortiz et al.'s findings that preventive conservation reduces expensive interventions in CH (Ortiz et al., 2018 [19]). By adopting this proactive approach, the methodology fosters more **sustainable, inclusive, resilient and cost-effective management of CH**, in accordance with UNESCO's principles about World Heritage, and sustainable development (Labadi, 2016 [20]).

Moreover, CH buildings are often **protected by law**, with varying levels of protection depending on their cultural significance. **Interventions** in these buildings can be **complex, time consuming** and subject to stringent **legal requirements**. Preventive maintenance aims to minimise the need for such interventions by implementing small-scale, proactive actions that conserve the assets before more extensive and invasive works becomes necessary. This approach helps preserve the integrity of the buildings while reducing the risk of altering or damaging their original elements.

According to UNESCO, "Heritage is our legacy from the past, what we live with today, and what we pass on to future generations. Our cultural and natural heritage are both irreplaceable sources of life and inspiration"⁴. This highlights the enduring value of heritage, not only as a connection to our history but also as a vital part of our present and a gift to future generations.

Using Spain as an example within the European context, buildings designated as Assets of Cultural Interest are legally recognised for their **significant historical, artistic, architectural or cultural value** (Sanz Rodríguez, 2021 [21]; Bond and Worthing, 2016 [22]; Spanish Law 16/1985, June 25 on Spanish Heritage [23]). This classification grants them substantial social importance, embedding them within

³ <https://www.cartif.es/en/itehis-en/>

⁴ <https://www.unesco.org/en/world-heritage>

the identity and history of their region. Consequently, their conservation is subject to strict legal protections. Once classified, these buildings must adhere to the regulations that ensure any intervention, no matter how minor, preserves their integrity and historical-artistic value.

The outlook for heritage buildings is concerning, as significant losses have occurred due to inadequate maintenance, often stemming from limited resources and funding. The inherent complexity of these buildings -due to their unique materials, construction techniques, geometric compositions, architectural styles and varied uses- further complicates their management. This complexity not only slows down preservation efforts but also exacerbates damage and pathologies, ultimately driving up the cost of interventions. It is important to note that, according to the Smart Heritage Buildings (SHBUILDINGS) project (INTERREG IV-B, SUDOE)⁵, "for every euro invested in conservation, between 3 (rural areas) and 5 (cities) euros are saved in restoration".

Ruiz-Jaramillo et al. emphasise the critical role that the continuous use of heritage buildings plays in ensuring their preservation. Building on this concept, and incorporating the insights of stakeholders and experts with over 10 years of experience in the cultural heritage field, Figure 3 presents a scheme inspired by the life cycle of a highly protected heritage building (i.e. *Monasterio de Nuestra Señora del Prado* in Valladolid, INHERIT Pilot 6). This scheme also reflects the risks and vulnerabilities that heritage buildings face, as highlighted by Ortiz et al. (2018 [19]) and Ruiz-Jaramillo et al. (2020 [24]). The image uses a traffic light metaphor to visually represent the key risks and challenges that heritage buildings encounter over time.

Figure 3: Scheme with the life cycle of a highly protected heritage building and the key points and risks that it faces over time

⁵ <https://www.cartif.es/en/shbuildings-en/>

Elaborating on the figure:

- **High Risk (Red):** Loss of Cultural Heritage due to abandonment and lack of maintenance.
 - **Impact:** Inadequate maintenance accelerates deterioration and causes irreparable damage to heritage buildings.
 - **Consequence:** This leads to loss of cultural and social identity, making recovery difficult and going against current EU trends in heritage conservation.
 - **Keywords:** Abandonment, no- use, vandalism, collapse, disappearance of artistic elements.
- **Moderate Risk (Yellow):** Management and preventive maintenance for functionality, ensuring durability over time.
 - **Impact:** Heritage buildings present unique challenge due to their materials, construction techniques and architectural styles, making their management complex and time-consuming.
 - **Consequence:** The lack of a unified maintenance or technical inspection methodology leads to insufficient management, increasing damage or restoration cost.
 - **Keywords:** Technical inspection, preventive maintenance, early detection of pathologies, corrective interventions.
- **Low Risk (Green):** Conservation and renovation to achieve a sustainable, inclusive, resource-efficient, inclusive and resilient Cultural Heritage.
 - **Impact:** Conservation and renovation aligned with current needs of society and sustainability principles ensure a long life-cycle of the building.
 - **Consequence:** An integrated approach combining energy renovation and efficient preventive maintenance not only increase the life-time of buildings, but also improves indoor comfort, ensuring compliance with current standards of habitability and energy efficiency, while preserving their cultural value.
 - **Keywords:** Sustainable, cost-effective, resilient, accessible, renovation, maintenance, installation of efficient systems, demand, cultural value.

As reflected, the conservation and maintenance of heritage buildings is not an easy task due to various external factors, and management coordination is often deficient (Torres-González et al., 2021 [25]).

The main deficiencies identified in terms of maintenance, conservation, functionality, energy efficient and accessibility are listed below.

- **Maintenance and Conservation**

- Lack of allocated budget leads to accumulation of structural and technical problems.
- No integrated strategies or standardised TI procedures to optimise and facilitate the process compared to conventional architecture.
- Shortage of technical professionals specialised in traditional construction.
- The unique geometry and complex characteristics of the architectural elements and their legal protection, based on their cultural value, make any kind of intervention difficult.

- **Functionality**

- Limitations due to historical architecture designs which do not respond to the needs of current use.
- Lack of facilities and services.
- Incompatibilities with existing legislation.

- **Energy Efficiency**

- Poor thermal efficiency due to lack of insulation or inefficient windows.
- Inefficient or outdated cooling and heating systems (even non-existent).
- Specific thermal and humidity conditions for the conservation of cultural heritage artefacts and assets.

- **Accessibility**

- Physical and spatial barriers that make access difficult for people with disabilities.
- Lack of attention to diversity.
- Slow digitalisation process of the CH buildings.

2.2. European framework. Specifications on conservation and intervention in heritage buildings

Allowing the abandonment of the Cultural Heritage buildings and, consequently, their disappearance, results in a loss of identity and value that are often difficult to restore.

Europe has an important architectural heritage. The European Union is committed to safeguarding it, one of its priorities being to conserve and promote Europe's CH. This target is in line with ICCROM's vision and UNESCO's principles.

Conservation and management of these buildings is a major challenge shared by all European countries due to the high economic investment required for any intervention in buildings in ruins or with irreparable losses caused by a no-existent or inadequate maintenance.

In this context, it is essential to deepen the European framework on these issues, starting from the task partners such as experts in the field of conservation and intervention of CH and also to know their executive procedures and current regulations unifying criteria and process to achieve a common baseline to carry out an innovative methodology of TI of heritage buildings useful and applicable to the entire European framework that facilitates the preventive maintenance of buildings (process outlined in Figure 4).

Figure 4: Process to create a common EU baseline for the technical inspection of CH buildings

A common EU approach will be established to conduct digitally-based technical inspections of heritage buildings. This methodology will assess their current condition and prioritise resource allocation across all aspects of their life cycle: design, renovation, operation, monitoring, maintenance and management. This approach will be underpinned by a seamless, multidimensional and multipurpose H-BIM model, serving as the foundation for digital twin generation.

Drawing from contributions by heritage experts across various countries, the tables at the end of the section provide an initial overview of the current state of conservation and CH interventions in their respective nations.

For instance, in Poland, buildings are designated as cultural heritage when they are formally recognised for their significant historical, architectural or cultural value. This recognition, similar to processes in Spain and other European countries, is followed by legal protections and regulations to preserve the building's integrity and significance.

CH buildings also require meticulous attention to meet various maintenance and preservation demands. In Poland, renovation work, such as insulating façades or replacing windows, must be approved by a cultural conservator responsible for the building. Similarly, in Spain, even minimal interventions must comply with extensive legislation, requiring the preparation of technical projects and navigating complex administrative procedures. In practice, these renovations are challenging and costly, as seen in both the Polish and Spanish cases.

The primary needs of CH buildings, identified through contributions from partners, stakeholders and expert consultations, include:

- 1. Ensuring Structural Stability:** Many heritage buildings face structural issues due to age, weathering and insufficient maintenance. Assessing structural integrity is crucial to identify problems like cracks, settling or material degradation, enabling appropriate reinforcement or restoration actions.

2. **Restoring Façades:** Façades of heritage buildings often show signs of wear, such as erosion, cracks and discoloration. Proper cleaning, repair and restoration are vital to maintain architectural integrity and historical significance. Additionally, non-insulated façades frequently lead to mould and humidity issues inside the building.
3. **Maintaining Roofs:** Ensuring the structural integrity of roof systems is critical to prevent water damage and protect building interiors. Regular inspections, leaks repairs, material replacements and drainage improvements are essential to avoid structural decay and preserve valuable interiors.
4. **Conserving Interiors:** The interiors of CH buildings often contain valuable artworks, decorative elements and historical features that require careful conservation. Measures such as indoor air quality control, lighting adjustments and routine evaluations are necessary to preserve their authenticity and cultural value.
5. **Upgrading Infrastructure:** Many heritage buildings lack modern infrastructure, such as heating (often outdated systems), ventilation (usually limited to natural ventilation), plumbing and electrical systems. Upgrading these systems requires careful planning to preserve the building's historical character while ensuring functionality and minimising visual impact.
6. **Enhancing Accessibility:** Improving accessibility for all visitors, including those with disabilities, is essential. Retrofitting buildings with accessible entrances, ramps and facilities while preserving historical features demands innovative design solutions that comply with accessibility standards.
7. **Documenting and Inventorying:** Comprehensive documentation is crucial for preventive maintenance and preservation. This includes archival research, condition assessments, photographic documentation and maintenance schedules to monitor changes and guide conservation efforts.
8. **Repurposing and Adaptive Reuse:** To prevent abandonment and neglect, finding new uses for heritage buildings that respect their historical significance while ensuring continued relevance is vital. Adaptive reuse projects not only revitalise these buildings but also attract funding and interest, enhancing their preservation.
9. **Retrofitting for Energy Efficiency:** Implementing energy-efficient solutions in heritage buildings promotes sustainability and reduces operating costs. This includes adding insulation, installing energy-efficient lighting and heating systems, utilising smart technologies and incorporating renewable energy sources where possible.

Addressing these needs through comprehensive assessment, strategic planning and targeted interventions is crucial to ensure the long-term preservation of CH buildings.

Regarding **inspection procedures**, taking inspiration from the Spanish legislation on Technical Inspection of Buildings (Real Decreto-ley 8/2011 de 1 de julio; Gobierno de España, 2011), the following points stand out:

- There is no standardised methodology for assessing the current state of conservation of CH buildings across different regions.
- Inspections are typically conducted by technical engineers and architects with a minimum of 1-2 years of experience.

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- Specialised companies in construction and inspection often create custom checklists for visual inspections and on-site tests. These checklists vary based on the type of inspection (e.g. energy efficiency, building TI for insurance purposes) and are informed by both standards and expert knowledge. The common testing methods include test pits, thermography, thermofluxometry, blower door tests, temporary analysers, noise tests, fissure metres, lux meters, CO₂ meters, temperature and humidity meters, combustion gas meters, tightness tests for facilities and smoke tests.
- There is a legal gap regarding the inspection and maintenance of heritage buildings. Unlike conventional buildings, which in Spain are required to undergo assessment every 10 years after 50 years of construction, heritage buildings lack clear regulatory guidelines.

The next step in this process was to determine the order of relevance of the TI headings, which were defined at the project's outset (Table 3).

Table 3: Second step of the methodology, in which partners (CARTIF, CEMOSA, FASADA and ISSO) ordered the relevance of the TI headings according to their criteria

Order of relevance of the headings <i>(Where [1] is the most important and [6] the least relevant)</i>	CARTIF	CEMOSA	FASADA	ISSO
Foundations and Structure	1	1	2	1
Façades and Roofs	2	2	1	2
Installations (cold/heat/lighting)	4	4	3	4
Biodegradation, water tightness and beauty	3	3	4	3
Accessibility	5	5	6	5
Functional behaviour (smart domotic/inmotic system)	6	6	5	6

The prioritisation of the headings for the TI of heritage buildings is guided by the need to address the most critical risks first. This ensures both safety of users and the structural integrity of the building, while also preventing further damage through appropriate maintenance. This approach aligns with the two primary perspectives drawn from the partners' contributions: first, the risk of structural collapse and safety loss (pyramidal model A), and second, the management of minor pathologies to avert more severe and costly damage (centralised model B), as illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Visualisation of the perspective on the TI headings relevance from some partners versus the one for another

To determine the sequence of inspection phases, several key aspects were considered:

- 1. Foundations and Structures:** Issues in this area can lead to catastrophic collapses, directly impacting user safety. Pathologies such as cracks, differential settlement and material deterioration cannot be mitigated solely through the maintenance of roofs and façades, as they are often caused by external factors or ground movements. Therefore, ensuring structural stability is an essential first step.
- 2. Façades and Roofs:** As the primary barriers against climatic and environmental forces, proper maintenance of façades and roofs is essential. This helps prevent water infiltration, which can accelerate internal structural degradation and cause significant material damage. Preserving the building's exterior condition is vital to maintaining its overall integrity.
- 3. Installations:** Modernising and maintaining internal systems, such as electrical, plumbing and HVAC, is necessary for ensuring user safety and comfort. Failures in these systems can be costly and hazardous, potentially leading to fires, floods or other severe damage that compromises both the building's structure and its habitability.
- 4. Biodegradation, Water tightness, and Beauty:** Controlling biodegradation and ensuring water tightness are fundamental for preserving building materials. Maintaining the building's aesthetic value is also important for its heritage significance, often in line with legislation that protects CH buildings.
- 5. Accessibility:** Enhancing accessibility is essential to ensure that all individuals, regardless of ability, can access and enjoy the building. This is both a regulatory requirement and a social and cultural responsibility.
- 6. Functional Behaviour:** Implementing intelligent systems optimises resource use and enhances the building's functionality and efficiency. These systems facilitate advanced monitoring and control, allowing early detection of potential issues and contributing to ongoing preventive maintenance. However, achieving this level of development in heritage

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building is uncommon, depending on the building’s protection status and available resources.

The pyramid structure (A) has been identified as the optimal approach for prioritising the phases of the TI. It **emphasises the structural safety and integrity** of the building, beginning with the foundations and structure to prevent collapse and ensure user safety. This method also prioritises protecting the building envelope to avoid internal damage. The logical sequence of the pyramid addresses the most critical issues first, followed by retrofitting, accessibility and intelligent systems, ensuring a safe and efficient methodology while supporting the sustainable long-term maintenance. In contrast, the centralised structure (B), though useful for preventive maintenance, lacks the same clarity in risk prioritisation.

The key factors that led to this choice include:

- Structural safety
- Building protection and optimal preservation of the envelope
- Logical maintenance sequence
- Ease of application and risk control

To continue research towards establishing a European baseline, the following tables present standards and procedures currently used, based on the technical experience of partners in Spain, Poland and the Netherlands (Spanish: Table 4; Polish: Table 5; and Dutch: Table 6).

Table 4: Spanish contribution on the main reference standards and procedures

Reference standards <i>SPAIN</i>	National legislation	European legislation	Local expert knowledge	Quantifying expert knowledge	How is the inspection carried out?
Foundations and Structure	UNE-EN 17121:2020 UNE 41805-4:2009 IN UNE 41805-7:2009 IN UNE 41805-8:2009 IN	-	Pathology analysis and damage inspection	Detection of cracks 3mm thick or more Discovery of movements, turns and displacements	Drone Monitor system
Façades and Roofs	UNE 41811:2017	-	Pathology analysis and damage inspection	Detection of cracks 3mm thick or more Material losses Biodeterioration	Visual analysis by an expert
Installations	UNE-EN 15759-1:2012 ITC-BT-28 REBT RITE IEE regional standards	EN 16883:2018	-	-	-
Biodegradation, water tightness and beauty	Municipal planning legislation	-	-	-	-

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Reference standards <i>SPAIN</i>	National legislation	European legislation	Local expert knowledge	Quantifying expert knowledge	How is the inspection carried out?
Accessibility	UNE 41531:2018 IN CTE DB-SUA9 ⁶	-	Depending on the needs of disabled persons or reduced mobility	Assessment of access (ramps, automatic doors, dimensions, etc.), presence of tactile and auditory signage, and of adapted furniture and equipment.	Visual analysis by an expert
Functional behaviour	-	Directive 2014/24/EU	-	Inspection by authorised agency	Multi-tester

Table 5: Polish contribution on the main reference standards and procedures

Reference standards <i>POLAND</i>	National regulation	European regulation	Local expert knowledge	Quantifying expert knowledge	How is the inspection carried out?
Foundations and Structure	Regulation of Ministry of Infrastructure on the technical conditions to be met by buildings and their location from 12 th of April 2002 with the updates ⁷	-	Pathologies analysis and visual inspection of damages	Dimension of the cracks Damage scale of the building Condition of structural construction	Visual analysis by an expert, for cracks use of Crack indicator, crack gauge, photos
Façades and Roofs	National law: Act on the protection and care of historical monuments from 23 July 2003 Local law: local zoning plan or zoning decision (for a specific building plot)	-		(From Very Good to Emergency)	Visual analysis by an expert, photos
Installations	Regulation of Ministry of Infrastructure on the technical conditions to be met by buildings and their location from 12 th of April 2002 with the updates ⁸	-	-	-	Visual analysis by an expert, photos
Biodegradation, water tightness and beauty	Municipal planning legislation	-	-	-	-

⁶ <https://www.codigotecnico.org/pdf/Documentos/SUA/DccSUA.pdf>

⁷ <https://isap.sejm.gov.pl/isap.nsf/download.xsp/WDU20220001225/O/D20221225.pdf>

⁸ <https://isap.sejm.gov.pl/isap.nsf/download.xsp/WDU20220001225/O/D20221225.pdf>

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Reference standards <i>POLAND</i>	National regulation	European regulation	Local expert knowledge	Quantifying expert knowledge	How is the inspection carried out?
Accessibility	Regulation of Ministry of Infrastructure on the technical conditions to be met by buildings and their location from 12 th of April 2002 with the updates ⁹	-	Depend on the building type (museum, library, residential building, etc.)	-	Visual analysis by an expert
Functional behaviour	-	Directive 2014/24/EU			-

Table 6: Dutch contribution on the main reference standards and procedures

Main reference standards <i>NETHERLANDS</i>	National regulation	European regulation	Local expert knowledge	Quantifying expert knowledge	How is the inspection carried out?
Foundations and Structure	URL 1001 NEN 6700:2018		Expertise for specific materials and impact of water and humidity	Should be done by an expert which can be assessed based on work experience and other qualifications such as degree, references and certificates (roughly counts for all the 6 headings)	Documentation of the historic building/monument is collected (construction drawings, maintenance reports, and pictures from earlier inspections) Checklists with visual inspections performed by an expert. Specific measurements: Thickness of roof, humidity and temperature
Façades and Roofs	URL 4010 URL 2006 NEN 6707:2011 nl	-			
Installations	NEN 2767 NEN 7370:2017 URL 2005:2020 URL 4005:2018 URL 5005:2020	EN 16883:2017	-	-	Previous inspection reports, testing the installations
Biodegradation, water tightness and beauty	NEN-EN 113:2019	EN 16281:2015 EN 16289:2015 EN 16581:2015	-	-	Degradation reports, changes in climate and precipitation
Accessibility	NEN 1814:2001 nl NEN 3140:2020	-	-	Safety regulation experts	-

⁹ <https://isap.sejm.gov.pl/isap.nsf/download.xsp/WDU20220001225/O/D20221225.pdf>

Main reference standards	National regulation	European regulation	Local expert knowledge	Quantifying expert knowledge	How is the inspection carried out?
NETHERLANDS					
Functional behaviour	-	EN-ISO 52120 EN 17458-1:2020 EN 17458-2:2020	-	More technical expertise in direction of data engineer	-

Experience and expertise in traditional work are crucial for tackling the complexities of heritage building conservation and establishing a unified approach to developing a TI methodology. To achieve a robust EU-wide framework in this area, it is essential to conduct comprehensive research into the key characteristics of CH buildings and perform an in-depth analysis of relevant European standards. This research will serve as the foundation for shaping the methodology for the technical inspection of CH buildings across the European Union.

2.2.1. Key points about the expert knowledge

The evolution of architecture has been shaped by conceptual, technical and social transformations that have redefined the perception of space and its qualities. In this context, Le Corbusier, one of the most relevant architects of the International Style, introduced his “5 points of Modern Architecture” in 1929, which have significantly impacted the evolution of building envelopes and structures.

Le Corbusier’s “5 points of Modern Architecture”, outlined in *Towards a New Architecture* (Le Corbusier, 1931 [26]), are as follows:

1. **Pilotis.** Replacing ground-floor load-bearing walls with a grid of reinforced concrete pillars, offering a new spatial freedom.
2. **Free design of the floor plan.** With the building raised on free-standing pillars and no supporting walls, the ground floor is left open for flexible use.
3. **Free design of the façade.** By separating the building’s exterior protective function from its structural function, the façade becomes free from conventional constraints.
4. **Horizontal windows.** The absence of load-bearing walls allows for expansive windows, maximising natural light.
5. **Roof garden.** This not only protects the roof but also creates a new experience for the building’s users.

Le Corbusier’s approach, seen as a symbol of disrupted modernity, revolutionised materials, construction systems and aesthetics. These changes laid the foundation for contemporary architecture.

Understanding the historical and conceptual evolution of building envelopes and structures is crucial for developing the TI methodology. This perspective allows to identify fundamental conditions relevant to heritage buildings.

- **Before 1920** (Traditional Architecture)

Traditional architecture, as illustrated in Figure 6 (left), features structures where the envelope and structure are intrinsically linked. Heritage construction materials like stone, clay and timber defined

both the structural framework and the façades and roofs. Any alteration to the envelope directly impacted the structure, and vice versa.

- **Between 1920-1930** (Conceptual Changes Post-Industrial Revolution)

The industrial revolution introduced new materials and construction techniques that allowed the separation of a building's structure from its envelope. This paradigm shift enabled greater flexibility in design, with free floor plans and non-load-bearing façades featuring large windows.

- **After 1930** (Modern Architecture)

Figure 6 (right) illustrates a modern building embodying Le Corbusier's principles. Here, an independent structural framework supports the load, allowing façades and roofs to be designed separately. This innovation enabled creative designs and the use of materials like steel and glass, aligning with modern aesthetic and functional demands.

Figure 6: Heritage building stock comparison between traditional architecture and modern architecture principles

Given these historical shifts, two distinct scenarios in the TI methodology should be addressed: traditional buildings, where the foundation, structure, façades and roofs are integrated; and modern buildings, where the structure and envelope are distinct and require separate assessment.

In heritage buildings, the integration of structure and envelope necessitates that TI methodology addresses both aspects together. This connection is vital for accurate inspection and preservation efforts:

- **Structures and Foundations:**

Made from stone, earth or timber, these elements support both the building and external loads (e.g. wind, seismic). Deterioration directly affects overall stability.

- **Façades and Roofs:**

These components protect the building’s interior and contribute to structural integrity. Damage to façades and roofs can compromise the building’s conservation, as in the case of load-bearing ashlar stone walls that also serve as exterior façades.

Recognising these considerations is essential for developing an effective TI methodology of CH buildings. The materials and construction techniques used throughout history have evolved based on available resources and societal needs. The Industrial Revolution, in particular, brought about significant changes in aesthetics, spatial perception and construction methods.

To implement the TI methodology effectively, it is crucial to account for various scenarios defined by the typology of heritage buildings, particularly, concerning the materials and techniques employed in their construction.

Figure 7 showcases a selection of materials and construction systems commonly used in heritage buildings. This reference will guide decision-making in defining and adjusting the Technical Inspection process to meet the specific requirements of different buildings.

Materials and Construction systems
Differences between contexts:

Material	Construction System	Description	Material	Construction System	Description
Wood	Solid Timber	Use of solid timber pieces or logs.	Concrete	Reinforced Concrete	Concrete mixture with steel reinforcement.
	Half-Timbered (Fachwerk)	Wooden structures filled with brick or clay.		Precast Concrete	Concrete elements manufactured in a plant and transported to the site.
Stone	Dry Stone Masonry	Stone constructions without mortar.	Wood	Glued Laminated Timber (Glulam)	Pieces of wood bonded by gluing layers of wood.
	Mortared Stone Masonry	Use of stone joined with mortar to form walls.		Steel	Steel Structures
Clay	Adobe	Dried mud bricks.	Steel framing		Lightweight system of galvanized steel profiles
	Rammed Earth	Technique of compacted earth in formworks	Curtain Wall		
Brick & Block	Brick Masonry	Construction with bricks joined by mortar			

Figure 7: Comparison of the different context of the materials and construction systems in traditional and modern architecture

In the next steps, one key objective will be to analyse the main characteristics of historic materials, focusing on damage, degradation and pathologies. Additionally, information on tests and tools frequently used to assess the state of conservation of heritage buildings will be gathered.

2.3. Landscape of European standardisation – Conservation of Cultural Heritage (CEN/TC 346) as a foundation for the TI methodology

Building upon the partners’ contributions summarised in the reference standards tables (Table 4, Table 5 and Table 6, in section 2.2), it is essential to delve into the European standards framework that governs Cultural Heritage conservation. This framework is fundamental to strengthening the foundation of the TI methodology.

Annex 1 presents a comprehensive list of CEN and ISO technical committees that have been selected for their relevance to cultural heritage buildings. Among these, the analysis of CEN/TC 345 stands out due to its significant influence of the TI headings and its overall impact on the methodology.

The scope of the **CEN/TC 346 – Conservation of Cultural Heritage**¹⁰ encompasses various facets crucial to preserving tangible CH. This includes the characterisation of materials, processes, methodologies and documentation involved in conservation efforts. By doing so, CEN/TC 346 supports the preservation, protection and maintenance of CH, enhancing its value and significance. Additionally, it addresses the characterisation of deterioration processes, environmental conditions affecting CH, and the products and technologies used in conservation, restoration, repair and maintenance efforts.

Also, the CEN/TC 346 is organised into several work groups (WG) that focus on distinct aspects of cultural heritage conservation:

- CEN/TC 346/WG 11 Conservation process
- CEN/TC 346/WG 12 Showcases
- CEN/TC 346/WG 15 Exhibition lighting of cultural heritage
- CEN/TC 346/WG 17 Management and monitoring of built heritage
- CEN/TC 346/WG 18 Characterisation, preservation, and management of archaeological sites
- CEN/TC 346/WG 19 Management and protection of collections
- CEN/TC 346/WG 3 Characterisation of materials constituting cultural heritage and evaluation of conservation treatments
- CEN/TC 346/WG 7 Specifying and measuring Indoor/outdoor climate
- CEN/TC 346/WG 9 Waterlogged wood

An in-depth analysis of the standards associated with CEN/TC 346 has been conducted (refer to Figure 9 to Figure 15) to aid in the development of an effective and practical TI methodology for conservation and maintenance managers. To streamline the selection and evaluation of relevant standards, a thematic classification was created. This classification organises the standards by headings that will guide the TI of heritage buildings.

The thematic areas considered for the analysis are: ● Execution, ● Documentation and research, ● Visual inspection of pathologies, ● Diagnostic, ● Test and characterization of materials, ● Tools and devise, ● Maintenance, and ● Intervention.

In the analysis, the difference in colour illustrates the level or extent of information provided by each standard (Figure 8). This colour-coding helps to identify the depth and applicability of the standards, making it easier to navigate and apply them within the context of heritage building conservation and technical inspection.

	High contribution
	Complementary information

Figure 8: Colour coding for the following figures, based on the level or extent of information provided

¹⁰

https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0::::FSP_ORG_ID:411453&cs=1CF54B40A1F71DDBD7991221E377664AE

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● Foundations and Structure

Standard	Name	CEN/TC	Execution	Documentation and Research	Inspection (Pathologies detection)	Diagnosis (Specifications on the report and methodology)	Material Characterization and tests	Tools	Maintenance	Intervention	Relevant Information
EN 17121:2019	Conservation of cultural heritage - Historic timber structures - Guidelines for the on-site assessment of load-bearing timber structures	CEN/TC 346									
EN 17187:2020	Conservation of Cultural Heritage - Characterization of mortars used in cultural heritage	CEN/TC 346									
EN 16515:2015	Conservation of Cultural Heritage - Guidelines to characterize natural stone used in cultural heritage	CEN/TC 346									
EN 16682:2017	Conservation of cultural heritage - Methods of measurement of moisture content, or water content, in materials constituting immovable cultural heritage	CEN/TC 346									
EN 16085:2012	Conservation of Cultural property - Methodology for sampling from materials of cultural property - General rules	CEN/TC 346									
EN 16302:2013	Conservation of cultural heritage - Test methods - Measurement of water absorption by pipe method	CEN/TC 346									
EN 16322:2013	Conservation of Cultural Heritage - Test methods - Determination of drying properties	CEN/TC 346									
EN 16455:2014	Conservation of cultural heritage - Extraction and determination of soluble salts in natural stone and related materials used in and from cultural heritage	CEN/TC 346									

Figure 9: Foundations and Structure analysis from the standards of CEN/RC 346

● Façades and Roofs

Standard	Name	CEN/TC	Execution	Documentation and Research	Inspection (Pathologies detection)	Diagnosis (Specifications on the report and methodology)	Material Characterisation and tests	Tools	Maintenance	Intervention	Relevant Information
EN 17187:2020	Conservation of Cultural Heritage - Characterization of mortars used in cultural heritage	CEN/TC 346									
EN 16515:2015	Conservation of Cultural Heritage - Guidelines to characterize natural stone used in cultural heritage	CEN/TC 346									
EN 16682:2017	Conservation of cultural heritage - Methods of measurement of moisture content, or water content, in materials constituting immovable cultural heritage	CEN/TC 346									
EN 16085:2012	Conservation of Cultural property - Methodology for sampling from materials of cultural property - General rules	CEN/TC 346									
EN 16302:2013	Conservation of cultural heritage - Test methods - Measurement of water absorption by pipe method	CEN/TC 346									
EN 16322:2013	Conservation of Cultural Heritage - Test methods - Determination of drying properties	CEN/TC 346									
EN 16455:2014	Conservation of cultural heritage - Extraction and determination of soluble salts in natural stone and related materials used in and from cultural heritage	CEN/TC 346									
EN 17543:2021	Conservation of Cultural Heritage - Finishes of built heritage - Investigation and documentation	CEN/TC 346									

Figure 10: Façades and Roofs analysis from the standards of CEN/RC 346

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● Installations and Facilities

Standard	Name	CEN/TC	Execution	Documentation and Research	Inspection (Pathologies detection)	Diagnosis (Specifications on the report and methodology)	Material Characterisation and tests	Tools	Maintenance	Intervention	Relevant Information
EN 15759-1:2011	<i>Conservation of cultural property - Indoor climate - Part 1: Guidelines for heating churches, chapels and other places of worship</i>	CEN/TC 346									
EN 15759-2:2018	<i>Conservation of cultural heritage - Indoor climate - Part 2: Ventilation management for the protection of cultural heritage buildings and collections</i>	CEN/TC 346									
EN 16242:2012	<i>Conservation of cultural heritage - Procedures and instruments for measuring humidity in the air and moisture exchanges between air and cultural property</i>	CEN/TC 346									

Figure 11: Installations and Facilities analysis from the standards of CEN/RC 346

● Biodegradation, water tightness and beauty

Standard	Name	CEN/TC	Execution	Documentation and Research	Inspection (Pathologies detection)	Diagnosis (Specifications on the report and methodology)	Material Characterisation and tests	Tools	Maintenance	Intervention	Relevant Information
EN 16790:2016	<i>EN 16790:2016 Conservation of cultural heritage - Integrated pest management (IPM) for protection of cultural heritage</i>	CEN/TC 346									
EN 16893:2018	<i>Conservation of Cultural Heritage - Specifications for location, construction and modification of buildings or rooms intended for the storage or use of heritage collections</i>	CEN/TC 346									

Figure 12: Biodegradation, water tightness and beauty analysis from the standards of CEN/RC 346

● Accessibility

Standard	Name	CEN/TC	Execution	Documentation and Research	Inspection (Pathologies detection)	Diagnosis (Specifications on the report and methodology)	Material Characterisation and tests	Tools	Maintenance	Intervention	Relevant Information
EN 16893:2018	<i>Conservation of Cultural Heritage - Specifications for location, construction and modification of buildings or rooms intended for the storage or use of heritage collections</i>	CEN/TC 346									Fire Safety

Figure 13: Accessibility analysis from the standards of CEN/RC 346

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● Functional behaviour

Standard	Name	CEN/TC	Execution	Documentation and Research	Inspection (Pathologies detection)	Diagnosis (Specifications on the report and methodology)	Material Characterisation and tests	Tools	Maintenance	Intervention	Relevant Information
EN 16883:2017	Conservation of cultural heritage - Guidelines for improving the energy performance of historic buildings	CEN/TC 346									Appendix B (Assessment template)
EN 16242:2012	Conservation of cultural heritage - Procedures and instruments for measuring humidity in the air and moisture exchanges between air and cultural property	CEN/TC 346									
EN 16893:2018	Conservation of Cultural Heritage - Specifications for location, construction and modification of buildings or rooms intended for the storage or use of heritage collections	CEN/TC 346									Fire Safety

Figure 14: Functional behaviour analysis from the standards of CEN/RC 346

● Common contributions for all the inspection headings

Standard	Name	CEN/TC	Execution	Documentation and Research	Visual Inspection (Pathologies detection)	Diagnosis (Specifications on the report and methodology)	Material Characterisation and tests	Tools	Maintenance	Intervention	Relevant Information
EN 16096:2012	Conservation of cultural property - Condition survey and report of built cultural heritage	CEN/TC 346									
EN 15898:2019	Conservation of cultural heritage - Main general terms and definitions	CEN/TC 346									
EN 16572:2015	Conservation of cultural heritage - Glossary of technical terms concerning mortars for masonry, renders and plasters used in cultural heritage	CEN/TC 346									
EN 16853:2017	Conservation of cultural heritage - Conservation process - Decision making, planning and implementation	CEN/TC 346									

Figure 15: Common contributions for all the inspection headings analysis from the standards of CEN/RC 346

After analysing the content of CEN/TC 346 and considering the issues presented in this document, it has been determined that aspects related to Biodegradation, water tightness and beauty considerations should be integrated into the existing headings of Foundations and Structure and Façades and Roofs. Consequently, these aspects will be incorporated into these headings, as illustrated in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Headings structure of the Technical Inspection methodology according to CEN/TC 346

Additionally, the review has identified gaps in the standards concerning historical materials and accessibility. To address these gaps, further examination will be conducted on European Directives, such as the European Accessibility Act¹¹, as well as Spanish regulations on CH conservation. Spain, with the third largest number of UNESCO-protected cultural heritage buildings globally (following China and Italy), provides a valuable reference due to its extensive experience and adherence to UNESCO principles.

Therefore, Spanish standards will serve as a complementary framework for conducting Technical Inspections. Annex 1 lists the most significant Spanish regulations selected for this propose.

2.4. Initial conclusions to consider for the Technical Inspection methodology of historic buildings

The preliminary conclusions drawn from this deliverable highlight key considerations for developing an effective methodology for inspecting historic buildings:

- **Prioritisation of structural integrity:** The methodology should first address the structural integrity of buildings, as it is crucial for the safety of the workers responsible for the conservation works, as well as the overall stability of the structure.
- **Comprehensive inspection framework:** The methodology must offer a standardised approach that comprehensively addresses all critical aspects of historic buildings. This includes evaluating risks and maintenance needs related to construction systems, materials and prevalent pathologies.
- **Legal and regulatory considerations:** It is essential that the methodology aligns with local and international heritage conservation laws and standards. This involves understanding and integrating various levels of protection and legal requirements into the inspection process to support effective maintenance and conservation planning.

¹¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32019L0882>

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- **Integration of modern technologies:** Embracing digital technologies, such as Heritage Building Information Modelling (H-BIM) (INHERIT service 8), should be considered to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of inspections.

These conclusions advocate for a strategic approach to CH conservation, ensuring that interventions are efficient, resilient, cost-effective, accessible and sustainable. Decisions made throughout this process have been driven by a thorough analysis of the complexities involved in maintaining heritage assets, with an emphasis on innovative methods to optimise conservation efforts and resource use.

3. Assessment and monitoring framework

To complement the inspection methodology, the assessment and monitoring framework developed in the INHERIT project assesses the current status of the CH buildings and enable to monitor them across four pillars (Figure 17).

Figure 17: INHERIT pillars for the assessment and monitoring framework

The first pillar focuses on the energy performance and the smart readiness of the CH buildings, as well as analysing the IEQ, tailoring it to the CH needs due to the presence of ancient and historical artefacts or the specific environmental conditions for preservation. The second pillar is about the ways that resource efficiency measures and circular economy approach can be integrated in the heritage buildings to improve their LCC, balancing the circular economy principles with the preservation of the historical and architectural integrity of the building. The third pillar assesses the CH sites' resilience through a multi-variate analysis to evaluate the risks in certain areas and categorise the levels of such risks. The fourth pillar focuses on the social side of the CH buildings, by delving into the accessibility, inclusiveness and openness or other related aspects.

Each pillar is defined by macro-objectives and a set of key performance indicators (KPIs) to be assessed and monitored. These objectives and KPIs are based on an intense literature review, leveraging on existing assessment methodologies, such as Level(s)¹², or the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI)¹³. They are detailed in the section dedicated to each of them (sections 3.1, 3.2, 3.3 and 3.4 respectively).

The assessment methodology will be used in the INHERIT pilots for the ex-ante and for the ex-post, after the deployment and application of the INHERIT services.

In the following Table 7, the relation of the INHERIT services (s.0 to s.10) with the pillars of the Assessment and Monitoring framework can be seen. This complements the Table 2 from the introduction that depicts the services that are applied to the pilots.

¹² https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/circular-economy/levels_en

¹³ https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficient-buildings/smart-readiness-indicator_en

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Table 7: INHERIT services’ relation with the pillars from the Assessment and Monitoring Framework

Heritage Building Lifecycle	INHERIT services	Assessment and Monitoring Framework			
		Pillar 1 Energy & Comfort	Pillar 2 Resource & Circularity	Pillar 3 Climate Resilience	Pillar 4 Accessibility & Sustainability
-	Smartification & Data Exchange Platform	s.0			
Design & Renovation	Interactive screen use & AR-VR interfaces	s.1			
	Modelling & simulation environment	s.2			
	Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	s.3			
Monitoring, operation & management	Indoor environmental quality & comfort optimisation	s.4			
	Energy forecasting & data-driven intelligent management	s.5			
	Digital Twin for heritage facilities’ real-time monitoring	s.6			
	Real-time insights on activity and mobility patterns	s.7			
Preservation & maintenance	Preventive maintenance with H-BIM	s.8			
	GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance	s.9			
	Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios	s.10			

The development of the INHERIT framework, led by CARTIF as task leader, was structured around the four pillars, each managed by designated partners as outlined in the Grant Agreement (part B): ICCS for Pillar 1, CARTIF for Pillars 2 and 3, and FASADA and ISSO for Pillar 4. The process began with defining the macro-objectives for each pillar and establishing corresponding assessment criteria, including an initial set of KPIs. Multiple feedback rounds, particularly with pilot leaders, ensured the KPIs were practical and applicable. The objectives and KPIs were then consolidated, with detailed procedures for their assessment, including criteria, required data and calculation methods. Further validation rounds with task partners finalised the KPIs, ensuring a comprehensive and practical assessment framework.

This comprehensive framework of indicators will serve to evaluate the impacts of the services applied to each of the pilots, based on a baseline defining the performance and status of the CH sites (mainly buildings) before the deployment of the services.

The Key Performance Indicators are an essential tool in the monitoring and evaluation process to measure the progress towards achieving goals and objectives. A KPI is a quantifiable measure of performance over time for a specific objective. KPIs can be either qualitative or quantitative, and play a critical role in the monitoring and evaluation process by providing specific metrics that can be tracked and evaluated to determine the achievement of the objectives and impact with respect to a baseline.

Thus, a KPI is also a design support tool that provides to the designer a quick feedback on the performance achieved and support design loops for performance optimisation. KPIs also are decision support tools to compare and identify the best option according to the stakeholders’ preferences. Finally, they are also communication tools, that serve to summarise and explain the performance of a design choice to non-technical users.

3.1. Pillar 1: Energy Performance and IEQ

CH buildings are typically exempt from strict energy-related requirements (Buda et al., 2022 [27]). However, many CH buildings are commonly used for functions involving the everyday presence of people. In such settings, energy efficiency is desired, while indoor environmental conditions have also to be suitable for the building's use. In this respect, building owners and managers often perform renovation work with the objective to enhance the technical infrastructure of CH buildings, tackle thermal and damp-related problems, and improve the resultant indoor air quality and overall comfort of the building's users, subjected however to constraints that ensure the conservation of their CH assets¹⁴.

When considering renovation and energy modernization actions in CH buildings, an improvement in the indoor conditions and the achievement of parameters that are typical for energy-efficient buildings often leads to an improvement in the overall environmental performance of the building as well. Some reasons that point out the importance of the IEQ are the following:

- Health and well-being
- Productivity and performance
- Occupant satisfaction
- Energy efficiency
- Regulatory compliance
- Sustainable design
- Employee retention and attraction
- Reduced liability

INHERIT Pillar 1, “Energy Performance & IEQ”, aligns with Level(s) macro objective 4: “**Healthy and comfortable spaces**”. This objective focuses on creating buildings that are comfort, attractiveness and productivity while protecting human health. Key areas of assessment include **indoor air quality, time outside of the thermal comfort range, lighting and visual comfort, and acoustics and protection against noise**. Improving IEQ is essential for occupant health and well-being, requiring a holistic approach that addresses air quality, thermal comfort, lighting and noise conditions. Based on these factors, a set of KPIs were established to monitor energy performance and IEQ at the INHERIT pilot sites, measuring the effectiveness of interventions.

RELEVANT IEQ STANDARDS

The design and evaluation of the indoor environment in buildings usually rely on national and international standards such as EN¹⁵, ISO¹⁶, and ASHRAE¹⁷ which are used to specify indoor environmental conditions that can be considered as safe and acceptable from most of the occupants¹⁸. IEQ involves four components, namely **Thermal Comfort (TC)**, **Air Quality (AQ)**, **Visual Comfort (VC)**, and **Acoustic Comfort (AC)**, as follows:

¹⁴ <https://standards.iteh.ai/catalog/standards/cen/189eac8d-14e1-4810-8ebd-1e852b3effa3/en-16883-2017>

¹⁵ European Standard (EN): <https://www.en-standard.eu/>

¹⁶ International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO): <https://www.iso.org/home.html>

¹⁷ American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning Engineers (ASHRAE): <https://www.ashrae.org/>

¹⁸ Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) implementation tools: https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficient-buildings/smart-readiness-indicator/sri-implementation-tools_en

- **TC:** Assesses mainly the air temperature and humidity within a space to ensure that occupants are comfortable and productive.
- **AQ:** Measures the presence of pollutants, allergens, and other contaminants in the indoor air. The parameter most used to evaluate AQ, however, is the concentration of CO₂, although volatile organic compounds and particulate matter are also considered in some applications.
- **VC:** Lighting quality considers the amount, type, and distribution of light within a space. It addresses factors like illuminance, colour temperature, and glare to ensure optimal visual comfort and support various activities.
- **AC:** Acoustic quality assesses the noise levels and sound characteristics within a building. It considers factors such as background noise, reverberation, and speech intelligibility to create an environment conducive to communication and concentration

Although it is important for building designers to consider all IEQ components, requirements for each component are often split up into the existing standards. For example, ASHRAE standards only consider one IEQ component, namely either TC or ventilation for acceptable AQ. CEN and ISO have tried to integrate various IEQ components into one standard, but while they have succeeded in including a complete set of requirements for TC and AQ, they have only partly included requirements for VC and AC, which are addressed in separate standards¹⁹. From all the international standards, in the context of the INHERIT project, the international standard EN 16798-1:2019 was considered more applicable. Below are presented the reasons for this preference:

- **International applicability:** EN standards are European standards, which means they are widely accepted and applied across European countries, making them more relevant for the examined pilots.
- **Comprehensive approach:** EN 16798-1:2019 provides a comprehensive approach to the assessment of TC, including considerations for various aspects, such as indoor air temperature and humidity. This holistic approach is beneficial in ensuring a more accurate evaluation of TC conditions.
- **Integration with other standards:** EN 16798-1:2019 is part of a series of standards that cover various aspects of energy performance in buildings. If the goal is to integrate TC considerations with broader energy performance assessments, then the EN standards provide a more cohesive framework.
- **European regulatory compliance:** Since all INHERIT pilot sites are located in European countries, they need to comply with European regulations, as demonstrated in EN 16798-1:2019. Note that EN 16798-1 is a non-obligatory standard in the EPB (Energy Performance of Building) standard series. Nevertheless, EU member states can use elements from the standard to improve their national building codes. Therefore, the standard can provide indicative values in case a local building code does not have any special requirements (e.g. new or renovated buildings).

Table 8 presents some of the IEQ parameters and thresholds considered in the EN 16798-1 standard. These parameters and thresholds are used in typical energy calculations for offices, schools, dwellings, and other indoor environments that are primarily meant for human occupancy, as is the

¹⁹ https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficient-buildings/smart-readiness-indicator/sri-implementation-tools_en

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case with all INHERIT pilots. The standard does so not by specifying design methods, leaving manufacturers free to provide their own, but by providing ranges for the parameters that need to be respected in the design and operation of heating, cooling, ventilation, and lighting systems. Specifically, the standard defines three categories in terms of required comfort and specifies the parameter ranges accordingly, as follows:

- *Category I:* High level of expectation (spaces occupied by very sensitive and fragile persons with special requirements).
- *Category II:* Normal level of expectation (new buildings and renovations).
- *Category III:* Moderate level of expectation (existing buildings).

Table 8: Thresholds considered by the EN 16798 - 1:2019 standard for various IEQ parameters.

IEQ aspect	Building/space type	Category			Remarks
		I	II	III	
Temperature range (winter)	Residential buildings (bedrooms)	21-25 °C	20-25 °C	18-25 °C	These are operative temperatures, assuming a clothing insulation value of 0.5 in summer and 1.0 in winter, with activity level of 1.2 met.
	Offices (landscape layout)	21-23 °C	20-24 °C	19-25 °C	
	Schools (classrooms)	21-23 °C	20-24 °C	19-25 °C	
Temperature range (summer)	Residential buildings (bedrooms)	23.5-25.5 °C	23-26 °C	22-27 °C	
	Offices (landscape layout)	23.5-25.5 °C	23-26 °C	22-27 °C	
	Schools (classrooms)	23.5-25.5 °C	23-26 °C	22-27 °C	
Maximum CO ₂ level (delta CO ₂ concentration)	Residential buildings (bedrooms)	380 ppm	550 ppm	950 ppm	Acceptable ppm levels above outdoor levels.
	Offices (landscape layout)	550 ppm	800 ppm	1.350 ppm	
	Schools (classrooms)	550 ppm	800 ppm	1.350 ppm	
Humidity range	All types of building	30-50 %	25-60 %	20-70 %	
Minimum lighting level (\bar{E}_m)	Residential buildings (living room)	-			\bar{E}_m is the minimum maintained illuminance.
	Offices (landscape layout)	500 lux			Values are in line with EN 12464-1.
	Schools (classrooms)	500 lux			
Maximum system noise level (LAeq)	Residential buildings (bedrooms)	25 dB	30 dB	35 dB	LAeq is the A-weighted, equivalent continuous sound level, in decibels having the same total sound energy as the fluctuating level measured.
	Offices (landscape layout)	35 dB	40 dB	45dB	
	Schools (classrooms)	30 dB	34 dB	38 dB	

The thresholds provided per IEQ parameter and category will effectively serve as the basis for evaluating the IEQ of the INHERIT pilot buildings. Specifically, the limits utilized within the defined IEQ KPIs correspond to the minimum thresholds assumed by the EN 16798-1:2019 international

standard (European Commission, 2020a [28]) as acceptable per case. The motivation of this choice is aligned with the nature of the CH buildings and their limitations; since CH buildings are particularly old and cannot be completely renovated, achieving high comfort should be encouraged but not mandatory.

For instance, when it comes to TC, maintaining the indoor air temperature in winter within the 21-23 °C range is considered exceptional and appropriate for spaces occupied by very sensitive persons with special requirements, within the 20-24 °C range normal and appropriate for new buildings and renovations, while within the 19-25 °C range moderate and appropriate for existing buildings. Therefore, the ranges of Category III are adopted in the present framework, although different thresholds can be defined for each building based on its objectives and particularities (e.g. presence of assets of particular CH value).

SRI – Smart Readiness Indicator

The SRI is an emerging framework that evaluates the building's readiness for smart technologies and systems integration. It measures the level of intelligence and connectivity within the building infrastructure, including sensors, automation systems, and data analytics capabilities. The SRI assesses factors such as the availability of digital infrastructure, interoperability of smart devices, and the ability to adapt to future technological advancements. Typically represented on a 0-100 scale, the SRI provides insights into the building's capacity to optimize energy efficiency, enhance occupant comfort, and improve operational performance through the deployment of smart solutions. Monitoring changes in the SRI over time enables stakeholders to identify opportunities for enhancing the building's intelligence and resilience in the face of evolving energy challenges and technological innovations. Increasing the SRI value signifies progress towards transforming the building into a more sustainable, responsive, and user-centric environment, aligned with the principles of smart and connected cities.

The concept of SRI was introduced in 2017, following the release of a technical study by the EC, which attempted to define SRI and develop a draft methodology for its calculation. However, the pivotal moment in establishing SRI came with the recast of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) in 2018 (Directive 2018/844/EU²⁰). This directive formally introduced SRI as an optional EU scheme for rating the smart readiness of buildings. Subsequent regulations (Commission Delegated Regulation 2020²¹; Commission Implementing Regulation 2020²²) and technical studies initiated the testing phase for SRI. EU member countries have the option to adopt and implement this assessment scheme, with support from the SRI support team. This team was created to provide technical guidance and assistance, serving as the official intermediary between the EC and the Member States.

The implementation of the SRI methodology serves various key objectives and offers numerous benefits for individual buildings and broader urban and environmental goals. Evaluating the SRI for buildings holds significant importance for several reasons. First, it prioritizes energy efficiency by assessing a building's readiness to integrate and optimize smart technologies. This assessment guides the implementation of energy-saving measures and technologies, enabling stakeholders to identify opportunities for reducing energy consumption and operational costs. It empowers building

²⁰ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2018/844/oj>

²¹ https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg_del/2020/692/oj

²² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32020R1197>

owners, managers, and occupants to make informed decisions regarding investments in smart technologies and energy-efficient upgrades. Second, the SRI encourages the integration of various smart systems and devices within buildings, promoting interoperability and compatibility between different technologies. This ensures seamless functionality and efficiency across building automation systems, energy management, indoor air quality, lighting controls, and more. On a broader scale, widespread adoption of smart technologies in buildings can significantly contribute to sustainability goals and reduce the carbon footprint of urban environments. The SRI assessment aids policymakers and urban planners in crafting effective regulations and incentives to promote smart technology adoption in buildings. The benefits resulting from the SRI implementation are extensive:

- It leads to significant energy savings by optimizing energy consumption through smart systems, sensors, and controls.
- Identifies cost-effective strategies for managing energy use, maintenance schedules, and equipment performance, reducing operational and maintenance costs.
- Improves occupant comfort, health, and convenience, enhancing their overall living or working experience.
- Increases market value of buildings with higher SRI scores due to improved performance, energy efficiency, and potential cost savings.
- Contributes to lowering the carbon footprint and environmental impact of buildings, aligning with broader sustainability objectives.

In essence, the SRI methodology aims to optimize building performance, enhance occupant experiences, and contribute to broader sustainability objectives.

The SRI calculation methodology is constructed around an inventory of "smart-ready services" that have the potential to enhance the intelligence of a building based on the functionalities they offer. Examples of these smart-ready services include heat emission control, cooling emission control, supply air flow control, and window shading control. These services are organized into a list of 54 items, in accordance with existing EU provisions. Each smart-ready service encompasses different levels of functionality, representing varying degrees of smartness. For instance, "heat emission control" may range from basic manual control to advanced individual room control with communication and presence detection. These smart-ready services are categorized into nine "technical domains", as presented in Figure 18 and contribute to seven impact criteria, as presented in Figure 19 which are further grouped into three discrete categories reflecting the primary objectives of the SRI, known as "key functionalities", as follows:

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Figure 18: Technical domains of SRI included in the SRI methodology

Figure 19: Smart service impact criteria included in the SRI methodology

Energy performance & operation: This is a pivotal aspect within the SRI framework, focusing on assessing a building's energy consumption and aiming to reduce excessive energy use and emissions, particularly from conventional sources. The implementation of smart-ready services plays a key role in achieving this reduction. The primary objective is to maximize energy efficiency, allowing the building to dynamically adapt to prevailing conditions. For instance, renewable energy storage can be utilized during peak demand periods. Within this functionality, the spotlight is on Energy Efficiency and Maintenance and Fault Protection impact criteria. The SRI framework evaluates energy efficiency by assessing the impact of smart-ready services on energy consumption and resulting savings. Rather than the overall energy efficiency, the focus is on the portion influenced by these services. For example, adjusting room temperatures individually can reduce energy consumption. Automated fault prediction and identification significantly contribute to optimizing Technical Building Systems (TBS) maintenance, minimizing energy losses, and preventing equipment deterioration.

Response to the needs of occupants: To achieve harmony within buildings, it is crucial to employ user-friendly smart technologies capable of predicting, adapting to, and responding to occupants' needs, ensuring visual, acoustic, and thermal comfort. These technologies operate autonomously, providing information on current and future conditions without requiring external user intervention. Comfort, a key impact criterion within the present functionality, encompasses visual, thermal, and acoustic comfort. Visual and thermal comfort rely on dynamic processes triggered by smart services, while acoustic comfort depends on sound-insulating building materials rather than

smart devices. Convenience, another impact criterion, aims to minimize user action, best achieved through fully automated systems. Indoor conditions significantly impact occupants' health and well-being, with indoor air quality being a prime example. Smart devices can improve indoor air quality by reducing pollutants, leading to a healthier environment, and reducing the risk of respiratory issues. Providing occupants with information is essential, with occupants benefiting from data on electricity consumption, humidity levels, and indoor temperature, accessible through appropriate software and sensors. This is facilitated by the increasing deployment of smart devices and the advent of high-speed internet like 5G, enabling real-time data exchange between devices.

Energy flexibility assessment: Member States currently face a significant challenge with energy shortages during extreme weather conditions. This is particularly evident in Southern European countries such as Greece, Spain, and Italy during the summer months, when air conditioning systems are in constant use, leading to increased electricity demand. One solution proposed is the installation of PV systems in buildings to utilize solar energy during daylight hours. This allows for scheduling the operation of energy-intensive devices accordingly, reducing reliance on the electricity grid and enhancing energy flexibility. The growing proportion of variable renewable generation in the electricity mix and the shift towards a fully decentralized energy system underscore the importance of flexibility. This can be achieved through the widespread deployment of energy storage, demand response schemes, and dispatchable, flexible power generation technologies. Numerous studies on the future of the European energy landscape emphasize that energy storage will be a critical component in this transition, with buildings playing a pivotal role in the overall process.

SRI tool

The SRI tool that was decided to be used in the context of the INHERIT project, is the SRI-ENACT tool which is developed within the European funding project SRI-ENACT²³. The SRI-ENACT tool stands out for its comprehensive methodology, designed to assess various aspects of building intelligence and readiness for smart technologies. Its ability to evaluate key functionalities, such as energy performance, comfort, and responsiveness to occupants' needs aligns perfectly with INHERIT's project goals of enhancing building efficiency and occupant satisfaction. Moreover, the SRI-ENACT tool is compliant with all EC directives and regulations, ensuring adherence to established standards and guidelines.

The user-friendly interface and robust analytical capabilities of the tool make it an ideal choice for guiding decision-making processes and identifying opportunities for improvement. The aim is not only to optimize building performance but also contribute to broader sustainability objectives and create healthier, more comfortable indoor environments for occupants. Figure 20 presents an indicative output of the SRI-ENACT tool, including the total SRI score and SRI class of the building (top right), the building's address, type, year of construction, date of assessment, and name of the assessor (top left), the impact scores (mid left), the domain scores (mid right), the detailed scores (bottom left), and the aggregated scores (bottom right). From these outputs, the aggregated scores will be exploited to compute the performance of the INHERIT pilots across the three key functionalities.

²³ <https://www.srienact-tool.eu/login>

Figure 20: Final SRI score screen from the SRI-ENACT tool

List of KPIs

Utilizing KPIs is crucial in the context of building energy monitoring and upgrading as it contributes towards a comprehensive understanding of the indoor environmental conditions and energy requirements of a building's complex. As such, KPIs enable the systematic and objective assessment of EP and IEQ, while providing metrics and data for comparative analysis that allows the selection of effective renovation strategies.

As explained in previous sections, there are still no clear specifications when it comes to IEQ and EP in relation to CH buildings. Therefore, within the INHERIT project, the KPIs selected for assessing IEQ were defined according to the EN 16798-1:2019 standard currently used for conventional buildings, summarizing indoor environmental conditions in a concise and comprehensive way, as presented in Table 9. Similarly, EP-related KPIs focused on the energy efficiency of the buildings, using the existing building stock as a benchmark. More specifically, the first 5 KPIs, focusing on EP, are related to energy efficiency, smart energy management, and energy production from Renewable Energy Sources (RES). The rest of the KPIs are related to the IEQ and can be disaggregated into those that concern TC, AQ, VC, and AC.

Table 9: Pillar 1 – Energy Performance and IEQ KPI set

ID	Name	Definition	Units	Source
1.1-EP	Total energy intensity	Energy (total) consumed, normalized by floor area	kWh/m^2	Buda et al., 2022 [27]
1.1.1-EP	Heating energy intensity	Energy (heating) consumed, normalized by floor area and HDD	$kWh/(m^2 \times HDD)$	Buda et al., 2022 [27] CEN EN 16883:2017

ID	Name	Definition	Units	Source
1.1.2-EP	Cooling energy intensity	Energy (cooling) consumed, normalized by floor area and CDD	$kWh / (m^2 \times DD)$	Buda et al., 2022 [27] CEN EN 16883:2017
1.1.3-EP	Lighting energy intensity	Energy (lighting) consumed, normalized by floor area	kWh / m^2	Buda et al., 2022 [27]
1.1.4-EP	Appliances energy intensity	Energy (other energy uses) consumed, normalized by floor area	kWh / m^2	Buda et al., 2022 [27]
1.2-EP	Energy autonomy	Ratio of energy consumed and energy produced by RES	%	Buda et al., 2022 [27]
1.3-EP	Energy performance & operation	As measured at the respective SRI functionality level	%	IEA ²⁴ Eurostat ²⁵
1.4-EP	Response to the needs of occupants	As measured at the respective SRI functionality level	%	IEA Eurostat
1.5-EP	Energy flexibility assessment	As measured at the respective SRI functionality level	%	IEA Eurostat
1.1-IEQ	Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	Frequency (% during occupancy hours) of indoor air temperatures within acceptable range (19-25°C in winter and 22-27°C in summer)	%	European Commission, 2020a [28]
1.2-IEQ	Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity	Frequency (% during occupancy hours) of indoor humidity within acceptable range (20-70%)	%	European Commission, 2020a [28]
1.3-IEQ	Air quality	Frequency (% during occupancy hours) of indoor CO ₂ concentration within acceptable range (<1.350 ppm)	%	European Commission, 2020a [28]
1.4-IEQ	Visual comfort	Frequency (% during occupancy hours) of illuminance within acceptable range (> 500 lux)	%	European Commission, 2020a [28]
1.5-IEQ	Acoustic comfort	Frequency of noise (% during occupancy hours) within acceptable range (< 45 db)	%	European Commission, 2020a [28]

²⁴ <https://www.iea.org/energy-system/buildings>

²⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Archive:Heating_and_cooling_degree_days_statistics

The objectives of the selected KPIs can be summarized as follows:

- **KPI 1.1-EP** measures the total energy consumed in the building, normalized by its floor area. Normalization enables comparisons with other buildings of the same type and use, thus facilitating benchmarking. Moreover, energy intensity is measured for key energy uses separately, namely heating (1.1.1-EP), cooling (1.1.2-EP), lighting (1.1.3-EP) and other energy uses (1.1.4-EP), as these uses typically contribute most to a building's total energy consumption, at least for office and residential buildings as is the case with the INHERIT pilots. By disaggregating energy intensity to such energy uses, more detailed insights can be provided regarding the renovation actions that could result in notable energy savings. Lower values suggest better performance. Note that KPI 1.1-EP should only be computed when there are no data available to allow the estimation of the 1.1.1-EP, 1.1.2-EP, 1.1.3-EP, and 1.1.4-EP KPIs. Similarly, depending on the infrastructure of the building, some of the above KPIs could be irrelevant.
- **KPI 1.2-EP** measures the energy produced from RES as a proportion of the building's energy consumption, thus implicitly summarizing the energy autonomy of the building. Zero-energy buildings will report a value of 1 (or even higher in case of excess energy production), while a value of 0 will suggest the complete absence of RES. In that sense, higher values suggest better performance.
- **KPIs 1.3-EP, 1.4-EP and 1.5-EP** focus in three key functionalities of the SRI presented in the previous section, namely the "Energy performance & operation", "Response to the needs of occupants", and "Energy flexibility assessment", with the objective to provide more detailed insights regarding the factors that contribute most/least to the overall smart readiness of the building. Higher values suggest better performance.
- **KPIs 1.1-IEQ and 1.2-IEQ** measure how frequently the users of the building experience TC in terms of indoor air temperature and humidity, respectively, as defined by the EN 16798-1:2019 standard. To make sure the measurements are representative, the indicators cover only the time periods that the building is occupied since e.g. on weekends, on holidays, and at night hours achieving TC may be irrelevant in some types of buildings. Higher values suggest better performance, while a score of 100% suggests perfect performance.
- Similar to the TC indicators, **KPIs 1.3-IEQ, 1.4-IEQ, and 1.5-IEQ** measure how frequently the users of the building experience acceptable AQ, VC, and AC, respectively, as defined by the EN 16798-1:2019 standard. Again, higher values suggest better performance, while a score of 100% suggests perfect performance. All KPIs are measured during occupancy hours.

The KPIs are described in detail in Annex 2.

3.2. Pillar 2: Resource efficiency, Circularity and LCC

Circular economy and resource efficiency principles are needed to be applied to buildings to reduce resource use in the future (European Commission, 2020b [29]). The EC reaffirmed that message by the European Green Deal²⁶, through a set of proposals adopted to transform the EU into a modern, resource-efficient and competitive economy, ensuring to be the first climate-neutral continent (no net emissions of greenhouse gases) by 2050. However, it is far from easy to implement concepts of resource efficiency and the circular economy to buildings, and especially when we talk about cultural heritage buildings, which must be balanced with preserving the historical and architectural integrity of the building.

These principles are framed also through the different macro-objectives defined by Level(s). **Level(s)**²⁷ is a voluntary reporting framework to improve the sustainability of buildings, applying principles of circular economy in the built environment.

The Level(s) framework is structured in six macro-objectives (JRC, 2017 [30]), which set goals for the contribution of buildings across the EU to environmental, health and comfort, and cost, value and risk objectives. Based on these goals, building specific indicators have been developed. With current pillar 2, different macro-objectives aligned and contain relevant indicators related to the resource efficiency, circular economy and life cycle cost, specifically:

- Macro-objective 1: **Greenhouse gas emissions along a buildings' life cycle**, which focuses on the emissions related to energy in the use phase of a building, and emissions embodied in building materials and associated processed along the life cycle. Mainly related to this pillar is the life cycle **Global Warming Potential (GWP)** indicator, which measures the contribution of the greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions associated with a building's life cycle to the earth's global warming or climate change.
- Macro-objective 2: **Resource efficient and circular material life cycles** is about the reduction of waste, the optimization of material use, and the reduction of environmental impacts of design and material choices through the life cycle. Thus, it provides tools and guidance for describing and assessing a number of life cycle scenarios that are important from a resource efficiency perspective. The consideration of the materials (through the development of a bill of materials) is key input for the Global Warming Potential indicator, especially for new buildings or, in this context, for renovation works in CH buildings.
- Macro-objective 3: **Efficient use of water resources**. It is aimed at making efficient use of water resources, particularly in areas of continuous or seasonal water stress. The intended scope is to take action to minimise water use at the building level in all areas, with a particular focus on water reuse in buildings located in areas of continuous or seasonal water stress. It is also relevant data for the Global Warming Potential indicator.
- Macro-objective 6: **Optimised life cycle cost and value**, focuses on the optimisation of the life cycle cost and value of buildings to reflect the potential for long-term performance, inclusive of acquisition, operation, maintenance, refurbishment, disposal and end of life. **Life Cycle Costing (LCC)** is particularly relevant to achieving an improved environmental performance as higher initial capital costs may be required to achieve lower life-cycle

²⁶ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

²⁷ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/circular-economy/levels_en

running costs, higher residual property values and improved workforce productivity. It therefore represents a method for making effective, long-term investment decisions. LCC is an important tool during the project definition, concept design and detailed design stages, where it can be used to select and value engineer the design that will provide the lowest overall cost (and highest residual value) along the life cycle of the asset.

The other two macro-objectives from Level(s), the macro-objective 4 (Healthy and comfortable spaces) and the macro-objective 5 (Adaptation and resilience to climate change), are not related with this pillar.

The overall principles of circular economy buildings (European Commission, 2020b [29]), are also relevant for the CH buildings, in this case balanced with the preservation of the historical and architecture integrity. These principles of circular economy buildings, according to the EC publication are:

- **Design principles** of circular economy and sustainable buildings are applicable to all actors along the value chain.
- Sustainable choices must consider total **life cycle costs**, financial and non-financial return on investments.
- **Viable business models** must exist or be developed for each economic operator in the supply or value chain.
- Principles need to be applied considering proportionality – benefits should outweigh the costs.
- Better knowledge is needed about construction techniques to facilitate deconstruction and to enhance **durability and adaptability** of the building:
 - **Durability**: durability of buildings depends on better design, improved performance of construction products and information sharing.
 - **Adaptability**: prevent premature building demolition by developing a new design culture.
- **Reduce waste** and facilitate **high-quality waste management**: design products and systems so that they can be easily reused, repaired, recycled or recovered.

The **adaptive reuse** of abandoned and underused cultural heritage sites can be a strategy to enhance heritage conservation, stimulating sustainable development processes through new uses of old buildings and sites, co-creating new meanings and re-activating neglected areas, turning them into new vibrant cultural places. The adaptive reuse of abandoned and underused buildings and sites, which represent urban “wastes”, also supports the implementation of the circular economy model in the spatial dimension. The CLIC project²⁸ applied the circular economy principles to cultural heritage adaptive reuse for achieving environmentally, socially, culturally and economically sustainable urban/territorial development. Adaptive reuse of cultural heritage is seen as a mean to circularise the flows of raw-materials, energy, cultural capital as well as social capital.

The following key performance indicators (KPIs) are proposed in this pillar, with a different focus as highlighted in the Table 10, and detailed in the Annex 3.

²⁸ <https://www.clicproject.eu/>

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Table 10: Pillar 2: Resource Efficiency, Circularity and LCC KPIs

ID	Name	Definition	Units	Focus	Source
2.1-TWC	Total Water Consumption	Water consumption in the building.	Resid. buildings: $m^3/occupant/year$ Non-residential: $m^3/m^2/year$	To understand (and decrease) the water consumption. Input to indicators 2.2-GWP and 2.7-WCI .	Level(s) – indicator 3.1, CLIC project
2.2-GWP	Global Warming Potential	Contribution of the GHG emissions associated with a building's life cycle to the earth's global warming or climate change. It is the carbon footprint assessment.	$kgCO_2eq/m^2/year$	It should be calculated for each life cycle stage. For CH buildings, especially relevant in the use stage, as well as end of life and construction (if renovation).	Level(s) – indicator 1.2, BIM-SPEED project
2.3-OEC	Operational Energy Costs	Total costs of the building spent on energy services (energy consumption, O&M, etc.).	$€/m^2/year$	Economic indicator. Input to indicators 2.4-PBP and 2.5-LCC .	BIM-SPEED project, OptEEmAL project
2.4-PBP	Payback Period	It is the time it takes to cover the investment costs.	Years	Economic indicator, relevant for the assessment of energy renovation in a building.	BIM-SPEED project OptEEmAL project, CLIC project
2.5-LCC	Life Cycle Cost	It assesses the life cycle of elemental costs of a building. It includes both CAPEX and OPEX costs.	$€/m^2/year$	Economic indicator, relevant for the assessment of energy renovation in a building.	Level(s) – indicator 6.1, OptEEmAL project
2.6-ECI	Energy Circularity Indicator	Rate of circular energy to total lifecycle energy consumption of the building or retrofitting.	%	Valid also to compare baseline rate with ex-post rate after energy intervention.	Adapted from: HOUSEFUL project and Ellen MacArthur Foundation
2.7-WCI	Water Circularity Indicator	Rate of circular water to total lifecycle water consumption of the building or retrofitting.	%	Valid also to compare baseline rate with ex-post rate after water efficiency intervention.	Adapted from HOUSEFUL project and Ellen MacArthur Foundation
2.8-MCI	Material Circularity Indicator	Rate of circular material to total lifecycle material use of the building or retrofitting.	%	Relevant also to obtain a rate and assess the circularity of the materials employed in an intervention.	Adapted from HOUSEFUL project, Madaster Platform and Ellen MacArthur Foundation

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The KPIs have been selected in order to cover the different focus and objectives of the circularity, resource efficiency and life cycle cost of a building life cycle, considering the specific needs and circumstances of a cultural heritage building. Thus, the first two indicators (KPIs **2.1-TWC** and **2.2-GWP**) are related to the circularity and efficiency of natural resources (water consumption and reduction of GHG emissions). Then, a set of economic indicators is included, the first of them applicable to all circumstances (KPI **2.3-OEC**) for the costs of the energy operation, while the following two (KPIs **2.4-PBP** and **2.5-LCC**) are specifically for the assessment of an (energy) renovation or other investment that is being planned for the building. Finally, related with the circularity overall, three indicators have been included for an index on water, energy and circularity of the building (KPIs **2.6-ECI**, **2.7-WCI** and **2.8-MCI**).

3.3. Pillar 3: Resilience to climate and human-made hazards

Climate change is directly and indirectly threatening the cultural heritage. According to the EC publication “Strengthening cultural heritage resilience for climate change” (European Commission, 2022 [31]), the most evident threats stem from extreme climatic events (severe precipitation, long heatwaves, droughts, strong winds and sea-level rise), all of which will increase dramatically in the future, as predicted by the IPCC. Gradual climate change, as the continuous increase in temperature and fluctuations in temperature and humidity or fluctuations in freeze-thaw cycles, causes degradation and stress in materials, leading to a greater need for restoration and conservation. Biological degradation caused by microorganisms, for example in the form of mould or algal growth, and insect infestations attacking the physical fabric of buildings and the collection of galleries, libraries, archives and museums are more likely to occur. Cultural heritage is also vulnerable to maladaptation, when inadvertent loss or damage is caused by adaptation measures.

Resilience is defined, according to IPCC6 report (IPCC, 2022 [32]), as the capacity of a social, economic and ecosystems to cope with a hazardous event or trend or disturbance, responding or reorganising in ways that maintain their essential function, identity and structure as well as biodiversity in case of ecosystems, while also maintaining the capacity for adaptation, learning and transformation. It is a positive attribute when it maintains such a capacity for adaptation, learning, and/or transformation. On the one hand resilience as a system trait overlaps with concepts of vulnerability, adaptive capacity and, thus, risk, and on the other hand resilience as a strategy overlaps with risk management, adaptation and transformation.

Resilience to climate change is also related to macro-objective 5 of Level(s) (JRC, 2017 [30]): **Adaptation and resilience to climate change**, which focuses on the futureproofing of building performance against projected changes in the climate, in order to protect occupier health and comfort and to sustain and minimise risks to property values. Two aspects are highlighted to be considered for potential future scenario development: the increased risk of extreme weather events, which may require consideration of the durability and resistance of building elements; and an increased risk of flooding, which may require consideration of the capacity of drainage systems and the resilience of structures.

The EC publication “Safeguarding Cultural Heritage from Natural and Man-Made Disasters” (European Commission, 2018 [33]) states that one of the major identified problems in the risk management of cultural heritage is the fact that knowledge of hazards and risks is not yet structurally integrated with cultural heritage protection measures. The document provides an overview of the main natural and human-made hazards that affect the built heritage, such as:

- **Air pollution changes.** Building surfaces were often blackened by the effects of industrial processes of the past, but now different organic rich pollutants, emanating from vehicle exhausts, can cause buildings to visually take on “warmer tones” that are not less damaging. Additionally, the higher frequency of events of intense wind-driven rain can alter the distribution of damage on façades, and warmer climates can favour greater degrees of biological colonisation. The colour, distribution and effects of deposited materials on façades can have significant aesthetic and performance implications, requiring the adoption of new maintenance and conservation strategies to be pursued.
- **Flood and landslide.** Even though cultural heritage suffers significantly during flood events, and its loss and damage substantially influences resilience processes and characteristics, it

is largely considered a marginal issue. Landslide and similar phenomena (e.g. avalanches, mud flows, debris flows, rock falls) can also cause a major loss of historic assets. Landslides frequently accompany floods, having the same triggering mechanism in consequence of heavy rainfall. Earthquakes are the second major cause of landslides, with additional important triggering factors such as erosion (e.g. by a river or sea), and human activity (excavations at the bottom or surcharge at the top of a slope).

- **Wind risk.** The damaging effects from wind is now considered a serious threat and risk, leading to the loss of life, property, and infrastructure as a result of partial structural damage, collapse or flying debris. The risk of damage to historic buildings in Europe due to wind and driven rain is well documented, however, the full scale of the consequences has not yet been fully assessed or analysed.
- **Earthquake.** It could have the most devastating impact in terms of loss of lives and damage to structures. Frequently, they are followed by other disasters (as side effects) such as fire, floods, landslides or tsunamis. To deal the natural disaster “earthquake” it is important to adopt a more holistic approach that goes beyond the structural restoration/strengthening of CH buildings and takes into account the synergy and effect of other natural disasters too. Although seismic events are not predictable or preventable, their effect on cultural heritage buildings and their content may be minimized through prevention measures that aim to reduce their vulnerability.
- **Volcanic eruption.** According to ESPON (European Spatial Planning Observation Network), the highest volcanic eruption hazard is concentrated in southern Europe, and comparing this with the distribution of the cultural heritage, the heritage exposed to this hazard is elevated.
- **Fire risk.** Fire is the most universally common catastrophe that can be encountered.
- **Armed conflicts and terrorism.** The destruction of cultural property during armed conflicts has recently gained a sad fearfulness, which shattered the world community.

Other natural disasters that could be considered as per the relation with cultural heritage are: tsunamis, sea level rise, storm, coastal erosion or drought. In relation with the human activity, it can also be considered the illicit artefact trafficking, the over-exploitation, the touristic pressure, the unsustainable development, or the climate change (fast/sudden).

A list of principal climate change risks and impact on cultural heritage is summarised in Table 11, based on HERACLES project²⁹, in D3.1 “Definition of methodologies for climate change impact evaluation and risk and vulnerability analysis” (Alexandrakis et al., 2017 [34]).

Table 11: Climate changes and associated risks and impacts on cultural heritage from HERACLES project

Climate parameter	Climate change risk	Physical, social and cultural impacts on cultural heritage
Atmospheric moisture change	- Flooding (sea, river)	Relative humidity cycles/shock causing splitting, cracking, flaking and dusting of materials and surfaces
	- Intense rainfall	Eutrophication accelerating microbial decomposition of organics
	- Changes in water table levels	Corrosion of metals

²⁹ <http://www.heracles-project.eu/>

Climate parameter	Climate change risk	Physical, social and cultural impacts on cultural heritage
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Changes in soil chemistry - Ground water changes - Changes in humidity cycles - Increase in time of wetness - Sea salt chlorides 	<p>Physical changes to porous building materials</p> <p>Damage due to faulty or inadequate water disposal systems</p> <p>Crystallisation and dissolution of salts caused by wetting and drying affecting standing structures, archaeology, wall paintings, frescos and other decorated surfaces</p> <p>Erosion of inorganic and organic materials due to flood waters</p> <p>Biological attack of organic materials by insects, moulds, fungi, invasive species such as termites</p> <p>Subsoil instability, landslides, ground motion, differential settling of building foundations, excessive thrust on retaining walls and subsidence</p>
Temperature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Diurnal, seasonal, extreme events (heat waves, snow loading) - Changes in freeze-thaw and ice storms, and increase in wet frost 	<p>Changes in freeze-thaw and ice storms, and increase in wet frost</p> <p>Deterioration due to thermal stress</p> <p>Damage due to increased pest frequency (e.g. wooden materials)</p> <p>Damage from freeze-thaw cycles or frost</p> <p>Damage inside bricks, stones, concretes and ceramics</p> <p>Overheating of buildings and artefacts, which leads to inappropriate alterations to materials</p>
Sea level rises	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coastal flooding - Sea water incursion 	<p>Erosion or loss of materials and structures on the sites</p> <p>Saltwater intrusion of subsurface structures</p> <p>Permanent inundation of resources in low-lying areas</p> <p>Coastal erosion/loss</p> <p>Intermittent introduction of large masses of “strange” water to the site, which may disturb the metastable equilibrium between artefacts and soil</p>
Wind	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Wind-driven rain - Wind-transported salt - Wind-driven sand - Winds, gusts and changes in direction 	<p>Penetrative moisture into porous cultural heritage materials</p> <p>Static and dynamic loading of historic or archaeological structures</p> <p>Structures damage and collapse</p> <p>Deterioration of surfaces due to erosion</p> <p>Increasing wave energy in coastal structures (increasing stress)</p>
Desertification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Drought - Heat waves - Fall in water table 	<p>Erosion</p> <p>Salt weathering</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - pH precipitation 	<p>Stone recession by dissolution of carbonates</p> <p>Blackening of materials</p>

Climate parameter	Climate change risk	Physical, social and cultural impacts on cultural heritage
Climate and pollution acting together	- Changes in deposition of pollutants	Corrosion of metals Influence of bio-colonization
Climate and biological effects	- Spread of existing and new species of insects - Increase in mould growth - Changes in lichen colonies on buildings - Decline of original materials	Reduction in availability of native species for repair and maintenance of buildings Changes in the natural heritage values of cultural heritage sites Changes in appearance of landscapes Changes in the livelihood of traditional settlements Changes in inhabited structures as sources

According to IPCC Chapter 1 “Climate Change: new dimensions in disaster risk, exposure, vulnerability and resilience” (Lavell et al., 2012 [35]), **disaster risk** is defined as a likelihood over a specified time period of severe alterations in the normal functioning of a community or a society due to hazardous physical events interacting with vulnerable social conditions, leading to widespread adverse human, material, economic, or environmental effects that require immediate emergency response to satisfy critical human needs and that may require external support for recovery. Disaster risks are a combination of physical hazards and the vulnerabilities of exposed elements and will signify the potential for severe interruption of the normal functioning of the affected society once it materializes as disaster.

This definition of disaster risk does not include the potential or actual impacts of climate and hydrological events on ecosystems or the physical Earth system per se. Such impacts are considered relevant to disaster (according to Chapter 1, in IPCC, 2012 [35]) if they comprise one or more of the following situations: i) they impact livelihoods negatively by seriously affecting ecosystem services and the natural resource base of communities, ii) they have consequences for food security, and/or iii) they have impacts on human health.

Following the definitions of the IPCC 2012, **hazard** is defined as the potential occurrence of a natural or human-induced physical event that may cause loss of life, injury, or other health impacts, as well as damage and loss to property, infrastructure, livelihoods, service provision, and environmental resources.

Exposure is referred to the presence (location) of people, livelihoods, environmental services and resources, infrastructure, or economic, social or cultural assets in places that could be adversely affected by physical events and which, thereby, are subject to potential future harm, loss, or damage.

Under exposed conditions, the levels and types of adverse impacts will be the result of a physical event (or events) interacting with socially constructed conditions denoted as vulnerability. **Vulnerability** is defined as the propensity or predisposition to be adversely affected. Such predisposition constitutes an internal characteristic of the affected element. Vulnerability is a result of diverse historical, social, economic, political, cultural, institutional, natural resource, and environmental conditions and processes.

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These terms are related in the Figure 21, indicating schematically key concepts involved in disaster risk management and climate change adaptation, and interaction of these with sustainable development.

Figure 21: Key concepts and scope of disaster risk, from IPCC 2012. Determinants of risk, from IPCC, 2023

In the IPCC 2023 [36], the Synthesis Report for the Sixth Assessment Report (AR6), the **risks** are defined as the dynamic interactions between climate-related hazards, exposure and vulnerability of the affected human society, species, or ecosystems result in risks arising from climate change. The determinants of risk are assessed similarly as in the previous report (IPCC 2012 [35]), see Figure 21), but adding the assessment of current implementation of adaptation and mitigation response options.

To evaluate the main risks to cultural heritage sites, a three-steps methodology for a qualitative analysis is proposed (summarised in Figure 22):

Figure 22: Methodology for a qualitative analysis of Pillar 3 – Resilience to climate and human-made hazards

- i. **Identification of hazards (risks)**, including climate change risks, geological incidents, and human-made hazards. → KPIs **3.1-IoH**, **3.2-HI** and **3.3-RAM**.
- ii. **Impacts assessment**: assessing the impact of each identified hazard, by the assessment of the vulnerability and exposure in relation to the risk impact (**Risk = Vulnerability x Exposure**), Table 12. → KPI **3.4-R_VxE**.
 - a. For the **vulnerability** assessment, “How propense or predisposed the CH site is to be adversely affected by the hazard?”. For this, historical, social, economic, political, cultural, institutional, natural resource, and environmental conditions and processes of the site that make them more vulnerable to the hazard should be considered.

- b. For the **exposure** assessment, “How much the CH site would be adversely affected by the hazard?”. For a site to be adversely affected, it should be taken into account if it is subject to potential harm, loss or damage by the hazard.

Table 12: Impacts assessment matrix, for the risk impact of each hazard identified to the CH site

Vulnerability Exposure	Very high	High	Moderate	Low	Very low
Very high	Very high	Very high	High	High	Moderate
High	Very high	High	Moderate	Moderate	Low
Moderate	High	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Low
Low	High	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Very low
Very low	Moderate	Low	Low	Very low	Very low

- iii. **Risk impact level evaluation:** evaluation of the level of each hazard or risk, by assessing the severity of consequences and the likelihood of occurrence, in a similar matrix (**Risk level = Severity of consequences x Likelihood of occurrence**), Table 13. → KPI [3.5-RI_SxL](#).
- a. The **severity of the consequences** measures the amount of damage or harm that the hazard could create. The scale rates from catastrophic consequences to the CH site, to insignificant, where there is no actual damage to the site.
- b. The **likelihood of occurrence** measures the probability of the hazard occurring.

Table 13: Risk impact level evaluation matrix, for the impact level of each hazard identified to the CH site

Severity of consequences Likelihood of occurrence	Catastrophic	Major	Moderate	Minor	Insignificant
Frequent	Very high	Very high	High	High	Moderate
Probable	Very high	High	Moderate	Moderate	Low
Occasional	High	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Low
Remote	High	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Very low
Improbable	Moderate	Low	Low	Very low	Very low

So, each potential hazard identified will be assessed in terms of exposure and vulnerability, and in terms of likelihood of occurrence and severity of consequences, which is in line with the indicators proposed in the table in next section.

For the assessment of both matrices, the following criteria (Table 14) can be considered, to understand the magnitude and acceptability of the risks.

Table 14: Risk scale for the assessment of magnitude and acceptability of risks

Risk index	Magnitude & Acceptability of the risk
Very high	Maximum → unacceptable: maximum threat to CH site. Implement immediate adaptation or mitigation measures/plan.
High	High → unacceptable: large threat to CH site. Implement adaptation or mitigation measures/plan.
Moderate	Medium → acceptable: some threat to CH site. Manage with adaptation or mitigation measures/plan.

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Risk index	Magnitude & Acceptability of the risk
Low	Low → acceptable: little threat to CH site. Some management with adaptation or mitigation measures/plan necessary.
Very low	Minimum → acceptable: no threat to CH site. Current approach is sufficient.

The following key performance indicators (KPIs) are proposed in this pillar, aligned with the methodology for qualitative analysis of risk impact, included in the Table 15, and detailed in the Annex 4.

Table 15: Pillar 3: Resilience to climate and human-made hazards KPIs

ID	Name	Definition	Units	Methodology step	Source
3.1-IoH	Inventory of relevant Hazards	Presence of an inventory of the relevant climate and human-made hazards occurred in the site (in the past).	Qualitative scale: 1 – 5 (scoring)	Step I – Identification of hazards	Adapted from Schokker et al. (2022) [37]
3.2-HI	Hazards Identification	Identification of the most significant (climate or human-made) hazards that the site faces or will face (in the future).	Qualitative scale: 1 – 5 (scoring)	Step I – Identification of hazards	Adapted from Schokker et al. (2022) [37]
3.3-RMP	Risk Management Plan(s)	Assessing the presence, quality and effectiveness of management plans to address risks, potential hazards and vulnerability.	Qualitative scale: 1 – 5 (scoring)	Step I – Identification of hazards	Adapted from Schokker et al. (2022) [37]
3.4-RI_VxE	Risk Impact assessment: Vulnerability and Exposure	Qualitative assessment of the risk impact through the matrix of vulnerability and exposure.	Qualitative scale: Very high – high – moderate – low – very low	Step II – Impacts assessment	<i>Own elaboration</i>
3.5-RL_SxL	Risk impact Level evaluation: Severity of consequences and Likelihood of occurrence	Qualitative assessment of the risk level through the matrix of severity of consequences and likelihood of occurrence.	Qualitative scale: Very high – high – moderate – low – very low	Step III – Risk level evaluation	<i>Own elaboration</i>

3.4. Pillar 4: Accessibility, inclusiveness, openness and socioeconomic sustainability

The examination of **Accessibility, Inclusiveness and Openness, and Socioeconomic Sustainability** in construction sites (buildings) protected by cultural heritage conservators takes centre stage in INHERIT project. Analysing accessibility, inclusiveness & openness, and socioeconomic sustainability in heritage buildings is critically important. This examination is vital for several reasons:

- **Preservation of Cultural Heritage:** Balancing accessibility and inclusiveness and openness with the preservation of cultural and architectural significance is complex. Analysis helps identify strategies to maintain the historical value of these sites while ensuring they remain usable and accessible to the public.
- **Adherence to Modern Standards:** Historic buildings must comply with contemporary safety and regulatory requirements, such as fire safety, thermal efficiency, and evacuation routes. Thorough analysis ensures that necessary upgrades are implemented without compromising the buildings' historical integrity. Adaptation of the heritage buildings to actual standards and norms requires often high investments and is not always possible in all aspects due to certain architectural/aesthetical restrictions and limitations.
- **Economic and Social Impact:** Considering the costs of maintaining and upgrading heritage sites is crucial for socioeconomic sustainability. Comprehensive analysis can guide investments and ensure these sites contribute positively to the local economy and community well-being.
- **Inclusiveness & Openness and Accessibility:** Ensuring that heritage sites are accessible to all individuals, including those with disabilities, is essential for social inclusion. Analysis helps identify obstacles and develop solutions to make these historic buildings welcoming to everyone.
- **Informed Decision-Making:** Detailed analysis provides the necessary data and insights for policymakers, conservators, and architects to make well-informed decisions. This ensures that interventions are effective and respectful of the buildings' historical value.

Universal design, pioneered by architect and disability rights advocate Ronald Mace at North Carolina State University's Centre for Universal Design³⁰ in the late 20th century, focuses on creating environments and products accessible to everyone, regardless of age or ability. Its core principles include equitable use, flexibility, simplicity, perceptible information, tolerance for error, minimal physical effort, and adequate space for approach and use. These guidelines ensure that spaces are inclusive, functional, and user-friendly for all individuals.

Incorporating **universal design principles** is essential for creating buildings that are accessible, inclusive, and open to all individuals, regardless of abilities or disabilities. By adhering to these principles, architects and designers can create environments that accommodate a broad range of users and promote inclusivity, ensuring that spaces are usable and welcoming to everyone.

The practical book "**ISSO Practical Guide for Sustainable Heritage**" [38], first issued in 2011 and revised in 2023, by project partner ISSO (see cover in Figure 23), provides updated strategies for the sustainable maintenance and restoration of historic buildings, including pre-1940 buildings. It

³⁰ <https://design.ncsu.edu/research/center-for-universal-design/>

emphasises a broader focus on sustainability for all historic structures, not just monumental ones. The guide advocates a tailored approach due to the diversity of historical buildings and discourages one-size-fits-all solutions. **Key recommendations** include:

- Understanding the building's characteristics.
- Intervening only where necessary and ensuring high-quality work.
- Ensuring interventions are reversible.
- Maintaining appropriate use and continuity.
- Adjusting comfort expectations to what the building can realistically provide.

Figure 23: Cover of the "ISSO Practical Guide for Sustainable Heritage", 2023 version

The "ISSO Practical Guide for Sustainable Heritage" emphasises the complex balance required in preserving historic buildings, which involves addressing both communal and individual needs. This balance includes not only the physical conservation of heritage structures but also accommodating diverse user requirements such as comfort, accessibility, safety, and aesthetic considerations. Achieving this harmony is challenging, as it necessitates aligning the collective goals of heritage preservation with individual priorities, often related to practical use and economic benefits.

A critical aspect of heritage preservation is reconciling modern demands for comfort and sustainability with the need to maintain heritage values. Efforts to enhance energy efficiency and comfort can sometimes result in the unintended loss of historical elements, especially when financial constraints favour practical or individual interests over communal values. Therefore, innovative and customised solutions are essential, focusing on the long-term impact on heritage rather than defaulting to standard approaches.

The "ISSO Practical Guide for Sustainable Heritage" offers a comprehensive guide for professionals, detailing sustainability steps and referencing tools and guidelines. The strength of this publication lies in its process-oriented approach, where heritage experts, construction professionals and

sustainability specialists collaborate to combine their expertise. Its primary objective is to encourage proactive action among heritage owners and managers by providing reliable information and facilitating knowledge sharing across the sector.

The handbook addresses the broader context, including government policies, climate agreements and the energy transition, which influence the sustainability of heritage buildings. It also explores important developments such as the repurposing of heritage sites and innovative approaches in sustainability.

It details **21 strategies to balance preservation and sustainability** (see Figure 24), covering various aspects of heritage sustainability, from understanding the building and addressing reuse and circularity to implement energy and water-saving measures. The Sustainable Monument Care (**DuMo**, per its name in Dutch: *Duurzaam Monument*, which translates to “Sustainable Monument”) instrument is included as an appendix, offering additional guidance on aligning restoration strategies with sustainability goals.

Strategies to balance preservation and sustainability for CH buildings <i>ISSO Practical Guide for Sustainable Heritage</i>	
1. Understanding the Building	12. Use or Infiltration of Rainwater
2. Minimal Intervention	13. Utilising High Spaces
3. Reversibility	14. Energy Savings and Retrofit Insulation
4. Appropriate Use	15. Healthy Indoor Climate
5. Adjusted Comfort Requirements	16. Protection of Plants and Animals
6. Reuse and Circularity	17. User Education
7. Traditional and Environmentally Friendly Materials	18. Regular Maintenance
8. Adjacent Unheated Spaces	19. Interaction between Sustainability and Heritage
9. Suitable Installation	20. Balancing Different Interests
10. Energy Savings and Retrofit Insulation	21. Restoration Strategy – Alignment with DuMo Profile
11. Drinking Water Conservation Measures	22. Neighbourhood Approach to Heritage Sustainability

Figure 24: Strategies for the sustainable maintenance and restoration of all built heritage provided by the revised "ISSO Practical Guide for Sustainable Heritage", 2023 version

In essence, the successful preservation of heritage buildings requires a nuanced approach that balances historical integrity with contemporary needs, embracing innovative solutions and compromises to achieve a globally satisfactory outcome.

In this context, **Building Information Modelling (BIM)** proves to be a valuable asset. BIM enhances the assessment of accessibility and sustainability of heritage buildings through its comprehensive and collaborative capabilities. By creating detailed digital models that incorporate critical information about a building’s structure and systems, BIM facilitates the visualisation of potential barriers and aids in designing inclusive solutions. Furthermore, BIM’s ability to simulate and analyse various design scenarios supports the evaluation of sustainable practices, allowing for informed decisions that minimise environmental impact. Thus, BIM streamlines the assessment process and fosters the integration of accessibility and sustainability considerations in heritage building preservation.

To assess and measure accessibility, inclusiveness and openness, and socioeconomic sustainability levels following set of KPI was developed, see Table 16.

Table 16: Pillar 4 – Accessibility, inclusiveness, openness and socioeconomic sustainability KPI set

ID	Name	Definition	Units	Related focus	Source
4.1-AL	Accessibility level	Study and analysis of all the potential barriers and building limitations (technical barriers) for various areas for a various group of people with disabilities.	%	Accessibility KPI (assessment through set of questions)	Developed by FASADA from different standards
4.2-I&OL	Inclusiveness and openness level	Capacity to accommodate diverse visitors regardless of cultural and social background, ensuring an engagement while preserving its historical significance and cultural integrity.	%	Inclusiveness and openness KPI (assessment through set of questions)	Developed by FASADA from different standards
4.3-RT	Direct revenue from tourism (entry fees)	The revenue generated directly from the monument/historic building itself, such as entry fees (and souvenirs if any).	<i>P, Q, R (ranges)</i>	Socio-economic KPI	Developed by ISSO (RURITAGE EU Project)
4.4-IRT	Indirect revenue through tourism attraction	Some monuments/ historic buildings will receive so much attention or popularity that people decide to visit places specifically for these. This will also be beneficial for local businesses that are close by.	<i>P, Q, R (ranges)</i>	Socio-economic KPI	Developed by ISSO (RURITAGE EU Project)
4.5-IPV	Increased property value	The actual increase of value of the property due to the increase in popularity or other contributing factors	<i>% or P, Q, R (ranges)</i>	Socio-economic KPI	Developed by ISSO ([59] & [60])
4.6-LJC	Number of local jobs created	The amount or percentage of the total of jobs which have been given to local residents	<i>% or P, Q, R (ranges)</i>	Socio-economic KPI	Developed by ISSO ([59])
4.7-IPI	Investment in public infrastructure	Investments made due to the monument's/ historic building's presence which highlights how it is driving broader improvements in the area	<i>P, Q, R (ranges)</i>	Socio-economic KPI	Developed by ISSO
4.8-CE	Cultural enrichment	This analyses the monument's contribution to the local cultural scene (events, festivals). Data sources: event attendance data, cultural organization partnerships	<i>P, Q, R (ranges)</i>	Socio-economic KPI	Developed by ISSO

ID	Name	Definition	Units	Related focus	Source
4.9-PP	Public perception	This assesses public sentiment towards the monument's/ historic building's impact on the community. Data sources: media coverage analysis, community surveys, public complaint data (nuisance: sound/ visual/ congestion due to over-tourism)	<i>P, Q, R (ranges)</i>	Socio-economic KPI	Developed by ISSO

For the KPIs with the focus on socioeconomic aspects, as they are usually hard to assess, the **P, Q, R framework** for evaluating KPIs has been used (as indicated in the “units” column). This framework categorises indicators as having significant (P), moderate (Q) or minimal (R) effects, and it is rooted in both qualitative and quantitative methods. This approach helps in prioritising resources and interventions by assessing the impact of KPIs in a nuanced manner.

Qualitative assessments allow for a deeper understanding of socioeconomic impacts (such as community engagement, tourism revenue and job creation) beyond mere numerical data.

Overall, the P, Q, R method complements traditional metrics by providing a qualitative layer of analytics, which is crucial for capturing the full scope of impacts in complex projects like those involving cultural heritage.

The adaptability of the P, Q, R ranges to every KPI ensures that it accurately reflects its unique circumstances and impacts, providing a tailored assessment that aligns with the specific goals and context of each KPI. Thus, the P, Q and R categories are contextualised for each KPI in Annex 5.

The KPIs of Pillar 4 presented in the Table 16 are detailed in Annex 5.

4. Web-based application for the multi-dimensional assessment

To facilitate multidimensional assessment of the CH sites, a web-based application will be developed by following the INHERIT framework established in previous section 3. This assessment tool will give the opportunity to trained facility managers, assessors, and inspectors to input the related information to the set of KPIs that are part of the INHERIT framework across the four different pillars. The assessment tool will allow to improve and/or stabilize the metrics to have more sustainable, energy efficient, and accessible CH sites.

4.1. Specifications of the Web-based Application

An analysis of the objectives and KPIs has been made, and has led to the elicitation of the **business requirements** for the application, as can be seen in the following Table 17, which provides an overview.

Table 17: Overview of the business requirements (BR) for the web-based application for the multi-dimensional assessment

Business Requirement	Description
BR.1	Ability of user to Register online
BR.2	Ability of user to Login with credentials (Username & Password)
BR.3	Ability of user to change password and modify his personal data
BR.4	Ability of user to retrieve password
BR.5	Ability of Assessor to insert all required data so as to calculate the assessment score of a building.
BR.6	Ability of Assessor to create his/her buildings' portfolio.
BR.7	Ability of Assessor to view the result of the assessment across the 4 different pillars through the assessment application.
BR.8	Ability of Assessor to see previous assessments for the same building and track the changes in assessment scores
BR.9	Ability of Application Administrator to modify specific parameters of the application.

The screenshots below illustrate the initial development of the web-based application (minimum viable product). The first one (Figure 25) shows the Buildings Dashboard page, offering a comprehensive overview and easy navigation between various buildings assessments. The second one (Figure 26) presents detailed results for a building, breaking down performance by assessment pillars with overall scores.

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Figure 25: INHERIT tool for Multi-dimensional Assessment – Buildings Dashboard page

Figure 26: INHERIT tool for Multi-dimensional Assessment – Test Building’s result per pillar

For the **design** of the tool, three aspects have been followed: User Experience (UX) Strategy, User Interface (UI) Design and User Journey.

The following Figure 27 provides an overview of the user-flow diagram is shown, from the entry point to the tool to the end of the experience for the user through it.

Figure 27: User flow diagram of the web-based application

In the following bullet points, the different **steps of the design** of the tool are depicted:

- **User Experience (UX) Strategy**
 - User Persona Understanding:
 - Identify key users: buildings managers, heritage site operators, sustainability consultants and policy makers.
 - Understand their goals: quick assessment, detailed analysis and action planning.
 - User Journey Mapping:
 - Landing Page: overview of the site’s performance across all pillars.
 - Detailed Analysis Page: dive into each pillar with specific KPIs.
- **User Interface (UI) Design**
 - Landing Page (Dashboard):
 - Summary Cards: displaying a high-level summary for each pillar.
 - Overall score: show the total score prominently.
 - Navigation links: easy access to detailed analysis for each pillar.
 - Detailed Analysis Page (Pillar):
 - KPI Scorecard: tabular view of KPIs with current values, target values, achievements and scores.
 - Radar Chart: visual representation of KPI achievements.
 - Trend Graphs: historical performance data for each KPI.
- **User Journey**
 - Multi-Step Form:
 - The form is divided into steps, each corresponding to a different KPI.
 - Users input their data step-by-step, with navigation buttons to move between steps.
 - Submit Form:
 - On form submission, data is processed, and a summary table is generated to show the overview.
 - The radar chart and trend graphs are updated based on the entered data.

- **Summary Table**

- Displays KPIs, current values, target values, achievements and scores.
- Provides an easy-to-read.

To better grasp the assessment tool and the analysis behind it, it is important to have a common understanding of some of the key terms that will be used in this tool. A **list of key terms** can be found below:

- **Positive Contribution:** Indicates if higher values are better (1) or lower values are better (0).
- **Pillar Weight:** The weight assigned to the entire pillar.
- **KPI Weight:** The specific weight assigned to the KPI within its pillar.
- **Current Value:** The measured value of the KPI.
- **Target Value:** The desired value of the KPI.
- **Achievement:** The percentage indicating how close the current value is to the target value.
- **Score:** The weighted score is calculated from the achievement percentage.

There are two important indexes that will be calculated that will then allow the improvement of the stabilization of the pilot sites. The two **calculations** are for the “**achievement**” and the “**score**” of the pilot sites that are being assessed. The formulas are the following:

- **Calculate Achievement:**

- If Positive contribution = 0 (lower values are better):

$$Achievement (\%) = \frac{Target Value}{Current Value} \times 100\%$$

- If Positive contribution = 1 (higher values are better):

$$Achievement (\%) = \frac{Current Value}{Target Value} \times 100\%$$

- **Calculate Score:**

- The score is calculated by multiplying the achievement percentage by the KPI weight and normalising it based on the pillar weight. Formula:

$$Score = \frac{Achievement (\%)}{100\%} \times KPI Weight \times \frac{Pillar Weight}{100\%}$$

To better analyse the functionality of the application, an **example scenario** for the evaluation of a CH building have been created (based on the KPIs examples provided in the details for each KPI in the Annex 2 to Annex 5). The following Figure 28 to Figure 31 show the exemplification of this scenario across the KPIs and pillars.

Pillar 1: Energy Performance and Indoor Environmental Quality KPIs

Example Scenario: residential building in Greece & office building in Greece

1. **Energy Intensity (total):** Measures the total energy used per squared meter.
 - **Example:** if a building consumes 16,400 kWh of energy annually and has a total area of 80 m², the energy intensity would be 205 kWh/m².
2. **Energy Intensity (heating):** Measures the energy used for heating per squared meter per degree day (DD).
 - **Example:** if the heating energy consumption is 7,600 kWh for a season with 1,000 heating degree days, and the building area is 80 m², the heating intensity would be 0,095 kWh/m².
3. **Energy Intensity (cooling):** Similar to heating, but for cooling energy.
 - **Example:** if cooling energy is 1,200 kWh for a season with 1,500 cooling degree days and the area is 80 m², the intensity would be 0,01 kWh/m².
4. **Energy Intensity (lighting):** Energy used for lighting per squared meter.
 - **Example:** if lighting consumes 400 kWh annually for a 80 m² building, the intensity is 5 kWh/m².
5. **Energy Intensity (appliances):** Encompasses various energy-consuming activities beyond heating, cooling and lighting. Energy consumption related to appliances, equipment, plug loads and others.
 - **Example:** if the building consumes 3,200 kWh for powering its various electrical appliances, with an area of 80m², the intensity is 40 kWh/m².
6. **Energy autonomy:** The proportion of energy consumed by a building over the energy produced from renewable sources (RES).
 - **Example:** if the building consumes a total of 16,400 kWh and 2,000 kWh comes from renewables, the percentage is 12,20%.
7. **Energy Performance and Operation (SRI functionality level):** Specific functionality within SRI to assess the energy consumption and operational performance of a building.
 - **Example:** calculated with the tool it scores 15%, which reflects very low efficiency.
8. **Respond to user needs (SRI functionality level):** Measures how well the building adapts to user needs.
 - **Example:** calculated with the tool it scores 30%, which indicates quite low adaptability.
9. **Energy flexibility (SRI functionality level):** Ability to adapt energy use patterns.
 - **Example:** calculated with the tool it scores 20%, which indicates low flexibility.
10. **Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature:** frequency of acceptable indoor air temperature in relation with the occupancy hours with acceptable indoor air temperature.
 - **Example:** for a office building in Greece operated for 8 hours a day, 5 days a week and 52 weeks a year, there are found 800 hours in the winter period and 600 hours in the summer period with acceptable temperatures. Thus, the frequency of acceptable air temperature is 67%.
11. **Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity:** Similar to temperature but for humidity.
 - **Example:** same office building in which 1,700 hours were found to be within acceptable indoor air humidity range of values. The frequency of acceptable humidity is 82%.
12. **Air quality:** Percentage of time CO₂ concentration level is acceptable (below 1350 ppm).
 - **Example:** same office building with 1650 hours found within acceptable indoor air quality range of values. The frequency of acceptable air quality is 84%.
13. **Visual comfort:** Time illuminance is acceptable (above 500 lux).
 - **Example:** same office building with 1500 hours found within acceptable indoor illuminance range of values. The frequency of acceptable visual comfort is 72%.
14. **Acoustic comfort:** Time noise is acceptable (below 45 db).
 - **Example:** same office building with 1800 hours found within acceptable indoor acoustic comfort range of values. The frequency of acceptable acoustic comfort is 87%.

Figure 28: Example scenario for the evaluation of a CH building for the KPIs in Pillar 1

Pillar 2: Resource Efficiency, Circularity and Life-Cycle Cost KPIs

Example Scenario: office building in Spain

1. **Total Water Consumption (TWC):** Water use per occupant or area.
 - **Example:** an office building of 380m² and 35 workers has an annual water consumption of 166 m³. The TWC is 0.44 m³/(m²·year).
2. **Global Warming Potential (GWP):** GHG emissions associated with a building's life cycle, mainly related to energy and water consumption.
 - **Example:** an office building of 380m² in Spain, with an energy consumption of 79,420 kWh/year, the GWP related to Energy is 31,64 kgCO₂eq./((m²·year). Considering the previous TWC, the GWP related to Water is 0,17 kgCO₂eq./((m²·year). Being the total GWP 31.81 kgCO₂eq./((m²·year).
3. **Operational Energy Costs (OEC):** Costs for energy bills, maintenance of energy systems and installations and other costs for energy services.
 - **Example:** the same office building has annual electricity costs of 10,223 € and annual natural gas costs of 1,686 €. It also has maintenance costs of 912 €/year and 457 €/year for energy services' costs. Thus, the operational energy costs are 34,94 €/((m²·year).
4. **Payback Period:** Time to recover the investment costs
 - **Example:** for an investment of 34,200 € for an energy retrofitting in the previous building, with which the new OEC are 20.89 €/((m²·year). The payback period is then calculated for 6.4 years.
5. **Life Cycle Cost (LCC):** Total costs over life cycle.
 - **Example:** the previous office building has the planned intervention of 34,200 €, with the new OEC of 20,89 €/((m²·year), and with a lifespan of 20 years. The LCC is calculated in 25.39 €/((m²·year).
6. **Energy Circularity Indicator:** Rate of circular energy to total life cycle energy consumption.
 - **Example:** the office building PV production (RES) of 27 MWh/year and a calculated potential energy savings through the implementation of passive measures of 7 MWh/year. Thus, with a total of 79 MWh/year energy consumption, the Energy Circularity of the building is 43%.
7. **Water Circularity Indicator:** Rate of circular water to total life cycle energy consumption.
 - **Example:** the office building has a greywater reused of 33 m³/year and around 20 m³/year of rainwater harvested to be used. Thus, considering the building has a total water consumption of 167 m³/year, the Water Circularity is 32%.
8. **Material Circularity Indicator:** Rate of circular materials to total life cycle energy consumption. These are materials from circular sources, cyclable materials at the end of its use and materials in the use phase with an extended lifespan from average materials.
 - **Example:** the office building has a planned intervention to replace windows, for which the following recycled materials will be used: 300 kg of recycled aluminium and 500 kg of 50% recycled glass (250 kg). The new windows have an extended lifespan of 50 years, which sums up the total weight of them (1,000 kg). The total weight of the intervention (including the disposal of old windows) is 86%.

Figure 29: Example scenario for the evaluation of a CH building for the KPIs in Pillar 2

Pillar 3: Resilience to Climate and Human-made Hazards KPIs

Example Scenario: residential building in France

1. **Inventory of relevant Hazards:** Existence of an Inventory of Hazards (answered from 1 to 5 according to certain criteria).
 - **Example:** a residential building in France has an inventory of the most relevant hazards that affect the building. A 3-score is assigned because the main hazards are identified and partially documented (although not complete information for all of them).
2. **Hazards Identification:** List of the most significant climate or human-made hazards that affect the building (assessed with a 1-5 scoring criteria).
 - **Example:** a residential building in France has a well documented list of the potential hazards that may occur to the building, however the documentation is located in different places (depending on to what they are related with). Thus, the assigned score is 4, according to the criteria described.
3. **Risk Management Plan(s):** Checks the existence of management plans for risks, hazards or vulnerabilities through adaptation, mitigation and/or other response. It is assessed through a checklist in which a total of 9 aspects needs to be answered with Yes/No, and the score is provided from 1 to 5 depending on the number of "Yes" answers obtained.
 - **Example:** the same residential building has a risks management plan, and according to the checklist, a total of 3 "Yes" answers have been obtained, which corresponds to a score of 3.
4. **Risk Impact assessment: Vulnerability and Exposure:** Qualitative assessment of the risk impact. It is done with a matrix of 1-5 scale for the vulnerability and exposure of each identified hazard.
 - **Example:** the residential building in France has three main hazards identified: flooding, extreme temperature events and fire. From the matrix assessment, it resulted that flooding is moderate, extreme temperature events is high and fire is low. Thus, the total assessment is 3.
5. **Risk Impact Level evaluation: Severity of consequences and Likelihood of occurrence:** Qualitative assessment of the risk impact level. It is done with a matrix of 1-5 scale for the severity of consequences and likelihood of occurrence of each identified hazard.
 - **Example:** the residential building in France has three main hazards identified: flooding, extreme temperature events and fire. From the matrix assessment, it resulted that flooding is moderate, extreme temperature events is low and fire is moderate. Thus, the total assessment is 2.7.

Figure 30: Example scenario for the evaluation of a CH building for the KPIs in Pillar 3

Pillar 4: Accessibility, Inclusiveness, Openness and Socioeconomic Sustainability KPIs
Example Scenario: residential building in Poland & museum building in Poland

1. **Accessibility level:** Assessment of the access route and within it, the possible accessibility restrictions or architectural barriers. It is assessed with a checklist of 31 questions that should be answered with Yes/No for the cases that they apply to the building.
 - **Example:** a residential building in Poland has been assessed through the questionnaire and obtained an Accessibility Level of 13.64%.
2. **Inclusiveness and openness level:** Evaluation of the inclusiveness and openness of the building, which are related with the accessibility, universal design, safety, community engagement, affordability or policy and practice to support diversity. It is assessed with a checklist of 38 questions that should be answered with Yes/No for the cases that they apply to the building.
 - **Example:** a residential building in Poland has been assessed with the questionnaire and obtained an Inclusiveness and Openness Level of 28%.
3. **Direct revenue from Tourism:** the revenue generated directly from the historic building itself, such as entry fees and souvenirs.
 - **Example:** a museum in a historical building in Poland receives around 2,000 visitors a month, with an entry fee of 20 PL (4.60 €), what would be a monthly revenue of 9.200 €. With a maintenance costs of 600 €/month, the museum appears to be self-sustaining, and thus a P is assigned.
4. **Indirect revenue from Tourism:** the revenue generated indirectly from the popularity of the historic building, impacting in local businesses that are close by.
 - **Example:** the museum in a historical building in Poland is the most important CH building in the city, and thereby it receives so much attention and the restaurants and other local business around it receive the attraction of tourists. Thus, a P is assigned.
5. **Increased property value:** the actual increase of value of the property due to the increase in popularity or other contributing factors.
 - **Example:** due to the recent attention that the historic museum building has received, the city has become better known and receives more tourism, which in turn makes the museum to receive more visitors (endless loop). This is why a Q is assigned, assuming around 5-15% has increased.
6. **Number of local jobs created:** the percentage of the total jobs which have been given to local residents from the positive impact of the monument.
 - **Example:** in this case, a R has been assigned, as the extra attention received by the monument has not affected the local jobs in a significant/quantifiable manner.
7. **Investment in public infrastructure:** the investments made due to the historic building's presence, which highlights how it is driving broader improvements in the area.
 - **Example:** in this case, a R has been assigned, as no additional investments have been made so far in the area nearby due to the CH building.
8. **Cultural Enrichment:** the contribution of the CH building to the local cultural scene (e.g. events, festivals).
 - **Example:** a R has been assigned also in this KPI, as no events or other cultural affairs have been organised so far due to the presence of the CH building.
9. **Public perception:** the public sentiment towards the CH building's impact on the community.
 - **Example:** a Q has been assigned to this KPI, as it causes a neutral feeling in the population.

Figure 31: Example scenario for the evaluation of a CH building for the KPIs in Pillar 4

For the **visualisation in the score card**, a radar chart (spider chart) visualizes the achievement percentage for each pillar, with the scores plotted on the axes.

The scoring system works as follows:

- Each pillar is evaluated based on performance against these KPIs.
- Scores are assigned based on performance against the KPIs.
- The achievement percentage shows how close the building or site is to achieving the optimal.
- A score is also provided for each pillar.

The radar chart is explained with the following elements:

- The radar chart provides a visual representation of the performance across all pillars.
- Each point on the chart represents the achievement percentage for a pillar.
- The area covered by the chart gives an overall sense of balance and performance across different metrics.

In the following Figure 32 the example of the score card is shown, including both the scores in each pillar and the radar chart.

Figure 32: Example of the calculated scorecard (screenshot from the minimum viable product of the INHERIT tool for Multi-dimensional Assessment)

The following conclusions can be extracted from this example:

- **Pillar 1. Energy Performance and Indoor Environmental Quality**
 - Achievement: 56%
 - Interpretation: The site has moderate performance in energy efficiency and indoor environmental quality. There is some room for improvement in energy management and indoor conditions.
- **Pillar 2. Resource Efficiency, Circularity, and LCC**
 - Achievement: 40%
 - Interpretation: The site shows moderate or quite low performance in managing resources efficiently and maintaining a circular economy approach. Life cycle costs are in a moderate range, with significant room to be optimized further.
- **Pillar 3. Resilience to Climate and Human-made Hazards**
 - Achievement: 41%
 - Interpretation: The site's resilience measures are almost insufficient and could be enhanced to better withstand climate-related and human-made risks.
- **Pillar 4. Accessibility, Inclusiveness, Openness, and Socioeconomic Sustainability**
 - Achievement: 46%
 - Interpretation: The site performs moderately well in ensuring accessibility and inclusiveness, contributing positively to socioeconomic sustainability. However, there is still potential for further inclusivity and openness improvements.

4.2. Assessment Tool Implementation

The INHERIT Assessment tool is available at <https://assesstool-inherit.euinno.eu/>, is being developed as a web service. The tool may be migrated to a new address once the INHERIT toolkit is made available. The backend service relies on a relational DB, and the front end/ user interface is using React. Its first release focuses on the assessment of the CH buildings by assessors. This initial release is extended to support the monitoring of the assessments by the different stakeholders as outlined in the technical specification of the application.

It should be also noted that the service design and implementation support interoperability and exposes a RESTful API to allow the communication and data exchange with other services. In Table 18 an example is provided with the data structure used in the application development:

Table 18: Example of the data structure used in the application development for the framework assessment

```
[
  {
    "id": "1.1",
    "name": "Energy intensity (total)",
    "currentValue": 42,
    "targetValue": 30,
    "positiveContribution": 0,
    "pillarWeight": 25,
    "kpiWeight": 1.25,
    "achievement": 71,
    "score": 0.00
  },
  {
    "id": "1.1.1",
    "name": "Energy intensity (heating)",
    "currentValue": 20,
    "targetValue": 12,
    "positiveContribution": 0,
    "pillarWeight": 25,
    "kpiWeight": 1.25,
    "achievement": 60,
    "score": 0.75
  },
  {
    "id": "1.1.2",
    "name": "Energy intensity (cooling)",
    "currentValue": 10,
    "targetValue": 8,
    "positiveContribution": 0,
    "pillarWeight": 25,
    "kpiWeight": 1.25,
    "achievement": 80,
    "score": 1.00
  },
  // more KPI objects
]
```

5. INHERIT Hub of measures

The INHERIT Hub of Measures is an inventory of solutions for the prevention, monitoring, management, and renovation of cultural heritage sites. The catalogue includes measures for cultural heritage sites' materials, envelope and systems for their modernisation towards energy and resource efficiency, climate and human-made hazards resilience, health and comfort, inclusiveness and accessibility. The measures should be cost-effective, less-disruptive, affordable, feasible and acceptable.

The catalogue aims to be a tool to support decision-making providing a preliminary selection of interventions to be evaluated in the modernisation of cultural heritage sites. For that reason, the measures will be characterized and classified according to different criteria such as building components, impact, KPIs, requirements, constraints, etc. The INHERIT Hub of Measures will be created to enable smart filtering. The inventory allows to automatically select a set of measures that meet the criteria pre-defined by the user.

The **methodology** used to elaborate the INHERIT Hub of measures inventory consists of three main steps, as can be seen also in Figure 33:

- **Measures collection:** it consists of creating a list of measures according to the literature review and the expertise of the partners involved in the task.
- **Measure template or datasheet:** it consists of developing a template or datasheet to characterise and document all the measures collected.
- **Catalogue:** It consists of filling in the technical datasheet of every collected measure and assembling them in a book or catalogue.

Figure 33: Inventory of measures Methodology for development

These three steps will be repeated in three **implementation waves** (see also Figure 34):

- **Initiation wave:** A global information search is conducted, and a list of the most important references is compiled. Once the list is compiled, the most relevant information from each reference is gathered.
- **Enrichment wave:** After the information is gathered, it is refined to retain only the most relevant details, and additional data is added as needed. The most interesting way to present the information is also determined.
- **Consolidation wave:** Finally, the information is grouped according to the chosen design.

Figure 34: Implementation waves of the methodology for the Hub of Measures development

This section explains the progress and status of the INHERIT Hub of Measures up to date. The work done corresponds to the initiation wave and can be summarized in following actions:

- Create an Excel sheet to list measures and tag them according to different criteria.
- Collect measures from literature review, partners' expertise and project solutions.
- Analyse, organise and classify the collected measures.
- Develop the first datasheet (template) to document the measures.

Following, the list of measures collected, the measures analysis and the datasheet developed will be explained.

The first Hub of Measures has been gathered considering following headings:

- **ID:** It is a numeric identifier that lists the measures (starting with #1).
- **Description:** This is a summary that highlights the most important features of the measure. It can also include more specific information.
- **Additional information:** Adds information on the requirements necessary to implement these measures in cultural heritage buildings.
- **INHERIT Pillars:** It classifies the measures according to their relation or impact in the INHERIT pillars (**Pillar 1:** Energy & Comfort, **Pillar 2:** Resources & Circularity, **Pillar 3:** Climate & Human Hazard Resilience and **Pillar 4:** Accessibility & Inclusiveness). A measure can belong to more than one pillar.
- **Measure group:** Classify measures into groups according to the system or building component to which each measure applies. The groups of measures have been defined as:
 - *Insulation system*, ● *Window system*, ● *Shadow system*, ● *Lighting system*, ● *Control system*, ● *HVAC system*, ● *DHW system*, ● *Appliances*, ● *RES integration*, ● *Digitalization system*, ● *Materials*, ● *Water system*, ● *Electrical system*, ● *Structural system*, ● *Accessibility*, ● *Programmes*, ● *Socioeconomic* and ● *Others*.
- **Technical Inspection Headings:** It classifies measures according to the headings of the Technical Inspection Methodology (from section 2): ● *Foundations & Structure*, ● *Façade &*

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Roofs, ● Energy system, ● Biodegradation & Water tightness, ● Accessibility and ● Smart system.

- **Phase:** It classifies the measures according to the phase in which they can be implemented. (● *Design & Renovation*, ● *Monitoring, Operation & Management*, ● *Preservation & Maintenance*).
- **Pilot site:** Name the pilot in which the measure is applied.
- **Reference:** Name the reference sites from which the information was obtained.
- **Partner:** Name of the partner who proposed this measure.

The following Figure 35 shows how this initial information of the measures was gathered.

HUB of Measures inventory for efficient, inclusive, resilient and low-emission						
ID	Measure Name	Measure Group	Description	Additional Information	INHERIT Pillars	Partner
#1	LED lighting	Lighting system	Change fluorescents or halogen lamps by LED lamps	It is a measure feasible regardless the protection level of the building and with low technical requirements	Pillar 1: energy & comfort	CEM
#2	Facade external insulation	Envelope insulation / passive measure	Insulation of the façade from the outside	Depends on the level of protection	Pillar 1: energy & comfort	REGEA
#3	Façade internal insulation	Envelope insulation / passive measure	Insulation of the façade from the inside	It would be only feasible for certain parts of the building less protected, or in the case that the indoor envelope is already modified for a different/current use.	Pillar 1: energy & comfort	CARTIF
HUB of Measures inventory for efficient, inclusive, resilient and low-emission						
ID	Measure Name	Measure Group	Description	Additional Information	INHERIT Pillars	Partner
#15	Heat pump installation	Change of energy systems / Active measure	(including heating distribution and heating elements) should lead to a proposal for a heating system concept that uses renewable energy sources and enables adequate temperature regulation in the rooms. Preference is given to the use of a heat pump.		Pillar 1: energy & comfort	REGEA
#16	Cooling system modernisation	Change of energy systems / Active measure	In order to perform thermal insulation, the existing external air conditioning units must be removed. It is necessary to propose the replacement of split units with new ones or to foresee a central cooling system.	It is necessary to foresee the positions of external air conditioning units in such a way that they do not ruin the original author's design of the building.	Pillar 1: energy & comfort	REGEA
#17	Mechanical ventilation with recuperation	Change of energy systems / Active measure	It is necessary to design a mechanical ventilation system with heat recovery.	It is necessary to check the impact of the element of the ventilation system on the facade and other structural parts of the building, as well as on the technical and functional conditions of use of the space, considering the purpose of the building.	Pillar 1: energy & comfort	REGEA
HUB of Measures inventory for efficient, inclusive, resilient and low-emission						
ID	Measure Name	Measure Group	Description	Additional Information	INHERIT Pillars	Partner
#35	Insulation of the attic and technical basemen	passive measure	measures to be undertaken: rinning an reflective membrane to insulate the building's plinth and technical basement is also essential. While it is not feasible to insulate the facades from the exterior, alternative renovation solutions must be explored.	This is a measure feasible regardless the level of protection of the building and with low technical requirements	Pillar 1: energy & comfort	RPR
#36	Mechanical ventilation with recuperation	Change of energy systems / Active measure	It is necessary to design a mechanical ventilation system with heat recovery.	It is necessary to check the impact of the element of the ventilation system on the facade and other structural parts of the building, as well as on the technical and functional conditions of use of the space, considering the purpose of the building.	Pillar 1: energy & comfort	RPR
#37	Low-budget renovations	Envelope insulation / passive measure	Soft measures, in particular low cost energy efficiency measures and building renovation strategies, such as repairing leaks in roofs, insulating hot water pipes/exposed pipes, and draught proofing/fixing air leakages around windows and doors		Pillar 1: energy & comfort	ICCS

Figure 35: Example of the initial information collected for the Hub of Measures in the template provided

5.1. List of measures

83 measures have been collected so far and classified. Next, there is a table per group of measures (Table 19 to Table 35), as the main structure for the measures' classification. Within the tables, the set of measures included in each group are depicted and characterised according to some main aspects:

- **Name** of the measure
- Brief **description** of it
- **INHERIT pillars** to which it relates: **Pillar 1** (Energy Performance and IEQ), **Pillar 2** (Resource efficiency, Circularity and LCC), **Pillar 3** (Resilience to climate and human-

made hazards), and **Pillar 4** (Accessibility, Inclusiveness, Openness and Socioeconomic sustainability).

- **Heading of the Technical Inspection (TI)** to which it relates: **1** (Foundations and structures), **2** (Façades and roofs), **3** (Installations), **4** (Biodegradation, water tightness and beauty), **5** (Accessibility), and **6** (Functional behaviour – intelligent domotic/ inmotoc system).
- **Phase of the building life cycle** to which it can be applied: **I** (Design and renovation), **II** (Monitoring, operation and management), and **III** (Preservation and maintenance).
- “Is the measure feasible for highly protected (HP) CH buildings?": Yes/No.

● Insulation system

This group of measures include solutions for insulation system. 7 measures have been included in this group, and are characterised using an insulation system on the building envelope. This system is designed to minimize heat transfer between the exterior and interior of the building. The primary goal is to enhance energy efficiency, provide thermal comfort, and reduce heating and cooling costs. The Table 19 summarizes this group of measures:

Table 19: Set of measures for insulation system

ID	Name	Description	INHERIT Pillars	TI Heading	Life cycle phase	Feasible for HP
#1	Façade external insulation	Exterior Thermal Insulation system to improve the energy efficiency of buildings by thermally insulating them from the outside. The main components are: Thermal insulation (XPS, EPS, mineral wool, or polyurethane), Fastening system and Coating.	Pillar 1	2	I	No
#2	Façade internal insulation	Insulation of the façade from the inside.	Pillar 1	2	I	No
#3	Façade intermediate insulation	Insulation of the cavity wall and air chamber (if any in the CH building).	Pillar 1	2	I	No
#4	Roof external insulation	Waterproofing and Roof Insulation System to improve the energy efficiency of buildings. For example: a vapor barrier, a half sandwich panel (waterproof particleboard, XPS core, and self-adhesive waterproofing membrane), and ceramic tile with polyurethane foam.	Pillar 1	2	I	No
#5	Roof internal insulation	Insulation of the roof (pitched or flat) from the inside.	Pillar 1	2	I	No
#6	Green Roof Installation	Installing green roofs or rooftop gardens helps insulate, reduce storm runoff, and boost biodiversity, while mitigating heat island effects.	Pillar 1	2	I	No
#7	Floor insulation	Insulation of the basement floor.	Pillar 1	2	I	No

- **Window system**

This group of measures include solutions for windows. 10 measures have been included, and they are characterised by offering solutions to common window problems such as heat loss in winter, heat gain in summer, insufficient thermal insulation and air leakage. The Table 20 summarizes this group of measures:

Table 20: Set of measures for window system

ID	Name	Description	INHERIT Pillars	TI Heading	Life cycle phase	Feasible for HP
#8	Natural lighting prioritization	Prioritize natural light over artificial light. This measure leads to a reduction in energy consumption and an increase in visual comfort.	Pillar 1	2	I	No
#9	Window and door restoration	It is possible to restore the existing doors and windows.	Pillar 1	2	I	No
#10	Windows sealing	Introducing weather stripping or sealing of the joints in doors and windows to reduce infiltration.	Pillar 1	2	I	No
#11	Windows with a low emissivity coating	The use of low emissivity coated windows helps to reduce heat loss, thereby improving the energy efficiency of a building. By maintaining more stable temperatures indoors throughout the year, these windows provide greater thermal comfort for occupants.	Pillar 1	2	I	No
#12	Aluminium carpentry with thermal break	These are aluminium frames designed with a thermal break or interruption in their structure, aimed at reducing the transfer of heat or cold through the material. It consists of two main parts: the aluminium frame and the insulating material.	Pillar 1	2	I	No
#13	Windows with double glazing (air chamber)	Change of the windows by double glazing windows with air chamber.	Pillar 1	2	I	No
#14	Windows with triple glazing (air chamber)	Change of the windows by triple glazing windows with air chamber.	Pillar 1	2	I	No
#15	Windows with double glazing (argon gas)	Windows with argon gas fill are those that have a layer of this gas between their glass panels. This configuration improves the thermal insulation of the building by reducing the transfer of heat through the windows. This leads to a decrease in energy consumption for heating and cooling, providing greater thermal comfort for	Pillar 1	2	I	No

ID	Name	Description	INHERIT Pillars	TI Heading	Life cycle phase	Feasible for HP
		occupants and preventing condensation issues.				
#16	Windows with triple glazing (argon gas)	Windows with argon gas fill are those that have a layer of this gas between their glass panels. This configuration improves the thermal insulation of the building by reducing the transfer of heat through the windows. This leads to a decrease in energy consumption for heating and cooling, providing greater thermal comfort for occupants and preventing condensation issues.	Pillar 1	2	I	No
#17	Windows new all (low emissivity, double glazing, argon, aluminium, thermal break)		Pillar 1	2	I	No

- **Shadow system**

This group of measures include solutions for shadows. Only a measure has been included in this group. It is characterised by providing solutions to problems caused by solar radiation, thus reducing heat gain and protecting materials from damage caused by UV radiation. The Table 21 summarizes this group of measures:

Table 21: Set of measures for shadow system

ID	Name	Description	INHERIT Pillars	TI Heading	Life cycle phase	Feasible for HP
#18	Sun protection/sun shading for historic buildings	Implement energy-efficient and culturally sensitive sun protection strategies for the cultural heritage building to reduce solar heat gain and protect sensitive materials from UV radiation damage. this can also help regulate the heat comfort of the building. can be achieved both on the exterior (retractable or fixed awnings to match architectural style, extending the roofline to provide shade, trees and vegetation for shade) or interior (movable blinds or shades or UV-filtering window films).	Pillar 1	2	I	No

- **Lighting system**

This group of measures include solutions for lighting. 5 measures have been included in this group, and they are characterised by offering solutions to reduce lighting energy consumption and provide greater visual comfort. The Table 22 summarizes this group of measures:

Table 22: Set of measures for lighting system

ID	Name	Description	INHERIT Pillars	TI Heading	Life cycle phase	Feasible for HP
#19	LED lighting	Change fluorescents or halogen lamps by LED lamps and replacement of concert lights/spotlights. Change of electrical wiring as well.	Pillar 1	3	II	Yes
#20	Lighting sensors	A lighting sensor monitors the number of lumens in a room to verify compliance with regulations and ensure uniform, indirect lighting.	Pillar 1	3	II	Yes
#21	Occupancy sensors	It provides information on the number of people in an enclosure. Install occupancy sensors in spaces to be able to control lighting and HVAC based on their number.	Pillar 1	3	II	Yes
#22	Lighting Controls	These controllers allow for multiple options such as adjusting the lighting intensity, scheduling usage times, or using an occupancy sensor to turn the lighting on and off. Reduces energy consumption and allows lighting control.	Pillar 1	3	II	Yes
#63	Modernization of the lightning protection system	Foreseen the removal and replacement of the existing lightning protection system with a new one. It is necessary to examine the existing grounding system and, if necessary, design a new grounding system.	Pillar 3	1	I	No

- **Control system**

This group of measures include solutions for control system. 6 measures have been included, and they are characterised by using sensors and control equipment to monitor building consumption. This monitoring makes it possible to identify the points with excess energy consumption, facilitating its reduction and the optimization of resources. In addition, monitoring makes it possible to control the building's interior conditions, such as humidity, temperature and air quality, thus improving the comfort and health of the occupants. The Table 23 summarizes this group of measures:

Table 23: Set of measures for control system

ID	Name	Description	INHERIT Pillars	TI Heading	Life cycle phase	Feasible for HP
#21	Occupancy sensors	It provides information on the number of people in an enclosure. Install occupancy sensors in spaces to be able to control lighting and HVAC based on their number.	Pillar 1	3	II	Yes

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ID	Name	Description	INHERIT Pillars	TI Heading	Life cycle phase	Feasible for HP
#22	Lighting Controls	These controllers allow for multiple options such as adjusting the lighting intensity, scheduling usage times, or using an occupancy sensor to turn the lighting on and off. Reduces energy consumption and allows lighting control.	Pillar 1	3	II	Yes
#41	Temperature sensors	These sensors are used to measure the ambient temperature in different areas of a building or space and provide feedback to the HVAC system to regulate the temperature efficiently.	Pillar 1	3	II	Yes
#42	EQ sensors	It is necessary to foresee the installation of additional sensors that will monitor the conditions in the building and manage the operation of other equipment. It is necessary to provide sensors for CO2 (optionally also CO), humidity, temperature, pressure, PM1, PM2.5 and PM10 particles, room lighting, presence sensors and sensors that detect the opening of windows and doors. It is necessary to foresee the integration of the mentioned sensors with the regulation of the heating, cooling, DHW preparation, ventilation, lighting, sun protection, etc.	Pillar 1	3	II	Yes
#43	Implementation of a system for remote measurement of energy consumption	It is necessary to foresee the installation of a system for remote measurement of the consumption of energy, which includes the installation, commissioning and testing of the system according to the "functional turnkey" system. The central processing unit in which all consumption data will be collected and recorded, should be integrated into the "central monitoring and control system".	Pillar 1 and Pillar 2	3	II	Yes
#44	Implementation of a system for remote measurement of water consumption	It is necessary to foresee the installation of a system for remote measurement of the consumption of water, which includes the installation, commissioning and testing of the system according to the "functional turnkey" system. The central processing unit in which all consumption data will be collected and recorded, should be integrated into the "central monitoring and control system".	Pillar 1 and Pillar 2	3	II	Yes

- **HVAC system**

This group of measures include solutions for HVAC system (heating ventilation and air conditioning). 15 measures have been included in the group, and they are characterised by offering solutions to improve the energy efficiency of HVAC equipment, reduce energy consumption, improve occupant comfort and provide greater control and flexibility. The Table 24 summarizes this group of measures:

Table 24: Set of measures for HVAC system

ID	Name	Description	INHERIT Pillars	TI Heading	Life cycle phase	Feasible for HP
#23	District Heating System	District heating networks offer great potential for efficient, cost-effective, and flexible large-scale use of low-carbon energy for heating.	Pillar 1	3	I	No
#24	Boiler - Natural Gas Condensing	Change of boiler by a Condensing natural gas boiler (with a nominal capacity at least of 97 KW)	Pillar 1	3	I	No
#25	Boiler - Biomass	Change of boiler by a Biomass boiler (with a nominal capacity at least of 60 KW)	Pillar 1	3	I	No
#26	Heat pump - Direct expansion	Analysis of the existing heating system with all elements (including heating distribution and heating elements) should lead to a proposal for a heating system concept that uses renewable energy sources and enables adequate temperature regulation in the rooms. Preference is given to the use of a heat pump.	Pillar 1	3	I	No
#27	Heat pump - Geothermal (ground source)	Analysis of the existing thermal system and consideration of GHSP system installation	Pillar 1	3	I	No
#28	Radiant heating system	Systems using direct radiant heaters reduce the problem that occurs with convection heating, related to the upward movement of warm air because people are heated by means of electromagnetic waves, whereas the air in the room is heated indirectly, because of heat emission by elements that have already been heated.	Pillar 1	3	I	No
#29	Reconstruction of the heating system and thermostat for control of heating according to system scheduling	Complete reconstruction of the heating system. Replacing all radiators and considering the possibility of building an infrared heating system in the concert hall, so that the entire volume of the room does not have to be heated. Possibilities to create heating of different zones with effective adjustment options. Control Thermostat system scheduling.	Pillar 1	3	I	No

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ID	Name	Description	INHERIT Pillars	TI Heading	Life cycle phase	Feasible for HP
#30	Energy-Efficient HVAC Systems	Upgrade heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) systems to energy-efficient models with programmable thermostats and zoning capabilities.	Pillar 1:	3	I	No
#31	Heat recovery	Incorporation of a heat recovery unit. This system reduces cooling and heating consumption due to ventilation.	Pillar 1	3	I	No
#32	Mechanical ventilation with recuperation	It is necessary to design a mechanical ventilation system with heat recovery.	Pillar 1	3	I	No
#33	Variable airflow fans	Variable airflow fans adjust their speed and air flow according to the system's needs, reducing energy consumption by adapting to the actual HVAC demand. This leads to more efficient operation, savings in operating costs, and greater comfort for occupants by ensuring adequate air supply.	Pillar 1	3	I	No
#34	High-efficiency filters	The use of high-efficiency filters in heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) systems helps to improve indoor air quality by trapping smaller particles and pollutants. This leads to lower energy consumption, as the HVAC system doesn't need to work as hard to compensate for the presence of contaminants. Additionally, high-efficiency filters can prolong the system's lifespan and reduce the need for maintenance, further contributing to lower energy consumption in the long term.	Pillar 1	3	I	No
#35	Variable water flow pumps	Variable flow pumps adjust their speed and water flow according to the system's needs, reducing energy consumption by adapting to the actual water demand	Pillar 1	3	I	No
#36	Storage systems	The installation of hot/cold water tanks in an air conditioning system can significantly affect the energy performance of the installation.	Pillar 1	3	I	No
#37	Increase the design temperature of the chilled water	Increasing the temperature of chilled water in air conditioning systems has advantages such as lower energy consumption and investment costs, along with a reduction in the risk of condensation.	Pillar 1	3	I	No

- **DHW system**

This group of measures include solutions for domestic hot water (DHW) system. Only one measure has been included in this group, and it is characterised by offering solutions to produce hot water in a more efficient and sustainable way. The Table 25 summarizes this group of measures:

Table 25: Set of measures for DHW system

ID	Name	Description	INHERIT Pillars	TI Heading	Life cycle phase	Feasible for HP
#38	Solar thermal panels	Replacement of typical Domestic Hot Water (DHW) systems, with Solar Domestic Hot Water (SDHW) systems, which include a supplementary heater (e.g. an integrated electric heater) to cover the total annual hot water demand of a household.	Pillar 1	3	I	No

- **Appliances**

This group of measures include solutions for appliances. Two measures have been included, and they are characterised by offering solutions to reduce the consumption of appliances. The Table 26 summarizes this group of measures:

Table 26: Set of measures for appliances

ID	Name	Description	INHERIT Pillars	TI Heading	Life cycle phase	Feasible for HP
#39	White appliances replacement	Replacement of conventional washing machines, kitchens, refrigerators with more energy-efficient models (i.e. of a higher energy class).	Pillar 1	3	I	No
#40	Prevent excessive use of air conditioning since it is threatening the energy supply	Over consumption of energy can be prevented through adjusting thermostat settings and selection of efficient equipment	Pillar 1	3	I	No

- **RES integration**

This group of measures include solutions for renewable energy sources integration. 4 measures have been identified, and they are characterised by the use of renewable sources for electricity generation and domestic hot water production, which allows greater independence from the electrical system and boilers. The Table 27 summarizes this group of measures:

Table 27: Set of measures for RES integration

ID	Name	Description	INHERIT Pillars	TI Heading	Life cycle phase	Feasible for HP
#38	Solar thermal panels	Replacement of typical Domestic Hot Water (DHW) systems, with Solar Domestic Hot Water (SDHW) systems, which include a supplementary heater (e.g. an integrated	Pillar 1	3	I	No

ID	Name	Description	INHERIT Pillars	TI Heading	Life cycle phase	Feasible for HP
		electric heater) to cover the total annual hot water demand of a household.				
#45	PV (+/- storage)	An electric energy production system will be incorporated by means of photovoltaic panels typically placed on the roofs or parking canopies. Incorporating a photovoltaic system reduces a building's energy consumption.	Pillar 1	3	I	No
#46	PV panels in the parking lot	Placement of photovoltaic panels in the parking area (if available) in order to produce electricity for ev chargers or self-consumption and to provide shade for cars	Pillar 1	3	I	No
#47	EV chargers	Examine the possibility of setting up a charger for electric vehicles.	Pillar 1	3	I	No

- **Digitalization system**

This group of measures include solutions for digitalization systems. 10 measures have been included, and they are the services offered by INHERIT, which are characterised by being innovative technical solutions. The Table 28 summarizes this group of measures:

Table 28: Set of measures for digitalisation system

ID	Name	Description	INHERIT Pillars	TI Heading	Life cycle phase	Feasible for HP
#48	Modelling & simulation environment	The aim of this service is to assess renovation strategies for three pilots. The service will use a bottom-up simulation model to derive dynamic simulations calibrated with in-situ measurements for each building. The service will help us understand the energy-saving potential of different renovation actions in these buildings and should guide owners and facilitators of historical buildings to apply cost-effective energy efficiency measures.	Pillar 1 and Pillar 2	3	I	Yes
#49	IEQ and thermal comfort optimisation	The final objective of the service is to improve the comfort of the CH building occupants. This will be done using data-driven models that measure thermal, visual, and acoustic comfort, as well as indoor air quality, and provide recommendations for improving overall IEQ. More specifically, the models will support the evaluation of the IEQ across its different components in key areas of the buildings, the detection of anomalies and bad practices, and the proposal of changes in building occupants' behaviour and building's operational settings that balance health and	Pillar 1	3	II	Yes

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ID	Name	Description	INHERIT Pillars	TI Heading	Life cycle phase	Feasible for HP
		safety with energy consumption. When possible, users' feedback will also be exploited to enhance the insights provided by the service.				
#50	Energy forecasting and intelligent management		Pillar 1	3	II	Yes
#51	Digital Twin for Heritage facilities real time monitoring operation & management	The digital twin to be developed is a virtual replica of the cultural heritage building and is used to provide meaningful information about the CH operation & management (energy & comfort) to building users and maintenance managers. The digital twin of cultural heritage encompasses a wide range of elements. This includes static data derived from BIM models detailing cultural heritage and its systems, to dynamic data provided monitoring systems. Additionally, data processing generates performance indicators and scores for both the cultural heritage and users. Finally, energy performance models are included to simulate different scenarios and conduct "what-if" analyses to evaluate potential energy conservation measures.	Pillar 1; Pillar 2; Pillar 3; and Pillar 4	3	II	Yes
#52	Real-time insights on activity and mobility partners	The service provides pilot administrators and staff with real-time data and analytics regarding visitor activity and mobility within the premises. By leveraging advanced tracking technologies and data analytics, this service offers valuable real-time insights into visitor behaviour, crowd flow patterns, and more. This information helps management optimize visitor experiences, allocate resources efficiently, and make data-driven decisions to enhance overall operations.	Pillar 1 and Pillar 4	3	II	Yes
#53	Preventive maintenance with H-BIM	The goal of this service is to integrate data derived from technical inspections into a collaborative H-BIM model with a referenced information structure, enabling a global analysis of interventions in historic buildings and improving their maintenance costs and sustainability. The tool complies with European standards, including BIM level 2 and energy performance improvement. It ensures	Pillar 1 and Pillar 2	3	III	Yes

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ID	Name	Description	INHERIT Pillars	TI Heading	Life cycle phase	Feasible for HP
#54	GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance	interoperability using non-proprietary formats such as IFC.	Pillar 1; Pillar 2; Pillar 3: and Pillar 4	3	III	Yes
#70	Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios	The service calculates the current energy demand of the building stock and the evolution of such energy demand according to different climate change scenarios. This allows to analyse the effects of different future climate scenarios on the building stock energy performance, providing an understanding of how the building stock energy demand will be affected in the future by climate change. The most relevant impacts affecting CH buildings according to the most prominent climate hazards will be assessed, calculating relevant KPIs that will be impacted by different climate scenarios.	Pillar 3	3	III	Yes
#86	Interactive screen use & AR-VR interfaces	The objective is to promote the design and construction of the renovation of heritage buildings through the development of a platform where the user can interact. This service will encompass the hardware and software tools enabling H-BIM /Digital Twins to reduce maintenance and renovation time and improve work quality, and support on-the-job training. In addition, it will evaluate optimising costs and schedules, promoting engagement with stakeholders and onsite personnel, and allowing on-site users to familiarize themselves with the site before any work begins through pre-training.	Pillar 4:	3	I	Yes
#87	Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	The goal of this tool will be to develop and apply a MCDA methodological framework to improve the condition of the historical buildings through efficient decision-making for optimal renovation considering environmental, economic, cultural heritage and societal factors as well as stakeholders' needs.		3	I	Yes

- **Materials**

This group of measures include solutions for materials. Two measures have been included, and they are characterised by providing alternatives that promote the circularity of materials. The Table 29 summarizes this group of measures:

Table 29: Set of measures for materials

ID	Name	Description	INHERIT Pillars	TI Heading	Life cycle phase	Feasible for HP
#57	Reclaimed Materials	Use reclaimed or salvaged materials for restoration projects to reduce the environmental impact of construction and preserve historical authenticity	Pillar 2	4	I and III	Yes
#58	Local Materials Sourcing	Source construction materials locally to reduce transportation-related emissions and support regional economies, prioritizing materials that are responsibly harvested or manufactured.	Pillar 2	4	I and III	Yes

- **Water system**

This group of measures include solutions for water system. Two measures have been identified, and they are characterised by offering solutions to reduce water consumption. The Table 30 summarizes this group of measures:

Table 30: Set of measures for water system

ID	Name	Description	INHERIT Pillars	TI Heading	Life cycle phase	Feasible for HP
#59	Efficient use of water	In order to limit and reduce water consumption, it is necessary to foresee sensor faucets and toilet cisterns with reduced flushing volume. To store rainwater and use it as technical water for flushing toilets and maintaining grass areas around the building, it is necessary to consider and propose tanks for collecting rainwater.	Pillar 2	4	III	Yes
#60	Replacement of the cold water and sewage system.	Systems need to be rebuilt.	Pillar 2	1	I and III	Yes

- **Electrical system**

This group of measures include solutions for electrical system. Only one measure has been included, and it offers improvements to the electrical system, including maintenance or replacement of components. The Table 31 summarizes this group of measures:

Table 31: Set of measures for electrical system

ID	Name	Description	INHERIT Pillars	TI Heading	Life cycle phase	Feasible for HP
#61	Replacement of the electricity supply and fire suppression system	Systems need to be rebuilt.	Pillar 2	1	I and III	No

- **Structural system**

This group of measures include solutions for structural systems. 5 measures have been identified, and they provide improvements to the structure of CH buildings, including their repair, maintenance, protection and renovation. The Table 32 summarizes this group of measures:

Table 32: Set of measures for structural system

ID	Name	Description	INHERIT Pillars	TI Heading	Life cycle phase	Feasible for HP
#62	Reinforcement of load-bearing structure	The load-bearing structure will be reinforced by repairing cracks that pose a risk to the structural stability of the building.	Pillar 3	1	I and III	No
#63	Moisture protection	Injections with epoxy resins on both sides of the wall at the lowest possible level, and to clean the mortar up to one meter in height with draining type mortar with fungicide properties and interior painting with silicate paint. Other methods to protect walls from moisture are drainage, waterproof barrier, waterproofing finish.	Pillar 3	1	I and III	No
#64	Protection of the metal structure	To preserve the metal structure from corrosion, it is proposed to remove the oxides from the metal profiles by dry blasting.	Pillar 3	1	III	No
#65	Reducing thrust in arches and vaults	Both traditional techniques and materials as well as innovative ones are applied such as prestressing by means of steel or timber tie rods or FRP bars to improve stability	Pillar 3	1	III	No
#66	Reducing slab deformation	Interventions aimed at reducing slab deformation. These techniques vary from traditional prestress strengthening systems using mechanical anchorages, to post-tensioning with anchorages by bonding using an epoxy adhesive, use of fibre reinforced polymers (FRPs) or CFRP strips	Pillar 3	1	III	No

- **Accessibility**

This group of measures include solutions for accessibility improvement. 6 measures have been identified, and they are recognized for providing solutions that promote inclusion, guaranteeing equal opportunities, improving the quality of life and encouraging full participation in society for all

people, regardless of their physical or cognitive abilities. The Table 33 summarizes this group of measures:

Table 33: Set of measures for accessibility

ID	Name	Description	INHERIT Pillars	TI Heading	Life cycle phase	Feasible for HP
#67	Improvement wheelchair accessibility (elevator)	Install an elevator as an alternative path for the access stairs.	Pillar 4	5	I	No
#68	Improvement wheelchair accessibility (ramp)	Build a ramp as an alternative path for the access stairs.	Pillar 4	5	I	No
#69	Handrail	Handrails will be installed on ramps and stairs.	Pillar 4	5	I	No
#70	Audible signage in customer service and elevators	Acoustic signals will be installed at customer service points and elevators to facilitate accessibility for individuals with visual impairments.	Pillar 4	5	I	No
#71	Podotactile pavement	Installation of tactile pavement on accessible routes to improve accessibility for users with reduced visibility. It consists of applying a layer of liquid methacrylate resin on the pavement, on which specific molds are placed to create a particular relief.	Pillar 4	5	I	No
#72	ISA signal	The ISA (International Signal of Access) sign is a symbol that indicates the accessibility of a place for people with disabilities. Accessible entrances to the building, accessible routes, accessible parking spaces and accessible restrooms (toilet, changing room and accessible shower) shall be marked with ISA, supplemented, if necessary, with directional arrows.	Pillar 4	5	I	Yes

● Programmes

This group of measures includes programmes' solutions. Three measures have been identified, and they offer social programmes that contribute to community development by strengthening social ties, encouraging civic participation and promoting collaboration among community members around cultural heritage buildings. The Table 34 summarizes this group of measures:

Table 34: Set of measures for Programmes

ID	Name	Description	INHERIT Pillars	TI Heading	Life cycle phase	Feasible for HP
#73	Cultural Heritage	Develop sustainable tourism strategies that balance visitor access with conservation	Pillar 4	5		Yes

ID	Name	Description	INHERIT Pillars	TI Heading	Life cycle phase	Feasible for HP
	Tourism Management	priorities, minimizing negative impacts on heritage sites and maximizing benefits to local communities				
#74	Historical Interpretation Programs	Development of interpretive programs and exhibits that highlight the environmental history and ecological significance of cultural heritage sites, encouraging a deeper understanding of the interconnectedness between human culture and natural systems	Pillar 4	5		Yes
#75	Heritage Conservation Training Programs	Training programs and workshops on heritage conservation techniques and sustainable practices to empower local communities and professionals.	Pillar 4	5		Yes

- **Socioeconomic**

This group of measures includes socioeconomic solutions. 6 measures have been identified, and they promote job creation, social cohesion and mobility, as well as investment in public infrastructure. The Table 35 summarizes this group of measures:

Table 35: Set of socioeconomic measures

ID	Name	Description	INHERIT Pillars	TI Heading	Life cycle phase	Feasible for HP
#76	Investment in public infrastructure	If a touristic monument is being renovated, this will come with increased popularity (at least for a while as it is "new") which will also likely see an increase in tourism. to better fit the needs of these visitors and locals (as it might lead to congestion) it might occur that a change in infrastructure will smoothen things over for both visitors as local people. If the renovation and attraction is big enough, this could even lead to permanent changes in infrastructure.	Pillar 4	5	I	Yes
#77	Local job creation	If more jobs are created locally rather than taking in employers from far away, then this will have a rather positive effect of the local community. including this local community will drive the local economy, which creates room for more improvements	Pillar 4	5		Yes
#78	Partnership with local artist and cultural organization	Partnering with local artist will increase the community involvement and also broadens the interest in the monument. combining this with events will have the added positive effect of generating more revenue through touristic attraction, both directly through entry fees as	Pillar 4	5		Yes

ID	Name	Description	INHERIT Pillars	TI Heading	Life cycle phase	Feasible for HP
		indirectly through spending on other local businesses				
#79	Increasing local activities and events close to the monument	If visitors are given more options to combine with their visit to see a monument or historic building, then this could help in them choosing this destination to visit. People enjoy combining activities when they are visiting an unknown destination as this gives them more value for their trip in total. this increases the likelihood of them picking this destination, which also helps the local economy grow again. having enough additional activities will increase the amount of visitors for the monument, but also the other way around	Pillar 4	5	I	Yes
#80	Offering educational programs	Offering educational programs related to the monument will increase awareness and relevance of the monument for the local economy and environment.	Pillar 4	5	I	Yes
#81	Improving public perception	By improving the public perception of a monument and its activities or events will likely benefit revenue generated by this monument. If there is a more positive public perception this also signals the importance of the monument the local community and economy. If this is made more salient, people will also be more understanding when negative effects due to visual or auditory nuisance or congestion due to overtourism as they can relate more to this and categorize it as positive popularity rather than an irritation they have to deal with.	Pillar 4	5	I	Yes

- **Others**

This group of measures includes other possible solutions. 2 measures have been identified. The Table 35 summarizes this group of measures:

Table 36: Set of Others measures

ID	Name	Description	INHERIT Pillars	TI Heading	Life cycle phase	Feasible for HP
#82	Bike infrastructure (parking)	Examine the possibility of setting up a parking infrastructure for bikes.	Pillar 1	1	I	No
#83	Energy advice and leaflets	Information and communication campaigns for raising public awareness on energy efficiency and induce behavioural change.	Pillar 1	1	III	Yes

Analysis of measures

The first Hub of Measures gathered have been analysed to get an overview and identify weaknesses that should be addressed in the next implementation waves (enrichment). The analysis consisted of identifying the number and percentage of measures addressing:

- Each inherit pillar
- Cutting-edge technologies
- High level CH protection
- Measures to be applied in the inherit pilots

The results, that can be also seen in Figure 36, show that more than half of the measures belong to Pillar 1. From them, only 30% are applicable to highly protected CH buildings. In addition, almost 20% of the measures are implemented in INHERIT pilot projects.

On the other hand, only 10% of the measures belong to pillars 2 and 3. And from them, around 50% are applicable to highly protected cultural heritage buildings in the case of Pillar 2, while 30% for the Pillar 3 case. In addition, 33% of Pillar 2 measures are applied in pilots, while 45% of Pillar 3 measures are implemented in pilots.

Finally, almost 20% of the measures belong to Pillar 4. From these, 70% are applicable to highly protected cultural heritage buildings. However, only 25% of these measures are applied in INHERIT pilots.

Figure 36: First Hub of measures analysis

The conclusions are:

- 83 measures have been collected.
- Few measures in pillar 2 & 3 have been collected in comparison with pillar 1. More measures in pillar 2 and 3 should be searched for in the next waves.
- Only 10 measures (inherit services) include cutting-edge technologies.
- 37 measures can be applied to CH with high level protection.
- 14 measures will be applied in the inherit demo sites. New measures applied to demo sites should be included when the Project progress.
- The resilience measures are applied before the hazard but not during and after the hazard.
- It should be evaluated if the measures should be tagged according to the kind of hazard.

5.2. Measure datasheet

The Figure 37 shows the first version of the datasheet developed to document the INHERIT Measures. The datasheet has the following headings:

- **ID:** Numeric identifier that lists the measures from #1 to #83.
- **Application:** Encompasses the methods, resources and field to which this measure applies.
- **Photo:** Image linked to the measure, it can be a photograph of a component that is part of the measure, or of some process or activity related to it.
- **Generic information:** Covers the most global aspects of a measure. This section includes details such as implementation conditions, advantages, disadvantages, limitations, social impact, visual impact, physical impact, and with what level of CH protection it is compatible.
- **Technical information:** This section includes relevant technical information for a measure, especially when it involves changes to architectural, structural, or systems aspects. The information is divided into technical characteristics, such as thermal resistance, thickness, power, and efficiency; geometric data, such as the height, width, and length of an object; and data related to installation, maintenance, and operation.
- **Impact:** This comprises a set of indicators that demonstrate the impact of the measure. These indicators are related to the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) defined in section 3 (and Annex 2 to Annex 5) of this document.
- **Costs:** This section covers the costs related to the measure. It includes information such as the initial investment cost, the savings involved in implementing the measure, and the time it takes to recover the initial investment.
- **Others:** Includes additional information. This section details the phase in which the measure is implemented, the maturity level of the technology, and the scale of implementation of the measure, i.e., the different levels at which it can be applied.
- **References:** Name of the references from which the measurement information was obtained.

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NAME OF MEASURE

[Description of the measure]

APPLICATION

[Field of application, methods, materials, etc.]

INHERIT PILLAR

[Name of INHERIT pillar(s) to which it belongs]

MEASURE GROUP

[Name of the group or groups of measures to which it belongs]

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS
[Name conditions necessary for the implementation of this measure]

ADVANTAGES
[Name the advantages of this measure]

DISADVANTAGES
[Name the disadvantages of this measure]

LIMITATIONS
[Name the possible limitations of this measure]

SOCIAL ACCEPTATION
[Low / Medium / High]

VISUAL IMPACT
[Low / Medium / High]

PHYSICAL IMPACT
[Low / Medium / High]

CH PROTECTION LEVEL
[Low / Medium / High]

ID #XX

PHOTO

PHOTO

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES

Thermal resistance [(m ² *K)/W]	Value
Thickness [mm]	Value
Power [W]	Value
Efficiency (%)	Value

GEOMETRY DATA

High [mm]	Value
Width[mm]	Value
Large [mm]	Value

INSTALLATION DATA

Installation time [h]	Value
-----------------------	-------

MAINTENANCE DATA

Type of maintenance	Name	Value
Useful life [Years]		

OPERATION DATA
[Needs of operation]

IMPACT

ENERGY EFFICIENCY IMPROVEMENT

DESCRIPTION	KPIs (%)
-------------	----------

COMFORT IMPROVEMENT

DESCRIPTION	KPIs (%)
-------------	----------

RESOURCES EFFICIENCY IMPROVEMENT

DESCRIPTION	KPIs (%)
-------------	----------

CIRCULARITY IMPROVEMENT

DESCRIPTION	KPIs (%)
-------------	----------

RESILIENCE IMPROVEMENT

DESCRIPTION	KPIs (%)
-------------	----------

ACCESSIBILITY IMPROVEMENT

DESCRIPTION	KPIs (%)
-------------	----------

INCLUSIVENESS IMPROVEMENT

DESCRIPTION	KPIs (%)
-------------	----------

OTHER IMPROVEMENT

DESCRIPTION	KPIs (%)
-------------	----------

COSTS

INVESTMENTS
(qualitative / quantitative)

SAVING
(qualitative / quantitative)

ROI
(qualitative / quantitative)

OTHERS

PHASE
[Design and Renovation / Monitoring, Operation and Management / Preservation and maintenance]

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY
[low=research; medium=cutting Edge; high=market]

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION
[Type of building]

REFERENCES

[1] [Name of the reference(s)]

Figure 37: First version of the measure datasheet template (with guidance)

The following Figure 38 and Figure 39 provide an example of the datasheet of a measure filled in.

LED LIGHTING

Change fluorescents or halogen lamps by LED lamps and replacement of concert lights/spotlights.

APPLICATION

This is a measure feasible regardless the level of protection of the building and with low technical requirements.

INHERIT PILLAR
Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort

MEASURE GROUP
Lighting system

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

It is important that the electrical installation is in good condition and that the lamps do not have a significant cultural value.

ADVANTAGES

- Reduce energy consumption.
- Reduce economic costs.
- Increase visual comfort.

DISADVANTAGES

- Cost of initial investment

LIMITATIONS

-

SOCIAL ACCEPTATION
High

VISUAL IMPACT
Low

PHISICAL IMPACT
Low

CH PROTECTION LEVEL
High

ID #19

PHOTO

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES

Lighting power in an office [W/m ²]	5
Lighting power in a house [W/m ²]	2
Lighting power in a museum [W/m ²]	4
Lighting power in a church [W/m ²]	3.5
Efficiency (%)	≈ 80

GEOMETRY DATA

High [mm]	-
Width[mm]	-
Large [mm]	-

INSTALLATION DATA

Installation time [h]	≈ 0.5 [h/lamp]
-----------------------	----------------

MAINTENANCE DATA

Type of maintenance	Cleaning and visual inspection
Useful life [h]	≈ 50 000

OPERATION DATA

In order to perform this measurement, it is necessary to have an electrical installation.

Figure 38: Example of the measure datasheet complete for the LED Lighting measure

IMPACT

ENERGY EFFICIENCY IMPROVEMENT

LIGHTING ENERGY INTENSITY KPIs (kWh/m²)

COMFORT IMPROVEMENT

VISUAL COMFORT KPIs (%)

RESOURCES EFFICIENCY IMPROVEMENT

GLOBAL WARMING POTENTIAL KPIs (kgCO₂e/m²/year)

LIFE CYCLE COST (€/m² year)

COSTS

INVESTMENTS

The final cost of the investment depends on the power of the luminaire, the brand and the number of units. In addition, if they are placed at a considerable height, it may be necessary to use equipment such as cranes. ≈ 15 - 50 [€/m²]

SAVING

The average savings in energy consumption by using LED lights instead of fluorescent lights can range from 50% to 80%.

ROI

(The payback period varies according to the initial investment and savings. However, it is generally stipulated between 2 and 3 years.

OTHERS

PHASE

Monitoring, Operation and Management

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

Installation can be carried out at different levels: only in some rooms, on specific floors or in the whole building.

REFERENCES

[1] NA

Figure 39: Example of the measure datasheet complete for the LED Lighting measure (continuation)

6. Financial sustainability and risk assessment methodology

This section outlines the methodology for assessing the financial sustainability and risk of interventions proposed for cultural heritage buildings. As the project progresses, ensuring that proposed measures are both financially viable and socially acceptable becomes crucial. The methodology focuses on evaluating cost-effectiveness, exploring financial options and understanding social acceptance. The goal is to provide a framework that supports sustainable and inclusive management of cultural heritage sites.

The methodology that will be followed is summarised in Figure 40, and more detailed described hereafter.

Figure 40: Approach to assess the financial sustainability, risk assessment and acceptance of CH measures

● Cost Assessment Analysis

The cost assessment aims to evaluate the financial feasibility of various interventions for CH buildings (INHERIT Hub of measures). Given the challenges of obtaining precise cost estimates, in a generic way and for different countries, interventions will be categorised based on the level of investment they require, such as low, medium or high-cost. This approach helps to understand the financial implications and guide decision-making without the need for exact figures.

The analysis will include three key aspects to categorise the measures based on cost, payback time and overall impact. These will be assessed through rating intervals set for each of the parameters (investment required, payback time and scope of impact, mainly). This rating will be done in a general way using literature research and personal experience from technical experts. It will serve to provide an idea of a cost assessment of the measures, however, there will be no guarantee that the rating applies in every case.

● Risk Assessment Analysis

The risk assessment focuses on identifying and evaluating **financial risks** associated with the proposed interventions. A risk assessment matrix will be developed to categorise and rate potential financial risks, including funding challenges and unexpected costs.

The analysis will cover a risk identification, a risk rating (to evaluate the severity and likelihood of each risk) and financing schemes, to explore various financing options to mitigate the financial risks). The approach will be informed by best practices in financial risk assessment and innovative financing models.

- **Acceptance Analysis**

Understanding social acceptance is essential for the successful implementation of interventions. A questionnaire will be developed to gather feedback from stakeholders, including building managers and users (connected with activities of stakeholder engagement, Multi-Stakeholder Forum and others within INHERIT project).

The questionnaire will assess the level of awareness and understanding of the interventions, the perceived benefits, the concerns and challenges related to the interventions and the willingness to support the implementation. The questionnaire will be designed to facilitate straightforward responses and generate a "social acceptance index" for each measure.

In the Figure 41, the methodology with the main points to be considered in each of the three steps, as outlined above, is shown.

Figure 41: Methodology for the assessment of the financial sustainability, risk assessment and acceptance of CH measures

In future phases, the methodology will be refined based on feedback and detailed findings. Subsequent reports will expand on the preliminary insights provided here, incorporating more precise data and advanced analysis methods and the project progresses.

By adopting this methodology, it is ensured that the proposed measures are financially sustainable, socially acceptable and aligned with best practices in heritage management.

To ensure the financial sustainability of the measures, it is crucial to explore and utilise various financing schemes. The following section provides a review of relevant literature on innovative financing models specifically tailored for cultural heritage interventions. This review serves as a foundational input for the risk assessment phase of the methodology, offering valuable insights into potential funding sources and mechanisms. By aligning these financing schemes with the project's goals, we aim to mitigate financial risks and ensure that the interventions are both cost-effective and supported by robust financial strategies.

6.1. Financing schemes for CH

Governments today face significant challenges in conserving and managing cultural heritage sites, often leading to neglect and deterioration. INHERIT not only aims to improve the sustainability, energy efficiency and accessibility of CH sites but also to explore financial schemes that can support the long-term sustainability of more sites. Below, several financial tools and models are discussed, which contribute to the conservation and management of CH, with a focus on Public-Private-People Partnerships (PPPPs or 4Ps) and related case studies.

Public-Private Partnership (PPP) and Public-Private-People Partnership (PPPP)

Public-Private Partnership (PPP) is a collaborative concept that brings together two distinct objectives: the public sector’s focus on maximising community service and the private sector’s goal of increasing profitability and returns for its stakeholders. Initially introduced as a synergistic approach to address budgetary constraints and meet the growing demand for public services, PPPs aim to create a win-win situation for all involved (McQuaid, 2000 [39]; Kernaghan, 1993 [40]; Kouwenhoven, 1993 [41]; Majamaa, 2008 [42]). PPPs allow both entities to share responsibilities, risks and benefits in the funding, development and management of projects, with the goal of benefiting both society and the participants (Irazábal, 2016 [43]).

However, PPPs often struggle to fully align with public benefit goals, as private sector involvement can sometimes prioritise profit over social responsibility. To address these limitations, the concept of Public-Private-People Partnership (PPPP) was developed. PPPP integrates public funding, private investment and active community involvement, ensuring that the interests of all stakeholders are considered. This model thrives when all participants collaborate toward goals that go beyond their individual interests (Irazábal, 2016 [43]). The inclusion of the “people” element is crucial for achieving inclusiveness and ensuring that the outcomes are beneficial for all stakeholders (United Nations Economic Commission for Europe, 2008 [44]).

Figure 42 presents a simple scheme with the potential stakeholders that can participate in a PPPP for a cultural heritage project.

Figure 42: Potential stakeholders for PPPP project in CH

Tools of PPPP

Various PPPP tools are employed as funding and management models to preserve cultural heritage. These include methods like crowdfunding, online petitions and contributions from foundations (Boniotti, 2023 [45]). Digital technologies and social media also play a significant role in enhancing citizen involvement in these efforts (European Commission, 2015 [46]).

- **Civic Crowdfunding:** it enables citizens and public administrations to co-finance public services and works through online platforms. It differs from traditional crowdfunding by focusing on public benefits rather than private gains.
- **Real Estate Crowdfunding:** originally developed to address real estate market challenges, real estate crowdfunding has potential applications in CH. It is an internet-based funding scheme that was first launched in 2012 in the USA, and it was used to address the real estate market crisis (Morri and Ravetta, 2016 [47]). While it certainly has a profit-driven nature, its growing popularity as a real estate investment tool makes it relevant for cultural heritage projects.
- **Social & Sustainability Bonds:** bonds are financial instruments through which an issuer borrows money from investors, agreeing to make periodic interest payments and repay the principal amount in full. When bonds are issued to finance projects with one or more social objectives, they are known as social bonds. These bonds allow investors to support social projects, with the proceeds specifically earmarked for the designated social initiatives as outlined in the bond's terms and conditions, ensuring that the funds are not diverted to other purposes (Park, 2018 [48]). Similarly, sustainability bonds are designed to finance projects that deliver both environmental and socio-economic benefits (AlAhbabi and Nobanee, 2020 [49]).

Case Studies

- ***Distretti Culturali (Cultural Districts) Project:*** as public funding for cultural heritage has diminished, efforts have increasingly shifted toward securing alternative resources and refining strategies to preserve and promote CH. The *Distretti Culturali* project aims to enhance cultural heritage for local development by engaging stakeholders, catalysing resources and forging strong alliances between public and private entities. With a long-term vision, the project focuses on investments in human capital, the integration of culture and manufacturing, innovation in services and sustainability. This large-scale initiative exemplifies culture-focused community welfare by integrating diverse cultural and economic activities and promoting social participation in heritage protection (Barbetta et al., 2013 [50]; Della Torre, 2015 [51]; Moioli, 2018 [52]).
- ***The Valore Paese – Cammini e Percorsi (Country Value – Path and Trails) Project***³¹: the project, part of the broader *Diamo Valore Italia* (“Value for Italy”) programme, was launched in collaboration with the Italian Ministry of Cultural Heritage and other institutional partners. The project aims to repurpose and promote the enjoyment of public buildings along pedestrian, cycling and historical-religious heritage paths. This initiative targets economic operators capable of leveraging public-private agreements to develop tourism-oriented projects that benefit local communities. a public consultation involving around 25,000

³¹ <https://www.agenziademanio.it/opencms/it/notizia/Valore-Paese-CAMMINI-e-PERCORSI-parte-la-consultazione-pubblica-online>

people provided valuable input for the project. Buildings have been allocated through two types of contracts: concession/lease of valorisation and free concession/lease. The latter aligns with PPPP initiatives, offering free concessions for nine years to enterprises, cooperatives and associations primarily composed of individuals under 40. The first public tender in 2017 received 47 offers (14 from international participants), with 33 participants, including 16 enterprises, 8 cooperatives and 9 associations.

- **Other Projects:** notable initiatives include the acquisition of the Castle of Pergine (Province of Trento) by the CastelPergine Foundation³² through public underwriting. By November 2020, 867 contributors had donated 704,203 €, with support from over 50 associations and 10 companies. Additionally, a civic crowdfunding campaign for the restoration of the San Luca Colonnade in Bologna, initiated in 2017 by the Municipality of Bologna and a dedicated committee, successfully raised 300,000 €.

³² <https://www.fondazionecastelpergine.eu/en/home-english/>

7. Conclusions

The INHERIT project aims to develop a systematic methodology for sustainable, inclusive and resource-efficient cultural heritage solutions, with Work Package 3 focusing on creating a comprehensive framework for the assessment and monitoring of cultural heritage buildings. WP3 includes establishing a standardised methodology for the Technical Inspections using digital technologies, developing a robust assessment and monitoring framework and creating a detailed catalogue of solutions to enhance sustainability and resource efficiency. WP3's objectives are to provide a systematic and scalable approach to evaluating and improving the performance of heritage sites across various dimensions, including structural integrity, energy efficiency, resource management, resilience to hazards and inclusiveness.

Key findings highlight that the **Technical Inspection methodology** has successfully established a structured approach for assessing the status of heritage buildings. Emphasising structural integrity ensures safety and preservation, while the integration of H-BIM technology enhances the precision and effectiveness of inspections. This TI methodology aims to balance sustainable performance with the preservation of cultural values, adapting to the specific needs of historic structures and leveraging digital innovations for improved conservation practices.

Complementing this, the **assessment and monitoring framework** evaluates the CH buildings through four key pillars: energy and comfort; resource and circularity; climate resilience; and accessibility and sustainability. By using KPIs, this framework provides a structured approach to monitor and measure the impacts of conservation interventions, aligning with established standards such as Level(s) and the Smart Readiness Indicator. Additionally, the development of a **web-based application** for multi-dimensional assessment represents a significant advancement. This tool allows facility managers and inspectors to input and analyse data within the INHERIT framework, enhancing the management of heritage sites. Features like radar charts for visualising performance metrics enhance sustainability and accessibility.

Additionally, the **INHERIT Hub of Measures** offers a valuable resource for managing and modernizing of CH sites. This inventory includes categorised solutions and interventions aimed at improving energy efficiency, resource conservation and resilience, while preserving the historical integrity of buildings. The hub's structured approach and smart filtering capabilities provide a useful tool for selecting appropriate measures and guiding decision-making processes.

In summary, the integrated approach to technical inspection, assessment and monitoring, along with innovative tools and comprehensive resources, ensures that heritage buildings across Europe are preserved and utilised efficiently. This work lays a strong foundation for future conservation efforts, aligning with contemporary standards for sustainability and inclusiveness.

Looking ahead, the INHERIT project will further refine and expand upon the methodologies and tools developed thus far. Future work will focus on se initial findings in the upcoming deliverables. D3.2 will focus on enhancing the Technical Inspection processes, refining the assessment framework, and integrating these advancements with digital technologies like H-BIM and the web-based application that will be developed for the assessment framework. Also, the Hub of measures will be enriched using the measure datasheet. These next steps will ensure that the project remains adaptable and comprehensive, supporting the sustainable preservation and management of cultural heritage buildings across Europe.

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Annex 1. Landscape of European standardisation for Technical Inspection methodology

As concluded with the contribution of the partners in the tables with the main reference standards (Table 4, Table 5 and Table 6, in section 2.2), it is mandatory to analyse the European standards framework applicable in the field of Cultural Heritage conservation in order to enrich the baseline supporting the TI methodology.

A list of all CEN and ISO technical committees that have been selected for their potential usefulness in CH buildings is presented below. The collected information has been classified according to the IT headings.

A1.1 CEN and ISO general framework

A list of all CEN and ISO technical committees that have been selected for their potential usefulness in CH buildings is presented below. The collected information has been classified according to the TI headings.

1. Foundations and Structures

- CEN/TC 288 - Execution of special geotechnical works
- CEN/TC 135 - Execution of steel structures and aluminium structures
- CEN/TC 104 - Concrete and related products
- CEN/TC 167 - Structural bearings
- CEN/TC 124 - Timber structures

- ISO/TC 167 - Steel and aluminium structures
- ISO/TC 71 - Concrete, reinforced concrete and pre-stressed concrete

2. Facades and roofs

- CEN/TC 128 - Roof covering products for discontinuous laying and products for wall cladding
- CEN/TC 125 - Masonry
- CEN/TC 246 - Natural stones
- CEN/TC 241 - Gypsum and gypsum-based products
- CEN/TC 129 - Glass in building
- CEN/TC 139 - Paints and varnishes
- CEN/TC 88 - Thermal insulating materials and products

- ISO/TC 160 - Glass in building
- ISO/TC 189 - Ceramic tile
- ISO/TC 165 Timber structures
- ISO/TC 327 - Natural stones
- ISO/TC 328.- Engineered stones

3. Installations/facilities

- CEN/TC 156 - Ventilation for buildings
- CEN/TC 228 - Heating systems and water-based cooling systems in buildings
- CEN/TC 110 - Heat exchangers
- CEN/TC 130 - Space heating and/or cooling appliances without integral thermal sources
- CEN/TC 169 - Light and lighting

- ISO/TC 163 - Thermal performance and energy use in the built environment
- ISO/TC 86 - Refrigeration and air-conditioning

4. Biodegradation, water tightness and beauty/ornament

- CEN/TC 164 -Water supply
- CEN/TC 165 - Waste water engineering
- CEN/TC 349 - Sealants for joints in building construction

5. Accessibility

- CEN/CLC/JTC 11 -Accessibility in the built environment
- ISO/TC 59/SC 16 - Accessibility and usability of the built environment

6. Functional behaviour

- CEN/TC 247 - Building Automation, Controls and Building Management

Finally, after having analysed the panorama of existing EU standards that could be used in this field, it has been concluded that there is no specific regulation on the maintenance of CH, with the exception of the standards developed by CEN/TC 346, which are usually related to the conservation of movable heritage and do not provide answers on the conservation of immovable heritage. Thus, it is important to underline that the existing legislation on the use of historic materials, as applied to buildings, in terms of intervention, maintenance, characterisation and inspection is not sufficient to address the current scenario with a unified and sustainable methodology.

The specific characteristics of the construction systems of the post-Industrial Revolution heritage buildings are similar to contemporary buildings which are the focus of the contributions of the

CEN/TC working groups specified in this section. There are inspection methodologies and processes applied for the maintenance and conservation of this type of buildings that can be easily extrapolated to this typology of heritage buildings. Therefore, future research development will focus on analysing the regulations, guidelines and technical manuals that allow understanding the behaviour of historic materials, and identifying and quantifying the associated risks.

A1.2 The Spanish standards

The Spanish Association for Standardization (UNE) aims to contribute to the development of activity sectors through technical standards. The technical committee responsible for the Cultural Heritage sector is the **CTN 41/SC 8 – Conservation, Restoration and Rehabilitation of buildings**. Its activity is mainly divided around three topics: firstly, buildings diagnosis, secondly, buildings conservation and finally, buildings intervention. The published standards by this committee are listed below:

- UNE 41805-1:2009 IN. Diagnóstico de edificios. Parte 1: Generalidades.
- UNE 41805-2:2009 IN. Diagnóstico de edificios. Parte 2: Estudios históricos.
- UNE 41805-3:2009 IN. Diagnóstico de edificios. Parte 3: Estudios constructivos y patológicos
- UNE 41805-4:2009 IN. Diagnóstico de edificios. Parte 4: Estudio patológico de la estructura del edificio. Terreno y cimentación.
- UNE 41805-5:2009 IN. Diagnóstico de edificios. Parte 5: Estudio patológico de la estructura del edificio. Estructuras de fábrica
- UNE 41805-6:2009 IN. Diagnóstico de edificios. Parte 6: Estudio patológico de la estructura del edificio. Estructuras de hormigón.
- UNE 41805-7:2009 IN. Diagnóstico de edificios. Parte 7: Estudio patológico de la estructura del edificio. Estructuras metálicas.
- UNE 41805-8:2009 IN. Diagnóstico de edificios. Parte 8: Estudio patológico de la estructura del edificio. Estructuras de madera.
- UNE 41805-9:2009 IN. Diagnóstico de edificios. Parte 9: Estudio patológico del edificio. Cubiertas.
- UNE 41805-10:2009 IN. Diagnóstico de edificios. Parte 10: Estudio patológico del edificio. Fachadas no estructurales.
- UNE 41805-11:2009 IN. Diagnóstico de edificios. Parte 11: Estudio patológico del edificio. Carpintería de ventanas y cerrajería.
- UNE 41805-12:2009 IN. Diagnóstico de edificios. Parte 12: Estudio patológico del edificio. Particiones interiores y acabados.
- UNE 41805-13:2010 IN. Diagnóstico de edificios. Parte 13: Estudio patológico del edificio. Instalaciones.
- UNE 41805-14:2010 IN. Diagnóstico de edificios. Parte 14: Informe del diagnóstico.
- UNE 41806-1:2009 IN. Conservación de edificios. Limpieza de elementos constructivos. Parte 1: Clasificación de los métodos de limpieza.
- UNE 41806-2:2009 IN. Conservación de edificios. Limpieza de elementos constructivos. Parte 2: Técnicas de limpieza con agua.

- UNE 41806-3:2009 IN. Conservación de edificios. Limpieza de elementos constructivos. Parte 3: Técnicas de limpieza mecánica.
- UNE 41806-4:2009 IN. Conservación de edificios. Limpieza de elementos constructivos. Parte 4: Técnicas de limpieza con láser.
- UNE 41806-5-1:2009 IN. Conservación de edificios. Limpieza de elementos constructivos. Parte 5-1: Técnicas de limpieza química. Aplicación en forma de solución.
- UNE 41806-5-2:2009 IN. Conservación de edificios. Limpieza de elementos constructivos. Parte 5-2: Técnicas de limpieza química. Aplicación en forma de apósitos.
- UNE 41807:2021. Reparación de revocos de mortero.
- UNE 41808:2013. Estructuras de madera existentes. Sistema de representación gráfica del estado constructivo de las estructuras de madera existentes.
- UNE 41809:2014. Estructuras de madera existentes. Uso del penetrómetro para diagnóstico de los elementos de madera en edificios existentes.
- UNE 41810:2017. Conservación del patrimonio cultural. Criterios de intervención en materiales pétreos.
- UNE 41811:2017. Criterios de intervención en cerramientos de cubiertas.
- UNE 41812:2023. Conservación del patrimonio cultural. Directrices para la conservación y restauración de morteros en el patrimonio cultural.
- UNE 41410:2023. Bloques de Tierra Comprimida (BTC) para muros y tabiques. Definiciones, especificaciones y métodos de ensayo

Annex 2. Pillar 1 KPIs: Energy Performance and IEQ

A2.1 Total energy intensity

ID: 1.1-EP

DEFINITION

Total energy intensity is a KPI that evaluates the overall energy efficiency of the building as it quantifies its overall energy consumption against its floor area.

OBJECTIVE

Total energy intensity, expressed in units of energy per unit area (i.e. kWh/m²), provides a standardized measure that enables comparison both across different buildings and over time for the same building. Monitoring this KPI allows stakeholders to gauge the baseline energy usage of a CH building and track changes resulting from energy efficiency improvements or operational adjustments.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

The KPI is computed as follows:

$$EI_{tot} = \frac{E_{tot}}{m^2}$$

where:

- EI_{tot} is the total energy intensity of the building
- E_{tot} is the total energy consumed within the examined time period (e.g. over a year)
- m^2 is the total gross floor area of the building

To calculate the KPI, smart meters are required for measuring the energy consumed by the building, although this amount can also be computed through energy bills.

EXAMPLE

A residential building in Greece, which has a floor area of 80 m², consumed a total of 16,400 kWh in 2023. Using the KPI's formula, the total energy intensity of the building would be the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Total Energy Intensity} &= \frac{\text{Total Energy Consumption}}{\text{Total Floor Area}} \\ \text{Total Energy Intensity} &= \frac{16400 \text{ kWh}}{80 \text{ m}^2} = 205 \text{ kWh/m}^2 \end{aligned}$$

A2.2 Heating energy intensity

ID: 1.1.1-EP

DEFINITION

Heating energy intensity is a KPI that specifically evaluates the energy efficiency of the building for heating purposes, thus normalizing the respective energy consumption against the building's floor area and HDD.

OBJECTIVE

The metric offers insights into the efficiency of the building's heating systems and insulation, as well as the effectiveness of temperature control measures. Measured in kilowatt-hours per square meter and HDD, the KPI provides a focused assessment of the energy required to maintain comfortable indoor temperatures during colder periods. By tracking its change over time, stakeholders can identify opportunities for energy savings through upgrades to heating systems, enhancements in insulation, and adjustments in temperature setpoints.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

The KPI is computed as follows:

$$EI_h = \frac{E_h}{m^2 \times HDD}$$

where:

- EI_h is the heating energy intensity of the building
- E_h is the total energy consumed for heating purposes within the examined time period (e.g. over a year)
- m^2 is the total gross floor area of the building
- HDD are the heating degree days

Degree days is a metric used in climatology and building energy management to quantify the demand required for heating or cooling a building space based on outdoor temperatures. In practice, they provide a measure of how much the daily average temperature deviates from a reference (base) temperature below/above which heating/cooling the building is typically required. The basic idea is to sum up the differences between the daily average temperature and the selected base temperature over a certain period, typically a day or a year. This cumulative value is expressed in DD (degree days)³³. As such, HDD are calculated based on how much the daily average temperature falls below a certain base temperature and are particularly relevant for estimating the energy required to heat a building during colder periods. The value of the base temperature depends in principle on several factors associated with the building and the surrounding environment. By using a general climatological approach, the base temperature is set to a constant value of 18°C and HDD are calculated as follows:

If $T_m \leq 15^\circ\text{C}$, then $[HDD = \sum_i(18^\circ\text{C} - T_m)]$; else $[HDD = 0]$ where T_m is the mean air temperature of day i .

³³ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Archive:Heating_and_cooling_degree_days_statistics

To calculate the KPI, smart meters are required for measuring the energy consumed for heating purposes, unless separate energy bills are issued for the heating system of the building. Moreover, HDD can be estimated using sensor data or by extracting some indicative values from Eurostat's energy statistics³⁴.

EXAMPLE

A residential building in Greece, which has a floor area of 80 m², consumed 7,600 kWh for heating in 2023, which reported 1000 HDD. Using the KPI's formula, the heating energy intensity of the building would be the following:

$$\text{Heating Energy Intensity} = \frac{\text{Heating Energy Consumption}}{\text{Total Floor Area} \times \text{HDD}}$$

$$\text{Heating Energy Intensity} = \frac{7600 \text{ kWh}}{80 \text{ m}^2 \times 1000} = 0.095 \text{ kWh/m}^2$$

A2.3 Cooling energy intensity

ID: 1.1.2-EP

DEFINITION

Cooling energy intensity is a KPI that specifically evaluates the energy efficiency of the building for cooling purposes, thus normalizing the respective energy consumption against the building's floor area and CDD.

OBJECTIVE

The KPI measures the efficiency of the building's cooling systems, including air conditioning units and ventilation, in maintaining comfortable indoor temperatures during warmer periods. Expressed in kilowatt-hours per square meter and CDD, the KPI offers valuable insights into the energy efficiency of the building's infrastructure during hotter periods. By monitoring its change over time, stakeholders can identify opportunities for energy savings through improvements in insulation, upgrades to cooling equipment, and optimization of ventilation systems. Improving this KPI will not only enhance energy efficiency but may also contribute to cost savings and environmental sustainability, making it a critical KPI for managing the energy performance of CH buildings, particularly in regions with warm climates.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

The KPI is computed as follows:

$$EI_c = \frac{E_c}{m^2 \times CDD}$$

where:

- EI_c is the cooling energy intensity of the building
- E_c is the total energy consumed for cooling purposes within the examined time period (e.g. over a year)
- m^2 is the total gross floor area of the building
- CDD are the cooling degree days

³⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/metadata/en/nrg_chdd_esms.htm

CDD are calculated based on how much the daily average temperature rises above a certain base temperature and useful for estimating the energy needed for cooling a building during warmer periods. The value of the base temperature depends in principle on several factors associated with the building and the surrounding environment. By using a general climatological approach, the base temperature is set to a constant value of 21°C and CDD are calculated as follows:

$$\text{If } T_m \geq 24^\circ\text{C, then } [CDD = \sum_i T_m - 21^\circ\text{C}]; \text{ else } [CDD = 0].$$

To calculate the KPI, smart meters are required for measuring the energy consumed for cooling purposes. Moreover, CDD must be estimated.

EXAMPLE

A residential building in Greece, which has a floor area of 80 m², consumed 1,200 kWh for cooling in 2023, which reported 1500 CDD. Using the KPI's formula, the heating energy intensity of the building would be the following:

$$\text{Cooling Energy Intensity} = \frac{\text{Cooling Energy Consumption}}{\text{Total Floor Area} \times \text{CDD}}$$

$$\text{Cooling Energy Intensity} = \frac{1200 \text{ KWh}}{80 \text{ m}^2 \times 1500} = 0.01 \text{ KWh/m}^2$$

A2.4 Lighting energy intensity

ID: 1.1.3-EP

DEFINITION

The lighting energy intensity of a building is a significant KPI that evaluates the energy consumed for lighting purposes, normalized against the floor area of the building.

OBJECTIVE

The metric measures the efficiency of the building's artificial lighting systems, but indirectly also accounts for the efficient use of natural sources in providing adequate illumination for occupants. Quantified in kilowatt-hours per square meter (kWh/m²), the KPI offers insights into the energy efficiency of the building's lighting infrastructure. By tracking changes in this KPI over time, stakeholders can identify opportunities for energy savings through the use of energy-efficient lighting technologies, daylight harvesting strategies, occupancy sensors, and lighting controls.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

The KPI is computed as follows:

$$EI_l = \frac{E_l}{m^2}$$

where:

- EI_l is the lighting energy intensity of the building
- E_l is the total energy consumed for lighting purposes within the examined time period (e.g. over a year)
- m^2 is the total gross floor area of the building

To calculate the KPI, smart meters are required for measuring the energy consumed for lighting purposes.

EXAMPLE

A residential building in Greece, which has a floor area of 80 m², consumed 400 kWh in 2023 for lighting purposes. Using the KPI's formula, the lighting energy intensity of the building would be the following:

$$\text{Lighting Energy Intensity} = \frac{\text{Lighting Energy Consumption}}{\text{Total Floor Area}}$$

$$\text{Lighting Energy Intensity} = \frac{400 \text{ KWh}}{80 \text{ m}^2} = 5 \text{ KWh/m}^2$$

A2.5 Appliances energy intensity

ID: 1.1.4-EP

DEFINITION

This KPI encompasses various energy-consuming activities beyond heating, cooling, and lighting as it accounts for energy consumption related to appliances, equipment, plug loads, and other miscellaneous sources within the building, again normalized based on the floor area of the building.

OBJECTIVE

The measure quantifies the efficiency of the aforementioned energy-consuming activities and provides insights into opportunities for optimization. Measured in kilowatt-hours per square meter (kWh/m²), the KPI offers a comprehensive assessment of overall energy usage within the building. By monitoring changes in its value over time, stakeholders can identify areas for energy savings through the adoption of energy-efficient appliances, behavioural changes and technology upgrades.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

The KPI is computed as follows:

$$EI_{other} = \frac{E_{other}}{m^2}$$

where:

- EI_{other} is the energy intensity of other energy sources of the building, including appliances that do not fall in the heating, cooling or lighting category.
- E_{other} is the total energy consumed for other purposes than lighting, cooling, and heating within the examined period (e.g. over a year)
- m^2 is the total gross floor area of the building

To calculate the KPI, smart meters are required for measuring the energy consumed in energy uses excluding heating, cooling, and lighting.

EXAMPLE

A residential building in Greece, which has a floor area of 80 m², consumed 3200 kWh in 2023 for powering its various electrical appliances. Using the KPI's formula, the lighting energy intensity of the building would be the following:

$$\text{Appliances Energy Intensity} = \frac{\text{Appliances Energy Consumption}}{\text{Total Floor Area}}$$

$$\text{Appliances Energy Intensity} = \frac{3200 \text{ KWh}}{80 \text{ m}^2} = 40 \text{ KWh/m}^2$$

A2.6 Energy autonomy

ID: 1.2-EP

DEFINITION

This measure is effectively the proportion of energy consumed by a building over the energy produced from RES, thus assessing its overall autonomy and sustainability.

OBJECTIVE

This metric quantifies the share of energy derived from RES, such as solar, wind, hydro, or geothermal, relative to the total energy consumed by the building. Expressed as a percentage, it provides a measure of the building's reliance on clean energy. Monitoring changes in the proportion of energy consumed from RES over time allows stakeholders to evaluate the effectiveness of renewable energy integration efforts, such as solar panel installations or wind turbine implementations. Increasing this proportion signifies progress towards reducing reliance on fossil fuels, lowering carbon emissions, and enhancing the building's resilience to energy price fluctuations.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

The KPI is computed as follows:

$$P_E = \frac{E_{res}}{E_{tot}} \times 100 \%$$

where:

- P_E is the percentage of the produced energy in comparison of the consumed energy
- E_{tot} is the total energy consumed within the examined period (e.g. over a year)
- E_{res} is the total energy produced by RES within the examined time period

To calculate the KPI, smart meters are required for measuring the energy produced from the various RES sources and the energy consumed by the building, although the latter can also be computed through energy bills.

EXAMPLE

In 2023, a residential building in Greece consumed a total of 16200 kWh and produced from RES 2000KWh. Using the KPI's formula, the percentage of the produced energy in comparison of the consumed energy of the building would be the following:

$$\text{Energy autonomy} = \frac{\text{Total Energy Consumption}}{\text{Total Energy Produced from RES}} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{Energy autonomy} = \frac{2000 \text{ KWh}}{16200 \text{ KWh}} \times 100\% = 12.35\%$$

Given that the optimal KPI value is 100%, the calculations indicate that the energy autonomy of the building is quite low.

A2.7 Energy performance & operation

ID: 1.3-EP

DEFINITION

“Energy Performance and Operation”, as an SRI-based KPI, assesses the energy consumption and operational performance of a building, focusing on reducing excessive energy use and minimizing emissions through the application of smart services and technologies.

OBJECTIVE

The goal of measuring this KPI is to improve the overall energy performance of a building by identifying and reducing excessive energy consumption, thereby reducing associated emissions. This KPI aims to leverage smart services and technologies to dynamically adapt to prevailing conditions, ensuring optimal energy use. In addition, it seeks to improve the maintenance and operational performance of technical building systems, minimizing energy losses and preventing unexpected breakdowns.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

The KPI will be computed using the SRI-ENACT tool (<https://www.srienact-tool.eu/login>) and specifically by reporting the “**1-Building**” aggregate score, which is effectively the average of the “energy efficiency” and “fault protection” impact criteria from each technical domain.

A2.8 Response to the needs of occupants

ID: 1.4-EP

DEFINITION

“Response to the needs of occupants”, as an SRI-based KPI, evaluates a building's capacity to utilize user-friendly smart technologies to autonomously predict, adapt to, and fulfil occupants' requirements for comfort and convenience, ensuring enhanced occupant satisfaction.

OBJECTIVE

The goal of the KPI is to assess the building's overall ability to use user-friendly smart technologies to accurately predict, seamlessly adapt, and satisfactorily meet the varying comfort and convenience needs of its occupants autonomously. This assessment aims to ensure that building functional functions are coordinated to improve overall occupant satisfaction and well-being, thereby fostering an environment that prioritizes user comfort and convenience.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

The KPI will be computed using the SRI-ENACT tool (<https://www.srienact-tool.eu/login>) and specifically by reporting the “**2-User**” aggregate score, which is effectively the average of the “comfort”, “Convenience” “Health, well-being & accessibility”, and “Information to occupants” impact criteria from each technical domain.

A2.9 Energy flexibility assessment

ID: 1.5-EP

DEFINITION

“Energy flexibility assessment”, as an SRI-based KPI, measures a building's capacity to adapt energy consumption and production to changing conditions, thus enhancing resilience and efficiency.

OBJECTIVE

The goal of the KPI is to measure a building's ability to dynamically modify its energy consumption and production in response to fluctuating conditions, such as changes in energy demand or availability. By assessing this capability, the KPI aims to improve overall building resilience, optimize energy efficiency and ensure reliable energy supply, particularly during periods of peak demand or when renewable energy sources are variable.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

The KPI will be computed using the SRI-ENACT tool (<https://www.srienact-tool.eu/login>) and specifically by reporting the “**3-Grid**” aggregate score, which is effectively the average of the “Energy flexibility & storage” impact criteria from each technical domain.

A2.10 Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature

ID: 1.1-IEQ

DEFINITION

The KPI evaluates the indoor air temperature to ensure it is typically maintained at levels conducive to general population's comfort and satisfaction.

OBJECTIVE

The KPI aims to ensure that indoor environments maintain optimal temperature levels for occupant comfort and productivity. By assessing and controlling air temperature, the KPI aims to prevent discomfort caused by excessive heat or cold, thereby improving the overall well-being and performance of building occupants. This assessment helps identify and implement effective HVAC solutions, promote energy efficiency, and ensure compliance with thermal comfort standards.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

The KPI is evaluated as follows:

$$F_{iat} = \frac{t_{iat}}{t_{oc}} \times 100\%$$

where:

- F_{iat} is the frequency of acceptable indoor air temperature
- t_{iat} are the occupancy hours with acceptable indoor air temperature (19-25°C for winter and 22-27°C for summer)
- t_{oc} is the total occupancy hours

Calculations computed over only the building's occupancy hours are typically more indicative, providing more representative insights. These hours can be specified either in a static (e.g. once per

year based on typical occupancy hours and holidays) or a dynamic (e.g. by exploiting sensor data summarizing energy consumption and mobility) way.

The limits of the KPI are defined based on those provided by the EN 16798 - 1:2019 standard for Category III. To calculate the KPI, temperature sensor measurements are required at hourly level at key spaces of the building. In case of multiple spaces and/or measurements per space, the average temperature of each hour is considered. The calculations should only include the hours the building operates.

EXAMPLE

In 2023, an office building in Greece operated for 8 hours a day, 5 days a week (52 weeks a year). By analysing the sensor data during these occupancy hours, 800 hours in the winter period and 600 hours in the summer period were found to be within the acceptable indoor air temperature range of values.

To compute the KPI, we first calculate the total occupancy hours, as follows:

Total Occupancy Hours = Hours per day × Days per week × Weeks per year

Total Occupancy Hours = $8 \times 5 \times 52 = 2,080$ hours/year

Then, we calculate the total number of hours with acceptable indoor air temperature values:

Total Hours with Acceptable Air Temperature = $t_{iat_winter} + t_{iat_summer}$

Total Hours with Acceptable Air Temperature = 800 hours + 600 hours = 1400 hours

Finally, using the KPI's formula, the thermal comfort of the building's occupants in terms of air temperature would be:

$$\begin{aligned} & \textit{Frequency of Acceptable Air Temperature} \\ &= \frac{\textit{Total Hours with Acceptable Air Temperature}}{\textit{Total Occupancy Hours}} \\ & \textit{Frequency of Acceptable Air Temperature} = \frac{1400 \textit{ h}}{2080 \textit{ h}} \times 100\% = 67\% \end{aligned}$$

Given that the optimal KPI value is 100%, the calculations indicate that the thermal comfort of the users is relatively poor.

A2.11 Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity

ID: 1.2-IEQ

DEFINITION

This KPI evaluates the indoor humidity of the building to ensure it is typically maintained at levels conducive to general population's comfort and satisfaction.

OBJECTIVE

The objective of the KPI is to ensure that humidity levels are maintained in the optimal range to support occupant health, comfort, and productivity. By monitoring and regulating indoor humidity, this KPI aims to prevent problems such as dryness, excess humidity and mould growth, which can negatively affect air quality and comfort. Proper humidity control contributes to a healthier indoor environment, improves HVAC system performance, and aligns with established indoor air quality standards.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

The KPI is evaluated as follows:

$$F_{ih} = \frac{t_{ih}}{t_{oc}} \cdot 100\%$$

where:

- F_{ih} is the frequency of acceptable humidity range
- t_{ih} are the occupancy hours with acceptable humidity range (20-70%)
- t_{oc} are the total occupancy hours

The limits are defined based on those provided by the EN 16798 - 1:2019 standard for Category III. To calculate the KPI, humidity sensor measurements are required at hourly level at key spaces of the building. In case of multiple spaces and/or measurements per space, the average humidity of each hour is considered. The calculations should only include the hours the building operates.

EXAMPLE

In 2023, an office building in Greece operated for 8 hours a day, 5 days a week (52 weeks a year). By analysing the sensor data during these occupancy hours, 1700 hours were found to be within the acceptable indoor air humidity range of values.

To compute the KPI, we first calculate the total occupancy hours, as follows:

Total Occupancy Hours = Hours per day × Days per week × Weeks per year

Total Occupancy Hours = 8 × 5 × 52 = 2,080 hours/year

Finally, using the KPI's formula, the thermal comfort of the building's occupants in terms of air temperature would be:

$$\text{Frequency of Acceptable Humidity} = \frac{\text{Total Hours with Acceptable Humidity}}{\text{Total Occupancy Hours}}$$

$$\text{Frequency of Acceptable Humidity} = \frac{1700 \text{ h}}{2080 \text{ h}} \times 100\% = 82\%$$

Given that the optimal KPI value is 100%, the calculations indicate that the thermal comfort of the users in terms of humidity is good.

A2.12 Air quality

ID: 1.3-IEQ

DEFINITION

This KPI, focused on CO₂ concentration, assesses the overall cleanliness of indoor air to ensure that occupants are typically within a healthy and safe environment.

OBJECTIVE

The objective of this KPI is to ensure that indoor environments are free of harmful pollutants, thereby protecting the health of occupants and improving overall well-being. This assessment aims to identify and mitigate sources of indoor air pollution, improve ventilation systems, and maintain compliance with air quality standards, ultimately fostering a safe and comfortable indoor atmosphere.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

The KPI is evaluated as follows:

$$F_{aq} = \frac{t_{aq}}{t_{oc}} \times 100\%$$

where:

- F_{aq} is the frequency of acceptable CO₂ levels
- t_{aq} are the occupancy hours with acceptable CO₂ levels (<1350 ppm)
- t_{oc} are the total occupancy hours

The limits are defined based on those provided by the EN 16798 - 1:2019 standard for Category III. To calculate the KPI, CO₂ sensor measurements are required at hourly level at key spaces of the building. In case of multiple spaces and/or measurements per space, the average CO₂ of each hour is considered. The calculations should only include the hours the building operates.

EXAMPLE

In 2023, an office building in Greece operated for 8 hours a day, 5 days a week (52 weeks a year). By analysing the sensor data during these occupancy hours, 1650 hours were found to be within the acceptable indoor air quality range of values.

To compute the KPI, we first calculate the total occupancy hours, as follows:

Total Occupancy Hours = Hours per day × Days per week × Weeks per year

Total Occupancy Hours = 8 × 5 × 52 = 2,080 hours/year

Finally, using the KPI's formula, the thermal comfort of the building's occupants in terms of air temperature would be:

$$\text{Frequency of Acceptable Air Quality} = \frac{\text{Total Hours with Acceptable Air Quality}}{\text{Total Occupancy Hours}}$$

$$\text{Frequency of Acceptable Air Quality} = \frac{1750 \text{ h}}{2080 \text{ h}} \times 100\% = 84\%$$

Given that the optimal KPI value is 100%, the calculations indicate that the air quality of the building is good.

A2.13 Visual comfort

ID: 1.4-IEQ

DEFINITION

This KPI evaluates the quality of lighting inside a building to ensure it is typically conducive to its intended use.

OBJECTIVE

The objective of the KPI is to enhance occupant well-being, productivity, and overall satisfaction by providing an environment that minimizes eye strain and discomfort. This includes identifying lighting solutions that meet both the aesthetic and functional requirements of building users.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

The KPI is evaluated as follows:

$$F_{vc} = \frac{t_{vc}}{t_{oc}} \cdot 100\%$$

where:

- F_{vc} is the frequency of acceptable visual comfort
- t_{vc} are the occupancy hours with acceptable illuminance levels (>500 lux)
- t_{oc} are the total occupancy hours

The values are defined based on those provided by the EN 12464-1 standard. To calculate the KPI, illuminance sensor measurements are required at hourly level at key spaces of the building. The calculations should only include the hours the building operates.

EXAMPLE

In 2023, an office building in Greece operated for 8 hours a day, 5 days a week (52 weeks a year). By analysing the sensor data during these occupancy hours, 1500 hours were found to be within the acceptable indoor illuminance range of values.

To compute the KPI, we first calculate the total occupancy hours, as follows:

Total Occupancy Hours = Hours per day × Days per week × Weeks per year

Total Occupancy Hours = 8 × 5 × 52 = 2,080 hours/year

Finally, using the KPI's formula, the thermal comfort of the building's occupants in terms of air temperature would be:

$$\begin{aligned} & \textit{Frequency of Acceptable Visual Comfort} \\ &= \frac{\textit{Total Hours with Acceptable Visual Comfort}}{\textit{Total Occupancy Hours}} \\ & \textit{Frequency of Acceptable Visual Comfort} = \frac{1500 \textit{ h}}{2080 \textit{ h}} \times 100\% = 72\% \end{aligned}$$

Given that the optimal KPI value is 100%, the calculations indicate that the Visual Comfort of the users is relatively good.

A2.14 Acoustic comfort

ID: 1.5-IEQ

DEFINITION

This KPI evaluates the quality of the building's acoustic environment to ensure occupant well-being and productivity in most hours of the day.

OBJECTIVE

High acoustic comfort ensures that spaces are free from excessive noise and disturbing sounds, providing a peaceful and functional environment fit for the purpose of the building. Assessing acoustic comfort involves measuring decibel levels and ensuring that design and materials contribute to an acoustically optimized space.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

The KPI is evaluated as follows:

$$F_{ac} = \frac{t_{ac}}{t_{oc}} \cdot 100\%$$

where:

- F_{ac} is the frequency of acceptable acoustic comfort
- t_{ac} are the occupancy hours with acceptable noise levels (<45 db)
- t_{oc} are the total occupancy hours

The limits are defined based on those provided by the EN 16798 - 1:2019 standard for Category III of the office buildings. To calculate the KPI, decibel sensor measurements are required at hourly level at key spaces of the building. The calculations should only include the hours the building operates.

EXAMPLE

In 2023, an office building in Greece operated for 8 hours a day, 5 days a week (52 weeks a year). By analysing the sensor data during these occupancy hours, 1800 hours were found to be within the acceptable acoustic comfort range of values.

To compute the KPI, we first calculate the total occupancy hours, as follows:

Total Occupancy Hours = Hours per day × Days per week × Weeks per year

Total Occupancy Hours = 8 × 5 × 52 = 2,080 hours/year

Finally, using the KPI's formula, the thermal comfort of the building's occupants in terms of air temperature would be:

$$\begin{aligned} & \textit{Frequency of Acceptable Acoustic Comfort} \\ &= \frac{\textit{Total Hours with Acceptable Acoustic Comfort}}{\textit{Total Occupancy Hours}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\textit{Frequency of Acceptable Acoustic Comfort} = \frac{1800 \text{ h}}{2080 \text{ h}} \times 100\% = 87\%$$

Given that the optimal KPI value is 100%, the calculations indicate that the Acoustic Comfort of the users is relatively good.

Annex 3. Pillar 2 KPIs: Resource efficiency, Circularity and LCC

A3.1 Total Water Consumption

ID: 2.1-TWC

DEFINITION

It measures the water consumption of sanitary fittings/devices and water consuming appliances, based on consumption rates and usage factors assumed.

The estimation or measurement of the substitution of potable water with alternative, non-potable source is also possible.

Specific information about the water consumption rates of sanitary fittings and water using appliances should be used, and flush volumes can be used instead. Actual water consumption can be accurately monitored via periodical meter readings. The most likely source of variations between estimated and actual per capita water consumption is an inaccurate estimate of occupancy rates, especially in buildings with significant number of visitors. This is why for non-residential buildings it is recommended to calculate it per square meter.

This reporting can also be disaggregated into potable and non-potable water use, for instance when rainwater or greywater collection systems are installed. This is highly recommended for areas of water stress.

OBJECTIVE

This indicator can be applied to both new or existing buildings to understand, and ultimately decrease, the water demand and consumption.

It is also relevant to calculate the following Global Warming Potential of the water consumption in the following indicator 2.3-GWP.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

The necessary input data are set out in the following Table 37.

Table 37: KPI 2.1-TWC input data

Input	Unit/Format	Source
Water consumption	m ³ /month	Monitored via periodic meter readings. Ideally to collect data from 12 consecutive months, and if possible averaged over three years.
Water consumption	m ³ /occupant/day (<i>residential buildings</i>) or m ³ /m ² /day (<i>non-residential buildings</i>)	Calculation by disaggregating the components specific (default) water consumption rates for different sanitary devices and fittings, which is provided by the manufacturers or suppliers and labelling schemes (e.g. the European Water Label ³⁵): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sanitary fittings and devices (e.g. toilets, urinals, taps, baths and showers)

³⁵ <http://www.europeanwaterlabel.eu/findaproduct.asp>

Input	Unit/Format	Source
		- Water using appliances (e.g. dishwashers and washing machines)
Occupancy rate	Day/year	Number of days that the building is expected to be occupied by year.

In the usage stage of the building lifecycle, actual water consumption shall be based on data collected. Reporting on **meter readings of actual consumption** should be based on data from at least 12 consecutive months and ideally averaged over at least three years.

Then, it is divided per occupant in the case of residential buildings, or per the area of the building (m^2) in the case of non-residential buildings.

$$TWC \text{ (residential)} \left[\frac{m^3}{\text{occupant} \cdot \text{year}} \right] = \frac{\sum_{\text{month}=1}^{12} \text{Water consumption} \left[\frac{m^3}{\text{year}} \right]}{\text{no. occupants}}$$

$$TWC \text{ (non – residential)} \left[\frac{m^3}{m^2 \cdot \text{year}} \right] = \frac{\sum_{\text{month}=1}^{12} \text{Water consumption} \left[\frac{m^3}{\text{year}} \right]}{A_b [m^2]}$$

where:

- **A_b** is the area of the building [m^2]

For the calculation of the indicator at the **design stage** (including for design and planning of CH building renovation), the following formulas can be applied to residential buildings and non-residential buildings.

$$TWC \text{ (residential)} \left[\frac{m^3}{\text{occupant} \cdot \text{year}} \right] = \sum_{\text{device}=0}^{\infty} \text{Water consumption} \left[\frac{m^3}{\text{occupant} \cdot \text{day}} \right] \times \text{occupancy rate} \left[\frac{\text{day}}{\text{year}} \right]$$

$$TWC \text{ (non – residential)} \left[\frac{m^3}{m^2 \cdot \text{year}} \right] = \sum_{\text{device}=0}^{\infty} \text{Water consumption} \left[\frac{m^3}{m^2 \cdot \text{day}} \right] \times \text{occupancy rate} \left[\frac{\text{day}}{\text{year}} \right]$$

Where the Water consumption of each component can be obtained per product or device from the European Water Label³⁶, but in the following Table 38, estimates of the water consumption rates for various sanitary devices per occupant per day is provided.

Table 38: Water consumption rates estimates of the sanitary devices and water using appliances

Device	Water consumption	Assumption	Daily water consumption rate [$m^3/\text{occupant}/\text{day}$]	Yearly water consumption rate [$m^3/\text{occupant}/\text{year}$]
Toilets	6.057 L/flush	5 flushes /occupant/day	0.03	10.95
Urinals (modern low-flow)	1.893 L/flush	3 uses /male occupant/day	0.0057	2.08
Taps	8.328 L/minute	8 minutes /occupant/day	0.07	25.55
Showers (modern showerheads)	9.464 L/minute	8 minutes /occupant/day	0.076	27.74

³⁶ <http://www.europeanwaterlabel.eu/findaproduct.asp>

Device	Water consumption	Assumption	Daily water consumption rate [m ³ /occupant/day]	Yearly water consumption rate [m ³ /occupant/year]
Baths (standard bathtub)	151.416 L/week	1 bath /occupant/week 0.143 bath /occupant/day	0.022	7.85
Bidets (standard)	7.571 L/minute	2 minutes /occupant/day	0.015	5.48
Dishwashers (modern standard)	30.283 L/cycle	1 cycle /household (4occupants)/day 0.25 cycle /occupant/day	0.008	2.92
Washing machines (front-loading high-efficiency models)	75.708 L/load	5 loads /household (4occupants)/week 0.179 loads/occupant/day	0.095	4.94

For reference, the average water consumption in Europe in 2021 was 124 l/inhabitant/day; which means **45.26 m³/inhabitant/year**. In the tertiary sector, according to a French study, the following water consumption is around 40 l/employee/day or 4 l/m² of office³⁷. Translated to a year, this would be **14.6 m³/employee/year** and **1.46 m³/m² of office/year**.

REFERENCES

Level(s) EU framework part 1 & 2 (JRC, 2017 [30]) and part 3 (JRC, 2018 [53]). Macro-objective 3 “Efficient use of water resources”, indicator 3.1 “Total water consumption”.

CLIC project, Deliverable 2.4³⁸ “Database of indicators and data in pilot cities”, indicator 6.1.1 “Fresh water consumption”, within water consumption (freshwater & recovered water) category, under freshwater efficiency criteria.

For the estimates of the water consumption rates of the sanitary devices and water using appliances:

- Unified Water Label Association (UWLA)^{39 40}
- Freitas et al., 2021 [54]
- Garzón-Orduña et al., 2024 [55]

EXAMPLES

An office building (non-residential building) of 380 m² and with 35 workers in usage stage has the following water consumption in the last 12 months (Table 39) according to the reading of the water consumption meters.

Table 39: Water consumption of the office building during the last 12 months (from metering reading)

Month	Water consumption [m ³]
January	13.395
February	15.308

³⁷ <https://iotfactory.eu/kpi-water-consumption-performance-indicators/>

³⁸ https://www.clicproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/D2.4_Database-of-indicators-and-data-in-pilot-cities.pdf

³⁹ <https://uwla.eu/>

⁴⁰ <http://www.europeanwaterlabel.eu/findaproduct.asp>

Month	Water consumption [m ³]
March	16.073
April	13.395
May	17.222
June	15.308
July	9.568
August	7.654
September	16.073
October	19.135
November	16.073
December	7.654
TOTAL	166.857 m³/year

So, the TWC can be calculated according to the number of occupants (workers) or according to the squared meters of the building:

$$TWC = \frac{166.857 \frac{m^3}{year}}{35 \text{ occupants}} = 4.77 \frac{m^3}{occupant \cdot year}$$

$$TWC = \frac{166.857 \frac{m^3}{year}}{380 m^2} = 0.44 \frac{m^3}{m^2 \cdot year}$$

As a second example for the calculation of the TWC in the design stage, in this case of a residential building. The residential building has three floors, with three dwellings each. In each floor there is a dwelling with 2 bedrooms (estimated 3 occupants), a dwelling with 3 bedrooms (estimated 4 occupants) and a dwelling with 4 bedrooms (estimated 5 occupants). Thus, the total number of occupants would be: (3 + 4 + 5) occupants x 3 floors = 36 occupants.

The following Table 40 contains the devices included in the dwellings together with the calculation with the number of occupants in the residential building.

Table 40: Sanitary devices and water using appliances water consumption data of a residential building in design stage

Device	Water consumption rate [m ³ /occupant/day]	2-rooms bedrooms [m ³ /day]	3-rooms bedrooms [m ³ /day]	4-rooms bedrooms [m ³ /day]	Water consumption in the building [m ³ /day] (with 36 occupants)
Toilets	0.03	3dwellings x 3occupants = 0.27	3dwellings x 4occupants = 0.36	3dwellings x 5occupants = 0.45	1.08
Taps	0.07	3dwellings x 3occupants = 0.63	3dwellings x 4occupants = 0.84	3dwellings x 5occupants = 1.05	2.52
Shower	0.076	3dwellings x 3occupants = 0.68	3dwellings x 4occupants = 0.91	3dwellings x 5occupants = 1.14	2.73

Device	Water consumption rate [m ³ /occupant/day]	2-rooms bedrooms [m ³ /day]	3-rooms bedrooms [m ³ /day]	4-rooms bedrooms [m ³ /day]	Water consumption in the building [m ³ /day] (with 36 occupants)
Baths	0.022	-	3dwellings x 4occupants = 0.26	3dwellings x 5occupants = 0.33	0.59
Dishwashers	0.008	3dwellings x 3occupants = 0.072	3dwellings x 4occupants = 0.096	3dwellings x 5occupants = 0.12	0.288
Washing machines	0.095	3dwellings x 3occupants = 0.86	3dwellings x 4occupants = 1.14	3dwellings x 5occupants = 1.43	3.43
TOTAL (in the building per day)					10.64 m ³ /day
TOTAL (per occupant and per day)					0.2955 m³/occupant/day

So, the Total Water Consumption per occupant and per year for this residential building would be:

$$TWC = 0.2955 \frac{m^3}{occupant \cdot day} \times 330 \frac{days\ occupied}{year} = 97.52 \frac{m^3}{occupant \cdot year}$$

Which is a total for the building of:

$$TWC = 10.64 \frac{m^3}{day} \times 330 \frac{days\ occupied}{year} = 3511.20 \frac{m^3}{year}$$

A3.2 Global Warming Potential

ID: 2.2-GWP

DEFINITION

This indicator measures the contribution of the greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions associated with a building's life cycle to the earth's global warming or climate change. That is, the carbon footprint assessment or whole life carbon measurement.

Whether possible, the indicator should include the assessment of the embodied CO₂ emissions, i.e. those that are not directly related to the use of energy in a building, but are instead the indirect result of processes to produce, construct, repair, maintain, renovate and eventually deconstruct a building.

GHGs are constituents of the atmosphere which absorb and emit radiation at specific wavelengths within the spectrum of the thermal infrared radiation emitted by the earth's surface, by the atmosphere itself, and by clouds. By doing so, GHGs obstruct the loss of thermal energy towards the space and act like a blanket which insulates the Earth and keep it warmer.

Effects on the Earth are different for different GHGs. The Global Warming Potential (GWP) was developed to allow for the comparison of the impact on global warming caused by different gases. Specifically, it is a relative measure of how much energy can be trapped in the atmosphere over a set time horizon by a mass of gas in comparison with the same mass of carbon dioxide (CO₂). A higher GWP means a larger warming effect in that period of time.

The key relevant emissions to consider are due to the energy consumption, water consumption and the use of construction materials in the building. For the energy consumption, data from Pillar 1 can

be used, although it should be disaggregated per energy type, to multiply it by the appropriate conversion factor to estimate the CO₂ equivalent emissions. For the water consumption, the results of the calculation of the indicator 2.1-TWC can be directly used as input, multiplying it by the tap water conversion factor. For construction materials, GHG are accounted all along their lifecycle and then multiplied by the relevant conversion factors. For such calculation, a Bill of Materials (BoM) should be used (described at the end of this section).

OBJECTIVE

The Global Warming Potential shall be reported separately for each life cycle stage. This is so that the trade-offs between decisions taken at different stages can be understood and considered.

For CH buildings, it is relevant to understand the building GHG emissions and, ultimately, plan energy renovations to decrease them. This would mean that the usage stage (current stage of the building) would be key to study. Additionally, the design stage would be key for the planning of renovation works.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

The GWP is calculated over a specific time horizon, commonly 20, 100 or 500 years. **GWP₁₀₀** is considered in this context. GWP is expressed as equivalent mass of carbon dioxide (whose GWP is normalised to 1).

The list of GHGs and their relative GWPs in 100 years is included in the Sixth Assessment Report of the IPCC⁴¹. The main specific GHGs that are of interest are also reported in the following Table 41.

Table 41: Relative GWP values for main specific GHGs of interest (IPCC_AR6⁴²)

Greenhouse gas	Chemical formula	Global warming potential (GWP ₁₀₀)
Carbon dioxide	CO ₂	1
Methane	CH ₄	27.9
Nitrous Oxide	N ₂ O	273

The overall GWP of a list of GHGs is given by the sum of the products between emission *i* and the respective GWP₁₀₀. As minimum, for the CH buildings at usage stage, **energy** modelling should be included. Data for the energy modelling come from the indicators in Pillar 1 (Annex 2). It is also recommended to include the **water** modelling, whose data will come from indicator 2.1-TWC. For an advanced assessment of the GWP, and also relevant for the design stage (in CH buildings might be focused on the design of energy renovations), the materials modelling can be also done, taking the data from the Bill of Materials. The quantification of the materials needed during the building life cycle shall be based on the corresponding rules set for the development of the Bill of Materials.

At **usage stage**, the main GHG emissions from the use are:

- **Direct emissions**, those from on-site power generation, refrigeration and air-conditioning equipment.
- **Indirect emissions**, those from production and distribution of electricity and steam/heat used in the building, and from supply of materials and construction products of which the

⁴¹ <https://www.ipcc.ch/assessment-report/ar6/>

⁴² <https://www.ipcc.ch/assessment-report/ar6/>

building is made up. For construction products, the term “embodied” emissions is often used.

There are several software tools and data that generally contain reference data for GWP₁₀₀ characterisation factors for the greenhouse gases, based on the Assessment Reports of the IPCC. Some of them are:

- **Carbon Footprint Ltd**⁴³ allows free searching and downloads for individual GHGs emission factors to use for simplified Life Cycle Analysis (LCA). The free version of their calculator tool holds life cycle emission factors for over 4,500 common products, materials and processes, including *Ecoinvent*⁴⁴ factors as well as extensive records from Carbon Footprint Ltd's Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) databases, drawn from internationally recognised and traceable sources. It allows modelling of a single building.
- **CarbonScopeData**^{TM45} is a life cycle inventory (LCI) database. It provides data for a broad array of raw materials used in the economy, common industrial processes, energy sources, transport modes and waste disposal. The database contains LCI data for well over 1600 materials, products and processes representing a broad range of industries and geographical locations (with more being added regularly), compiled from highly credible raw data sources and research literature and processed according to rigorous LCA standards.

GWP from Energy

Without using software tools, the GWP from energy in usage stage of a building can also be calculated using the following formula:

$$GWP_{Energy} \left[\frac{kgCO_2eq}{m^2 \cdot year} \right] = \frac{\sum \left(E_{F,i} \left[\frac{kWh}{m^2 \cdot year} \right] \cdot fe_{F,i} \left[\frac{kgCO_2eq}{kWh} \right] \right)}{A_b [m^2]}$$

where:

- $E_{F,i}$ is the final energy for energy carrier i [kWh/m²-year]
- $fe_{F,i}$ is the emission factor for energy carrier i [kgCO₂eq/kWh]
- A_b is the area of the building [m²]

For the emission factor obtention, standard emission factors are provided for European countries by the Covenant of Mayors (Covenant of Mayors, 2024 [56]) and internationally by the IPCC. Emission factors used with reference to source and year should accompanied the assessment. Conversion factors (for GHG emissions, namely CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O) for European countries for national electricity consumption (considering the national energy mix) are included in following Table 42.

⁴³ <https://www.carbonfootprint.com/>

⁴⁴ <https://ecoinvent.org/>

⁴⁵ <http://www.cleanmetrics.com/html/database.htm>

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Table 42: 2021-year emission factors for national electricity consumption for EU member states (following an activity-based approach, IPCC; and a life-cycle approach, LC), from JRC dataset [56]

Country	Year 2021 Emission factor for GHG emissions from electricity consumption [tonnes of CO ₂ eq/MWh]	
	Activity-based approach, IPCC	Life-cycle approach, LC
Belgium	0.170	0.208
Bulgaria	0.508	0.540
Czechia	0.546	0.590
Denmark	0.105	0.138
Germany	0.383	0.438
Estonia	0.253	0.351
Ireland	0.348	0.442
Greece	0.412	0.502
Spain	0.175	0.236
France	0.068	0.087
Croatia	0.378	0.416
Italy	0.285	0.383
Cyprus	0.663	0.833
Latvia	0.305	0.437
Lithuania	0.079	0.100
Luxembourg	0.287	0.334
Hungary	0.222	0.266
Malta	0.356	0.470
Netherlands	0.331	0.406
Austria	0.244	0.281
Poland	0.779	0.877
Portugal	0.181	0.248
Romania	0.378	0.418
Slovenia	0.205	0.235
Slovakia	0.354	0.396
Finland	0.059	0.073
Sweden	0.015	0.027
Iceland	0.000	0.153
Norway	0.012	0.022
United Kingdom	-	-

Also, from the Covenant of Mayors publication on Technical Report on default emission factors (2024) [56], the following Table 43 provides also the default emission factors at European level for fossil fuels and municipal wastes (non-biomass fraction).

Table 43: CoM GHG default emission factors of SECAP online template

Energy carrier or Renewable energy	Standard (IPCC, 2006) [t CO ₂ eq/MWh]	LCA (ELCD ⁴⁶) [t CO ₂ eq/MWh]
Natural gas	0.202	0.261
Liquified Petroleum Gases	0.227	0.311
Natural Gas Liquids	0.232	0.339
Gas/Diesel oil	0.268	0.340
Motor gasoline	0.250	0.333
Lignite	0.365	0.373
Anthracite	0.356	0.404
Other Bituminous Coal	0.342	0.392
Sub-Bituminous Coal	0.348	0.416
Peat	0.383	0.388
Municipal Wastes (non-biomass fraction)	0.337	0.346
Other Liquid Biofuels	0.0001 (0.287)	0.147
Biogasoline	0.0001 (0.256)	0.057
Biodiesel	0.0001 (0.256)	0.264
Wood /wood waste	0.0007 (0.410)	0.015
Municipal wastes (biomass fraction)	0.0007 (0.367)	0.017
Other primary solid biomass	0.0007 (0.367)	0.022
Other biogas	0.000 (0.197)	0.025
Solar thermal	0.000	0.020
Geothermal	0.000	0.083
Wind	0.000	0.036
Hydroelectric	0.000	0.004
Photovoltaics	0.000	0.063

For reference, total annual primary energy demand from all end-uses in energy-efficient buildings does not usually exceed 120 kWh/m², which corresponds to about 24.5 kg CO₂eq/m².

So, the calculation is:

GWP from Water

For the calculation of the greenhouse gases associated with the delivery of water, the emission factor of the water is provided (GHG factor tap water):

$$GHG \text{ factor for tap water} = 0.378 \frac{kgCO_2eq}{m^3}$$

So, for the calculation of the GWP the formulas (adapted for both residential and non-residential buildings, from the calculation of TWC according to indicator 2.1-TWC, per occupant and per square meter respectively) are:

⁴⁶ ELCD: European reference Life Cycle Database. <https://nexus.openlca.org/database/ELCD>

$$GWP_{water} \left[\frac{kgCO_2eq}{m^2} \right] = \frac{TWC \left[\frac{m^3}{occupant \cdot year} \right] \times no.occupants \times GHG_{factor} \text{ tap water} \left[0.378 \frac{kgCO_2eq}{m^3} \right]}{A_b [m^2]}$$

$$GWP_{water} \left[\frac{kgCO_2eq}{m^2} \right] = TWC \left[\frac{m^3}{m^2 \cdot year} \right] \times GHG_{factor} \text{ tap water} \left[0.378 \frac{kgCO_2eq}{m^3} \right]$$

REFERENCES

Level(s) EU framework part 1 & 2 [30] and part 3 [53]. Macro-objective 1 “Greenhouse gas emissions along a buildings life cycle”, indicator 1.2 “Life cycle Global Warming Potential”.

BIM-SPEED project, Deliverable 4.1⁴⁷ “Baseline and Use Cases for BIM-based renovation projects and KPIs for EEB renovation”, indicator “Global Warming Potential (BS.GWP)”.

OptEEmAL project, Deliverable 2.2⁴⁸, “Report on District Sustainability Indicators to formulate and optimise scenarios”, indicator ENV 01 – Global Warming Potential (GWP)”.

EXAMPLE

An office building (non-residential building) located in Spain of 380 m² and with 35 workers has an energy consumption of 209 kWh/m²/year over the last year.

It means that the total energy consumption of the building is: 209 kWh/m²/year x 380 m² = 79,420 kWh/year, which is 79.42 MWh/year.

In the Table 44, this consumption is disaggregated per energy carrier in order to calculate the GWP. This data can come from the calculation of the indicators in Pillar 1.

Table 44: Energy consumption in the office building for the example and transformation to GWP, following the activity-based approach from the IPCC

Energy consumption type (per carrier)	Consumption [MWh/year]	Emission factor for GHG emissions [t CO ₂ eq/MWh]	GWP from energy [t CO ₂ eq/year]
Electricity	48.35	Spain: 0.175	8.46
Natural gas	17.64	0.202	3.56
RES: Photovoltaic	13.43	0	0
TOTAL			12.02 t CO ₂ eq/year

Calculating the total per square meter in the proper units:

$$GWP_{energy} = \frac{12.02 \frac{t CO_2eq}{year} \cdot 1000 \frac{kg CO_2eq}{t CO_2eq}}{380 m^2} = 31.64 \frac{kgCO_2eq}{m^2 \cdot year}$$

As calculated in the example for the 2.1-TWC, the Total Water Consumption of this building is 4.77 m³/occupant/year. So, the calculation of the GWP would be as follows:

$$GWP_{water} = \frac{4.77 \frac{m^3}{occupant \cdot year} \times 35 workers \times 0.378 \frac{kg CO_2eq}{m^3}}{380 m^2} = 0.17 \frac{kgCO_2eq}{m^2 \cdot year}$$

It can also be calculated based on the other TWC = 0.44 m³/m²/year:

⁴⁷ <https://www.bim-speed.eu/en/Project%20Results%20%20Documents/Deliverables/D4.1.pdf>

⁴⁸ <https://www.opteemal-project.eu/press-corner/publications/deliverables.html>

$$GWP_{water} = 0.44 \frac{m^3}{m^2 \cdot year} \times 0.378 \frac{kg CO_2eq}{m^3} = 0.17 \frac{kg CO_2eq}{m^2 \cdot year}$$

In this example, the total GWP is the sum of both GWP from energy and from water:

$$GWP_{(total)} = GWP_{Energy} + GWP_{Water} = 31.64 + 0.17 = 31.81 \frac{kg CO_2eq}{m^3}$$

A3.2.1 Bill of Materials (BoM)

As mentioned in the Global Warming Potential indicator, for the calculation of the GHG emissions in construction materials, a Bill of Materials (BoM). With a BoM, the GHG are accounted all along the materials lifecycle and then multiplied by the relevant conversion factors.

The Bill of Materials (BoM) is a mass-based inventory of the materials that compose a building, organised according to the main elements that a building is composed of. The focus is on the compilation of data on what the building is composed of, using the Bill of Quantities (BoQ) as starting point. Reporting can be made on the four main types of materials used, according to the four types defined by Eurostat⁴⁹: fossil energy materials, biomass, metal ores and non-metallic minerals.

As explained in Level(s) EU framework (part 1 & 2 [30] and part 3 [53]), for the indicator 2.1 “Life cycle tool: Building bill of materials (BoM)”, the BoQ is the starting point for compiling a BoM. A BoQ specifies the elements of a building (e.g. foundations, columns), including their technical specifications and expected lifetime. The BoQ comprises different categories of elements, which can have different functional performance characteristics. A BoM differs from a BoQ in that it describes the materials contained in the building's elements (e.g. concrete, steel, aluminium).

In CH buildings, it is especially relevant for the design stage of renovation works, mainly to be used as input for the calculation of the Global Warming Potential (indicator 2.2-GWP) of the renovation works and assess the carbon footprint (and compare it with the current one and the potentially reduced one after the energy renovation).

As explained in the Part 3 of the Level(s) EU framework, firstly a Bill of Quantities (BoQ) needs to be developed, and then, based on the composition of the elements in that list, the Bill of Materials is built under the four main elements defined by Eurostat.

Suggested tools and templates to report the results are provided in the Level(s) Part 3, and summarised in the following Table 45.

Table 45: KPI BoM data collection template (suggestion): Bill of Materials by building parts and elements

Building element	Bill of Quantities (indicate unit)	Bill of Materials by material type (kg)			
		Metals	Non-metallic mineral	Fossil energy	Biomass
Element X (e.g. window units)	(e.g. 10 units, 3m ² each)	(e.g. 5kg/unit)	(e.g. 2.6kg/unit)		
Element Y					
Element Z					

Calculating the total materials in kg, can be obtained the TMI or the Total Material Input of the building, as well as the TMO or the Total Material Output.

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https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Material_flow_accounts_and_resource_productivity#Consumption_by_material_category

A3.3 Operational Energy Costs

ID: 2.3-OEC

DEFINITION

It represents the total costs of the building spent on energy services (energy consumption, operation, maintenance, etc.). It includes all the costs arising from the use of energy sources. It is calculated as the energy consumption per type of fuel multiplied by the energy cost per type of fuel.

OBJECTIVE

This economic indicator is relevant in CH buildings when planning energy renovation (to be able to compare baseline and planned energy costs). It is thus also relevant to calculate the Payback period, indicator 2.4-PBP, as well as input for indicator of Life Cycle Cost, 2.5-LCC.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

The Operational Energy Costs (OEC) is assessed using real data or analytical methods related to building operational costs. There are two methods to calculate the operational energy costs. There are two methods to calculate OEC. The first and most accurate method uses energy bills. If these are unavailable, the second method estimates costs based on the building's energy consumption and local energy prices.

For the energy bill method, the data required include annual energy bills (of different carriers and energy types, such as electricity and natural gas), maintenance costs, and other energy service costs, all calculated per building area.

The formula for such calculation is:

$$OEC \left[\frac{\text{€}}{\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{year}} \right] = \frac{\sum \text{Energy Bills} + \text{Maintenance Costs} + \text{Other costs energy services} \left[\frac{\text{€}}{\text{year}} \right]}{A_b \text{ [m}^2\text{]}}$$

where:

- A_b is the area of the building [m²]

For the method of estimations, the formula to calculate the operational energy costs is similar, although considering the energy price of the different energy consumption types:

$$OEC \left[\frac{\text{€}}{\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{year}} \right] = \frac{\sum \left(\text{Final Energy consumption} \left[\frac{\text{kWh}}{\text{year}} \right] \times \text{Energy price} \left[\frac{\text{€}}{\text{kWh}} \right] \right) + \text{Maint. Costs} + \text{Other costs} \left[\frac{\text{€}}{\text{year}} \right]}{A_b \text{ [m}^2\text{]}}$$

For the energy price, the following Table 46 reports on electricity and natural gas prices for the EU Member States from Eurostat data source.

Table 46: Energy prices for households' consumers bi-annual data (both semesters of 2023 year) from Eurostat statistics per country, electricity prices⁵⁰ and natural gas prices⁵¹

Country	Electricity prices 2023-s1 [€/kWh]	Electricity prices 2023-s2 [€/kWh]	Natural gas prices 2023-s1 [€/kWh]	Natural gas prices 2023-s2 [€/kWh]
Belgium	0.2793	0.3592	0.1043	0.0843
Bulgaria	0.0993	0.0948	0.0789	0.0586
Czechia	0.2582	0.2624	0.0940	0.0929

⁵⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/nrg_pc_204/default/table?lang=EN

⁵¹ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/nrg_pc_202/default/table?lang=EN

Country	Electricity prices 2023-s1 [€/kWh]	Electricity prices 2023-s2 [€/kWh]	Natural gas prices 2023-s1 [€/kWh]	Natural gas prices 2023-s2 [€/kWh]
Denmark	0.1846	0.2976	0.0998	0.0651
Germany	0.2882	0.2973	0.0969	0.0930
Estonia	0.1826	0.1666	0.0879	0.0621
Ireland	0.4590	0.4514	0.1269	0.1415
Greece	0.1905	0.1876	0.1074	0.0853
Spain	0.2068	0.2165	0.0983	0.0919
France	0.2161	0.1893	0.0785	0.0899
Croatia	0.1171	0.1170	0.0422	0.0435
Italy	0.2565	0.3230	0.1044	0.1151
Cyprus	0.2099	0.2312	-	-
Latvia	0.2497	0.2521	0.1262	0.0725
Lithuania	0.1919	0.2407	0.1528	0.1201
Luxembourg	0.2875	0.3012	0.1492	0.0968
Hungary	0.0891	0.0914	0.0265	0.0263
Malta	0.1203	0.1186	-	-
Netherlands	0.2659	0.4436	0.1591	0.0802
Austria	0.2990	0.2691	0.1260	0.1147
Poland	0.1164	0.0918	0.0550	0.0588
Portugal	0.2012	0.2983	0.1060	0.0995
Romania	0.1441	0.1435	0.0461	0.0469
Slovenia	0.1614	0.1614	0.0856	0.0849
Slovakia	0.1230	0.1322	0.0476	0.0509
Finland	0.1712	0.1934	-	-
Sweden	0.1407	0.1784	0.1466	0.1378
Iceland	0.1274	0.1208	-	-
Norway	0.3174	0.3888	-	-
United Kingdom	-	-	-	-

REFERENCES

BIM-SPEED project, Deliverable 4.1⁵² “Baseline and Use Cases for BIM-based renovation projects and KPIs for EEB renovation”, indicator “Operational Energy Costs (BS.OEC)”.

OptEEmAL project, Deliverable 2.2⁵³, “Report on District Sustainability Indicators to formulate and optimise scenarios”, indicator ECO 01 – Operational energy cost”.

EXAMPLES

An office building (non-residential building) located in Spain of 380 m² and with 35 workers in has the following energy bills over the last year (Table 47).

⁵² <https://www.bim-speed.eu/en/Project%20Results%20%20Documents/Deliverables/D4.1.pdf>

⁵³ <https://www.opteemal-project.eu/press-corner/publications/deliverables.html>

Table 47: Energy bills (electricity and natural gas) of the office building example

Month	Electricity Bills [€]	Natural gas Bills [€]
January	1,319.84 €	261.41 €
February	1,199.85 €	261.41 €
March	1,099.87 €	217.84 €
April	799.90 €	174.27 €
May	799.90 €	87.14 €
June	628.07 €	24.44 €
July	251.23 €	24.44 €
August	209.36 €	24.44 €
September	628.07 €	40.73 €
October	879.29 €	122.19 €
November	1,151.46 €	203.66 €
December	1,256.13 €	244.39 €
TOTAL	10,222.96 €	1,686.36 €

The building has annual maintenance costs of 912.08 € (mainly due to the maintenance of HVAC systems), and costs for energy services of 456.54 €, which correspond to the optimisation of the energy use and the energy-efficient practices.

So, the calculation of the operational energy costs is the following:

$$\begin{aligned}
 OEC &= \frac{10,222.96€ \text{ (electricity)} + 1,686.36€ \text{ (natural gas)} + 912.08€ \text{ (maint.)} + 456.54€ \text{ (ener. serv.)}}{380 \text{ m}^2} \\
 &= \mathbf{34.94} \frac{€}{\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{year}}
 \end{aligned}$$

For an example of the second method for calculation of the operational energy costs, estimating the costs in case there is not access to energy bills, for a residential building located in Bulgaria of three floors, with three dwellings each (total of nine dwellings and estimate of 36 occupants). It has 926 m² and a total annual consumption as referred in Table 48, for each month of the year and disaggregated per energy type (electricity, and both natural gas and district heating in this case, half of each for the heating). The consumption is also multiplied by the energy prices of each, to obtain the energy costs.

Table 48: Energy consumption of a residential building and calculation of the energy costs

Month	Electricity consumption [kWh]	Electricity Price (0.0993 €/kWh for s1, 0.0948 €/kWh for s2)	Natural gas consumption [kWh]	Natural gas Price (0.0789 €/kWh for s1, 0.0586 €/kWh for s2)	DH consumption [kWh]	DH Price (0.049 €/kWh)
January	4075.50	386.36 €	8892.00	701.58 €	9792.00	479.81 €
February	3795.00	359.77 €	8280.00	653.29 €	8568.00	419.83 €
March	3861.00	366.02 €	5054.40	398.79 €	4993.92	244.70 €
April	3762.00	356.64 €	3283.20	259.04 €	3270.53	160.26 €
May	2797.20	265.17 €	596.74	47.08 €	0.00	0.00 €
June	2732.40	259.03 €	416.37	32.85 €	0.00	0.00 €
July	2581.20	256.31 €	344.16	20.17 €	0.00	0.00 €

Month	Electricity consumption [kWh]	Electricity Price (0.0993 €/kWh for s1, 0.0948 €/kWh for s2)	Natural gas consumption [kWh]	Natural gas Price (0.0789 €/kWh for s1, 0.0586 €/kWh for s2)	DH consumption [kWh]	DH Price (0.049 €/kWh)
August	2486.70	246.93 €	294.72	17.27 €	0.00	0.00 €
September	2670.30	265.16 €	474.72	27.82 €	0.00	0.00 €
October	3705.90	368.00 €	3234.24	189.53 €	3202.56	156.93 €
November	3993.00	396.50 €	5227.20	306.31 €	5162.40	252.96 €
December	4009.50	398.14 €	8748.00	512.63 €	8085.60	396.19 €
TOTAL		3,537.68 €		2,464.79 €		1,630.87 €

So, total energy costs (summing up the annual cost of the three energy types from the Table 48) are **7,662.58 €/year**.

Estimating also a cost for energy maintenance of 1,980 € (around 1300€ for the heating maintenance and around 650 for the electrical maintenance), and a cost for the additional energy services of 1,300 € due to the energy management, the calculation of the operational energy costs is the following:

$$\begin{aligned}
 OEC &= \frac{7,662.58€ \text{ (energy costs)} + 1,980€ \text{ (maintenance)} + 1,300€ \text{ (energy services)}}{926 \text{ m}^2} \\
 &= 11.82 \frac{€}{\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{year}}
 \end{aligned}$$

A3.4 Payback Period

ID: 2.4-PBP

DEFINITION

The payback period is the time it takes to cover the investment costs (mainly referred in this context to the investment in an energy retrofitting of a CH building). It can be calculated from the number of years elapsed between the initial investment, its subsequent operating costs and the point in time when cumulative savings offset the investment.

Investments with a short payback period are considered safer than those with a longer payback period.

OBJECTIVE

Payback period is usually considered as an additional criterion to assess an investment, especially to assess its risk. In this case, this economic indicator is relevant to assess the investment of an energy renovation in a CH building.

Thus, the target is to reduce the payback period by improving the building's energy performance and selecting cost-effective solutions. This leads to achieving lower operational energy costs.

As the invested capital flows back slower, the risk that the market changes and the investment capital can only be recovered later or not at all increases. On the other hand, costs and savings that occur after the investment has paid back are not considered. This is why sometimes decisions that are based on payback periods are not optimal and it is recommended to also consult other indicators.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

The indicator of payback period can be calculated from the following formula:

$$\text{Payback period [years]} = \frac{\text{Initial Investment Cost (of building retrofitting) [€]}}{\text{Yearly economic savings} \left[\frac{\text{€}}{\text{year}} \right]}$$

where:

$$\text{Yearly economic savings} \left[\frac{\text{€}}{\text{year}} \right] = \left(\text{OEC baseline} - \text{OEC after intervention} \left[\frac{\text{€}}{\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{year}} \right] \right) \times A_b \text{ [m}^2\text{]}$$

The Operational Energy Costs (OEC) are calculated according to the previous indicator (2.3-OEC).

A length of the period to recover an investment is a key factor in deciding among different scenarios. A 4-5-year period is usually acceptable. Longer periods may be acceptable if there are considerable energy savings (reduced energy costs and operating expenses) over the long run.

REFERENCES

BIM-SPEED project, Deliverable 4.1⁵⁴ “Baseline and Use Cases for BIM-based renovation projects and KPIs for EEB renovation”, indicator “Payback Period (BS.PP)”.

OptEEmAL project, Deliverable 2.2⁵⁵ “Report on District Sustainability Indicators to formulate and optimise scenarios”, indicator “Payback period (ECO 05)”.

CLIC project, Deliverable 2.4⁵⁶ “Database of indicators and data in pilot cities”, indicator 3.1.1 “Payback period”, within financial self-sustainability category.

EXAMPLE

An office building (non-residential building) located in Spain of 380 m² and with 35 workers, as calculated in previous examples, has a yearly Operational Energy Costs of 34.94 €/m². The energy consumption is 48.35 MWh/year for electricity, 17.64 MWh/year for natural gas and 13.43 MWh/year from PV.

For such building, there is a planned **investment of 34,200 €** in energy retrofitting: switching to LED lighting (5,700 €) and upgrade the HVAC system (28,500€).

The new (reduced) Operational Energy Costs are estimated mainly through a reduction in electricity bill (due to the LED lighting and to the new efficient HVAC system), as well as in the natural gas bill, derived from the increased efficiency and better control provided by the new HVAC system. Through the reduction of such costs (around 30% reduction of electricity bill and 50% of the natural gas bill), the **new operational energy costs are: 20.89 €/m² per year**.

Thus, the Payback Period is calculated as follows:

$$\text{Payback period} = \frac{34,200 \text{ € of investment}}{\left(34.94 \frac{\text{€}}{\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{year}} - 20.89 \frac{\text{€}}{\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{year}} \right) \cdot 380 \text{ m}^2} = 6.41 \text{ years}$$

⁵⁴ <https://www.bim-speed.eu/en/Project%20Results%20%20Documents/Deliverables/D4.1.pdf>

⁵⁵ https://www.opteemal-project.eu/files/opteemal_d2.2_districtsustainabilityindicators.pdf

⁵⁶ https://www.clicproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/D2.4_Database-of-indicators-and-data-in-pilot-cities.pdf

A3.5 Life Cycle Cost

ID: 2.5-LCC

DEFINITION

This indicator is focused on the life cycle elemental costs of a building, including the cost of construction, operation, maintenance, refurbishment and disposal. Although Level(s) recommends to report on costs for all the life cycle stages, the minimum scope of reporting required is for the following stages:

Use stage energy and water costs: the utility costs associated with **occupation of a building**, inclusive of communal costs of **operating a building** and the costs associated with occupants' **energy and water use**.

Construction and long-term maintenance, repair and replacement costs: including the elemental **cost of constructing** the building asset, exclusive of land costs. Comprising the enabling works to prepare the site for construction (or a **building for renovation**), the construction of the building (on- and off-site activities), and fit out in preparation for occupation.

These costs are strongly related with the calculated indicators in other pillars (energy – pillar 1), and in this pillar (total water consumption).

The common unit of measurement for each life cycle stage is euros per square metre of useable floor area per year (€/m²/year). The common unit shall be based on the net present cost of each life cycle stage. This shall be calculated by applying a discount rate of the costs incurred for each year of the reference study period.

The net present costs should be generally calculated using real costs, i.e. excluding inflation. However, assumptions about inflation may also be included within the discount rate if nominal costs are required for the purpose of detailed financial planning.

OBJECTIVE

The indicator has a focus on energy renovation, to optimise the life cycle cost and value of buildings to reflect the potential for long term performance, inclusive of acquisition, operation, maintenance, refurbishment, disposal and end of life.

Life Cycle Costing (LCC) is particularly relevant to achieving an improved environmental performance as higher initial capital costs may be required to achieve lower life-cycle running costs, higher residual property values and improved workforce productivity. It therefore represents a method for making effective, long-term investment decisions.

The life cycle costs provide important information to investors, asset managers and occupiers. The latter includes homeowners, who may wish to understand the costs associated with maintaining and running a home for the duration of a full mortgage term, and residents' organisations responsible for the communal costs of maintaining apartment block.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

The data required for the calculation of this indicator and sources of such data are:

- Construction costs: data obtained from suppliers and contractors.

- **Operational (utility) costs:** during the design and construction stage, on the basis of the energy and water use performance assessment. Upon completion, property managers and owner occupiers may obtain data from metering.
- **Maintenance, repair and replacement costs:** at a basic level, estimates require data on the design of elements and components, the environmental exposure conditions that they may be exposed to, the service conditions that they will be subjected to, and the potential causes and probability of early failures.
- **Refurbishment costs:** based on currently available products and technologies at current prices. For offices, this could range from costing of a renewal of the fit-out and servicing, to a change of use from office to residential or short stay units (or vice versa).
- **End-of-life costs:** revised cost estimates could be obtained from contractors on the basis of design features intended to make the building easier to deconstruct, reuse and recycle. Cost estimates would need to be made based on current technologies and prices.

In the case of CH buildings, the most relevant costs to consider from those listed above are the operational costs (from energy and water use), and the refurbishment costs, if planned.

The calculation formula for the LCC would be the following:

$$LCC \left[\frac{\text{€}}{\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{year}} \right] = \frac{\text{Initial Investment Cost (of retrofitting) [€]} + \text{OEC over lifespan [€]} + \text{Other Costs [€]}}{A_b [\text{m}^2] \cdot \text{Lifespan of the building or retrofit [years]}}$$

where:

- **A_b** is the area of the building [m²]
- **Lifespan of the building or retrofit:** estimated lifespan of the building or of the retrofitting measures if it is what is being evaluated [years]
- **OEC over lifespan [€] = OEC after intervention** $\left[\frac{\text{€}}{\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{year}} \right] \cdot A_b [\text{m}^2] \cdot \text{Lifespan [years]}$
- **Other costs:** for Maintenance, Replacement or Repair Costs not related to the energy operation of the building (the costs not included in the OEC but relevant for the calculation or the building retrofit) [€]. They should be included by their related lifespan (years), so the cost is only provided in €.

REFERENCES

Level(s) EU framework part 1 & 2 [30] and part 3 [53]. Macro-objective 6 “Optimised life cycle cost and value”, indicator 6.1 “Life cycle costs”.

OptEEmAL project, Deliverable 2.2⁵⁷ “Report on District Sustainability Indicators to formulate and optimise scenarios”, indicator “Life cycle cost (ECO 03)”.

EXAMPLE

The office building (non-residential building) located in Spain has 380 m² and 35 workers, and, as previously calculated, has a yearly Operational Energy Costs of 34.95 €/m² and an energy consumption of 48.35 MWh/year for electricity, 17.64 MWh/year for natural gas and 13.43 MWh/year from PV.

⁵⁷ https://www.opteemal-project.eu/files/opteemal_d2.2_districtsustainabilityindicators.pdf

There is a planned investment of 34,200 € in energy retrofitting, by switching to LED lighting (5,700 €) and upgrading the HVAC system (28,500€). For it, the new OEC are 20.89 €/m² per year, and the payback period (2.4-PBP) to recover the investment is calculated in 6.4 years. For this kind of interventions, we have assumed a lifespan of 20 years for the LED lighting and HVAC system upgrades.

Following the LCC formula, the calculation of the life cycle cost would be:

$$LCC = \frac{34,200 \text{ €} + \left(20.89 \frac{\text{€}}{\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{year}} \cdot 380 \text{ m}^2 \cdot 20 \text{ years}\right)}{380 \text{ m}^2 \cdot 20 \text{ years}} = 25.39 \frac{\text{€}}{\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{year}}$$

A3.6 Energy Circularity Indicator

ID: 2.6-ECI

DEFINITION

It is referred to the rate of circular energy to total life cycle energy consumption of the building or retrofitting. By “circular energy” it is understood the renewable energy produced onsite or near places and the energy savings derived from the application of passive measures. Therefore, it explicitly excludes the renewable energy coming from the grid.

OBJECTIVE

The objective is to obtain a simple indicator that provides insights of the energy circularity of the cultural heritage building.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

The formula to calculate this indicator is provided below, it is expressed in % but calculated in Primary Energy Terms.

$$\text{Energy circularity } [\%] = \frac{\text{RE produced onsite} \left[\frac{\text{kWh}_{PE}}{\text{year}} \right] + \text{Energy savings for passive measures} \left[\frac{\text{kWh}}{\text{year}} \right]}{\text{Total energy consumption} \left[\frac{\text{kWh}_{PE}}{\text{year}} \right]} \times 100\%$$

where:

- **RE:** Renewable Energy [kWh_{PE}/year]
- **PE:** Primary Energy

To actually assess the energy savings derived from the application of passive measures, as well as the increase of renewable energy produced onsite, it is needed to calculate the ECI ex-ante and ex-post the interventions or energy retrofitting.

REFERENCES

The main source is from the HOUSEFUL project, which adapted it from the Ellen MacArthur Foundation “Materials Circularity Indicator” [57].

HOUSEFUL project, Deliverable 2.3⁵⁸ “Reference methodologies and KPIs in circular economy analysis”, indicator “Energy Circularity Indicator (ECI)”.

⁵⁸ https://houseful.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/HOUSEFUL_D2.3-Reference-methodologies-and-KPIs-in-circular-economy-analysis.pdf

EXAMPLE

The office building (non-residential building) located in Spain has 380 m² and 35 workers, and, as previously calculated, has a total energy consumption of 79.42 MWh/year, from which 48.35 MWh are for electricity, 17.64 MWh for natural gas and 13.43 MWh from PV (produced onsite, self-consumption). The PV panels produce more energy than it is consumed by the building, this, the PV annual production of the panels in the building is 27.38 MWh.

There is a planned intervention to replace the windows of the building with more efficient ones (passive measure). Assuming that around 30% of the total energy consumption is lost through inefficient windows, and that the new ones would be 30% more efficient in terms of insulation, the **potential energy savings** would be 7.15 MWh/year.

So, applying the formula to calculate the circular energy, the result for this example (with all units in MWh) would be:

$$\text{Energy circularity} = \frac{27.38 \frac{\text{MWh}}{\text{year}} + 7.15 \frac{\text{MWh}}{\text{year}}}{79.42 \frac{\text{MWh}}{\text{year}}} \times 100\% = 43.47\%$$

A3.7 Water Circularity Indicator

ID: 2.7-WCI

DEFINITION

It is referred to the rate of circular water to total life cycle water consumption of the building or retrofitting. By “circular water” it is understood the water content of the recycled/reused products and the recycled or rainwater harvested used during operations and/or end-of-life phases.

“Circular water” explicitly includes greywater, blackwater and rainwater use.

OBJECTIVE

The objective is to obtain a simple indicator that provides insights of the water circularity of the cultural heritage building.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

The formula to calculate this indicator is provided below, expressed in % but calculated in m³ of water.

$$\text{Water circularity} [\%] = \frac{\text{Reused Water} \left[\frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{year}} \right]}{\text{Total Water Consumption (TWC)} \left[\frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{year}} \right]}$$

To calculate the indicator, it is needed to identify the volume of greywater and blackwater reused (the later after appropriate treatment, if applicable), as well as to identify the volume of rainwater harvested and used.

For the total water consumption, ideally, the volume of water used during construction phase (or during the retrofitting works if applicable) would be identified, as well as the water used during the operational phase (TWC, which can be obtained from indicator 2.1-TWC, but multiplying the result by the number of occupants or area (m²), in order to obtain the total water consumption of the building).

To actually assess the increase of water circularity derived from an intervention, application of measures or retrofitting, it is needed to calculate the WCI ex-ante and ex-post.

REFERENCES

The main source is from the HOUSEFUL project, which adapted it from the Ellen MacArthur Foundation “Materials Circularity Indicator” [57].

HOUSEFUL project, Deliverable 2.3⁵⁹ “Reference methodologies and KPIs in circular economy analysis”, indicator “Water Circularity Indicator (WCI)”.

EXAMPLE

An office building (non-residential building) of 380 m² and with 35 workers in usage stage, with a Total Water Consumption (calculated in the example of 2.1-TWC) of 4.77 m³/occupant per year, or equivalent to 0.44 m³/m² per year; which means a total 166.86 m³ of water per year.

The building has a **greywater reused** from water in sinks of around a 20% of the total water consumption (**33.37 m³** per year).

In addition, the building counts on a system to harvest and use some of the **rainwater**, around **20 m³/year**.

$$\text{Water circularity} = \frac{33.37 \frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{year}} + 20 \frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{year}}}{166.86 \frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{year}}} \times 100\% = 32.00 \%$$

A3.8 Material Circularity Indicator

ID: 2.10-MCI

DEFINITION

It is referred to the rate of circular materials to total life cycle material use of the building or retrofitting. By “circular material” it is understood:

- Materials from **circular sources** (at **construction phase**): recycled content or renewable content according to Cradle to Cradle Certified Products Standard⁶⁰.
- **Cyclable material** at the end of its use (**end of life phase**) through technical or biological cycle. The paths and strategies considered cyclable according to Cradle to Cradle Certified Products Standard.
- Material in the **use phase**, what is the expected **lifespan** of the products used, as opposed to the average lifespan of similar products.

For the identification of such different materials in the different phases of the building lifecycle, some examples are included below, from Ellen MacArthur Foundation⁶¹, Cradle to Cradle Products

⁵⁹ https://houseful.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/HOUSEFUL_D2.3-Reference-methodologies-and-KPIs-in-circular-economy-analysis.pdf

⁶⁰ Cradle to Cradle products innovation institute. Cradle to Cradle Certified, Product Standard Version 4.1: https://api.c2ccertified.org/assets/c2cc-v4.1-standard_final_050224-1715731328.pdf, searcher for certified products: <https://c2ccertified.org/certified-products>

⁶¹ <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/>

Innovation Institute⁶², BuildingGreen⁶³, Biodegradable Products Institute (BPI)⁶⁴, International Living Future Institute⁶⁵, and World Green Building Council (WorldGBC)⁶⁶.

Materials from circular sources (construction phase):

Materials from recycled content could be steel, aluminium, concrete, glass, plastic, gypsum (if recycled) or reclaimed wood.

Materials from renewable content are bamboo, cork, hempcrete, linoleum, straw bales, cellulose insulation or wood from sustainable forestry.

Additional examples are the bio-based composites (made from agricultural residues or natural fibers) and Polylactic Acid (PLA).

Cyclable materials (end of life phase):

Materials that can be **technically recycled** or reused could include:

- Metals, such as steel, aluminium or copper.
- Plastics, such as Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET), High-Density Polyethylene (HDPE) or Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC).
- Glass
- Concrete
- Gypsum
- Timber and engineered wood products (such as plywood and MDF).
- Ceramic tiles
- Fiberglass insulation.

The materials that are part of the **biological cycle** are those that can be safely returned to the environment through processes like composting or biodegradation. These materials are derived from natural sources and decompose without harmful residues, thereby enriching the soil and contributing to natural cycles. These materials include:

- Untreated wood (natural wood not treated with chemicals) and bamboo.
- Natural fibres, such as cotton, wool, linen or hemp.
- Natural insulation materials, such as sheep wool insulation, cork and cellulose insulation.
- Natural polymers, such as Polylactic Acid (PLA) or starch-based plastics.
- Bio-based composites, such as hempcrete and

Expected (to assess if **extended**) **lifespan** (use phase):

The expected lifespan of the materials can be known through the manufacturer specifications (technical datasheets and product warranties), from industry standards and guidelines, from

⁶² <https://c2ccertified.org/>

⁶³ <https://www.buildinggreen.com/>

⁶⁴ <https://bpiworld.org/>

⁶⁵ <https://living-future.org/>

⁶⁶ <https://worldgbc.org/>

historical performance data, research studies, building codes and regulations, as well as sustainable certification programmes (certifications such as LEED⁶⁷, BREEAM⁶⁸, Cradle to Cradle...).

OBJECTIVE

The objective is to obtain an indicator that provides insights of the material circularity of the CH building.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

The formula for this indicator is provided below, expressed as % but calculated in kg of materials.

$$\text{Materials circularity } [\%] = \frac{\sum \text{Cyclable } M \text{ at } EoL [kg] + \sum \text{Extended lifespan } [kg]}{\sum M \text{ total } [kg]}$$

where:

- **M:** Materials
- **EoL:** End of Life
- **Materials from circular sources:** identified by determining the mass of materials that are recycled (recycled content) and the mass of materials that are renewable (renewable content), as per the Cradle to Cradle Certified Products Standard.
- **Cyclable Materials at End of Life:** such materials are identified by determining the mass of materials that can be recycled or reused technically (technical cycle) and the mass of materials that can be composted or biodegraded (biological cycle).
- **Extended lifespan:** to assess the mass of extended lifespan in the use phase, evaluating the expected lifespan of the products used to the average lifespan of similar products. If a product used has an extended lifespan, this should be accounted in the calculation.

For the assessment of the mass of all these materials, a developed Bill of Materials (BoM) can be of help for an easier accounting.

REFERENCES

The main source is from the HOUSEFUL project, which adapted it from Madaster⁶⁹ “Madaster Circularity Indicator Explained”⁷⁰ and Ellen MacArthur Foundation “Materials Circularity Indicator”. HOUSEFUL project, Deliverable 2.3⁷¹ “Reference methodologies and KPIs in circular economy analysis”, indicator “Materials Circularity Indicator (MCI)”.

EXAMPLE

An office building (non-residential building) located in Spain of 380 m² and with 35 workers. For such building, there are different planned interventions: one to replace the windows of the building with more efficient ones (passive measure). The other intervention is with a focus on accessibility, to include an access ramp to bridge 8 steps to the main entrance of the building.

⁶⁷ <https://www.usgbc.org/leed>

⁶⁸ <https://breeam.com/>

⁶⁹ Madaster Platform: <https://madaster.com/>

⁷⁰ Madaster Platform, 2021. *Madaster Circularity Indicator Explained.* <https://docs.madaster.com/files/en/Madaster%20-%20Circularity%20Indicator%20explained.pdf>

⁷¹ https://houseful.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/HOUSEFUL_D2.3-Reference-methodologies-and-KPIs-in-circular-economy-analysis.pdf

To estimate the MCI for both interventions in the building, firstly it is needed to identify the materials used in each intervention and determine their total mass (through Bill of Materials, BoM), then, it is needed to determine the proportion of circular materials, key input data for the Materials Circularity indicator. In the following Table 49 the materials used in both interventions are depicted, with the type of materials and its mass. It is also included the phase to which they belong to and their mass in kilograms.

Table 49: Bill of Materials of the interventions that are planned for the building

Intervention	Building element	Material type	Mass [kg]	Phase
Window replacement	New windows: Frames	Aluminium (recycled)	300 kg	Construction
	New windows: Glazing	Double-glazed glass (50% recycled)	500 kg	Construction
	New windows: Insulation	Fiberglass (not recycled)	200 kg	Construction
	Old windows (disposal): Frames	Aluminium	300 kg	End of Life
	Old windows (disposal): Glazing	Single-glazed glass	500 kg	End of Life
Accessibility ramp	Concrete	Concrete (not recycled)	1,000 kg	Construction
	Reinforcement	Recycled steel rebar	200 kg	Construction

With these figures, the **Total mass** of Materials is **3,000 kg**, including both construction and end of life materials.

From the end of life phase, the original materials of the old windows are not recyclable, so they have not been included in the equation.

In addition, the new windows have an **extended lifespan** of 50 years, compared to typical windows, which have a lifespan of 30 years. Thus, the mass of the new windows should be added to the equation: 300 kg aluminium + 500 kg glazing + 200 kg insulation = **1,000 kg**.

The result of the Materials Circularity indicator (MCI) for this example would be:

$$MCI = \frac{300 \text{ kg aluminium} + \frac{500}{2} \text{ kg glass} + 200 \text{ kg steel} + 1,000 \text{ kg extended lifespan}}{3,000 \text{ kg}} = 58.33 \%$$

Annex 4. Pillar 3 KPIs: Resilience to climate and human-made hazards

A4.1 Inventory of relevant Hazards

ID: 3.1-IoH

DEFINITION

It assesses the presence of an inventory of the relevant hazards, to keep track of relevant current or future climate and human-made hazards in the site (pilot).

The main hazards impacting CH are outlined in Table 50, categorised by their nature: climate change risks, geological incidents and human-made hazards. Table 11 in section 3.3 (Pillar 3) provides an in-depth overview of specific climate change hazards affecting CH, based on the HERACLES project. This includes potential physical, social and cultural impacts on CH of each hazard group.

Table 50: Hazards overview, depending on their nature

Nature	Hazard
Climate change risks (from Table 11, climate change risks from HERACLES project)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Flooding (sea, river, coast) - Intense rainfall - Changes in water table levels, in soil chemistry, in ground water changes - Sea salt chlorides - Diurnal, seasonal, extreme temperature events (heat waves, snow loading) - Changes in freeze-thaw and ice storms, and increase in wet frost - Wind-driven rain - Drought - pH precipitation - Changes in deposition of pollutants - Spread of existing and new species of insects - Increase in mould growth - Changes in lichen colonies on buildings - Decline of original materials
Geological incidents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Earthquakes - Volcanic eruptions - Tsunamis
Human-made hazards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Continuous population growth (uncontrolled urbanisation) - Unsustainable tourism - Pollution to the atmosphere and of the seas - Destruction of rain forests - Fires burning out of control - Alterations to sensitive ecosystems - Destruction of the ozone layer - Civil strife - Wars and acts of terrorism - Vandalism on buildings, infrastructures, etc.

OBJECTIVE

This indicator aims to understand whether the CH site has an inventory of relevant hazards that have occurred in the past, to understand the degree of documentation, concern and awareness of the climate change, geological incidents and human-made hazards.

It is related to the step I of the methodology for risk assessment, the identification of hazards.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

This indicator is evaluated through an answer to the main question: “Does the CH site have an inventory of the relevant (climate change, geological incidents or human-made) hazards that have occurred in the past?”.

This includes historical records, archives, reports and studies conducted by relevant authorities or organisations responsible for managing the site. The hazards should be compiled and documented. The documentation of the hazard should include, at least, the date, location, severity, impacts and any mitigation or response measures taken. Additionally, the documentation could include the relation of the event with the climate change, geological incident or human-made hazard.

The documentation where this inventory is reported could include various types of documents, such as incidents reports, newspaper articles, scientific studies, historical accounts, government records or archives, environmental impact assessment, as well as risk assessment and hazard mapping documents.

Table 51: Assessment of indicator 3.1-IoH, scoring

Does the CH site have an inventory of the relevant hazards that have occurred in the past?	
Answer	Score
No, the hazards occurred are not documented or compiled anywhere.	1
No, only few hazards of those occurred are identified, but they are not well documented.	2
Partially, the main hazards are identified and partially documented (although not complete information for all of them).	3
Yes, the hazards occurred are well documented (relevant information) and, although they are located in different places (documents), a list has been developed relating (and linking) all of them.	4
Yes, the hazards occurred are properly identified and documented with all the relevant information (collected in one place): date, location, severity, impacts and mitigation/response measures taken.	5

REFERENCES

The indicator is adapted from the paper “A Review on Key Performance Indicator for Climate Change” from Schokker et al. (2022) [37], specifically, indicator #30 under Climate Hazards category.

A4.2 Hazards Identification

ID: 3.2-HI

DEFINITION

It lists the most significant climate or human-made hazards that the site faces or will face.

The main hazards affecting CH can be consulted in Table 52 of hazards overview, related to their different nature: climate change risks, geological incidents or human-made hazards. Table 11 in

main section 3.3 (pillar 3) from HERCALES project includes a deeper overview of the specific climate change hazards that affect the CH, including the potential physical, social and cultural impacts on cultural heritage of each group. Although not exhaustive, both lists of potential main hazards affecting CH sites can give a good idea to identify the different risks, impacts and threats that the site may suffer, depending on its location (country/city and geography), climate, geopolitical context, cultural context, use, population, etc.

Table 52: Hazards overview, depending on their nature

Nature	Hazard
Climate change risks (from Table 11, climate change risks from HERACLES project)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Flooding (sea, river, coast) - Intense rainfall - Changes in water table levels, in soil chemistry, in ground water changes - Sea salt chlorides - Diurnal, seasonal, extreme temperature events (heat waves, snow loading) - Changes in freeze-thaw and ice storms, and increase in wet frost - Wind-driven rain - Drought - pH precipitation - Changes in deposition of pollutants - Spread of existing and new species of insects - Increase in mould growth - Changes in lichen colonies on buildings - Decline of original materials
Geological incidents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Earthquakes - Volcanic eruptions - Tsunamis
Human-made hazards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Continuous population growth (uncontrolled urbanisation) - Unsustainable tourism - Pollution to the atmosphere and of the seas - Destruction of rain forests - Fires burning out of control - Alterations to sensitive ecosystems - Destruction of the ozone layer - Civil strife - Wars and acts of terrorism - Vandalism on buildings, infrastructures, etc.

OBJECTIVE

This indicator aims to obtain a list of the main hazards that potentially affects the CH site, as an inventory of relevant hazards that may occurred in the site.

It is related to the step I of the methodology for risk assessment, the identification of hazards.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

This indicator is evaluated through an answer to the main question: “Does the CH site have a set of the relevant potential hazards (climate change, geological incidents or human-made) that may occur or affect the pilot in the future?”.

The list should encompass the various potential threats relevant to the CH site’s location, historical context and vulnerability. The hazards identified should be detailed, through the definition of the category and also through the specification of why it is relevant for the site, as well as including a description of how/in what degree would affect the site’s physical integrity, historical significance, cultural value or visitor experience. Additionally, the identification can include also whether the identification of the hazard is supported by evidence, such as historical records, scientific studies, risks assessment or expert knowledge. Along with that, the consideration of future trends can be included in such documentation, considering potential future trends and scenarios, particularly regarding climate change impacts.

Table 53: Assessment of indicator 3.2-HI, scoring

Does the CH site have a set of the relevant potential hazards that may occur or affect the pilot in the future?	
Answer	Score
No, the potential hazards that may occur in the future are not documented or compiled anywhere.	1
No, only few potential hazards that may occur are identified, but they are not well documented.	2
Partially, the main potential hazards that may occur are identified and partially documented (although not complete information for all of them).	3
Yes, the potential hazards that may occur are well documented (relevant information) and, although they are located in different places (documents), a list has been developed relating (and linking) all of them.	4
Yes, the potential hazards that may occur are properly identified and documented with all the relevant information (collected in one place): category, relevance for the site, impact to the site’s physical integrity, historical significance, cultural value or visitor experience. Added value: identification supported by evidence as well as the consideration of future trends.	5

REFERENCES

The indicator is adapted from the paper “A Review on Key Performance Indicator for Climate Change” from Schokker et al. (2022) [37], specifically, the indicator #31 under Climate Hazards category.

A4.3 Risk Management Plan(s)

ID: 3.3-RMP

DEFINITION

It assesses the presence, quality and effectiveness of management plans designed to address risks, potential hazards and vulnerability at cultural heritage sites, related to climate change and human-made hazards.

Specifically, it checks the existence of management plans for risks, hazards or vulnerabilities through adaptation, mitigation and/or other response.

OBJECTIVE

This indicator aims to understand whether the CH site has management plan(s) for the risks, potential hazards and vulnerability, either for adaptation, mitigation or response.

It is related to the step I of the methodology for risk assessment, the identification of hazards.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

This indicator is evaluated through an answer to the main question: “Does the CH site have a one or more management plans addressing risks, potential hazards and vulnerability (related to climate change or human-made hazards), providing response, adaptation, and mitigation measures?”.

The management plan(s) should be a **formal document** outlining strategies, protocols and procedures for identifying, assessing and mitigating risks. They should address a **wide range of potential hazards and vulnerabilities** relevant to the CH site (aligned to those identified as relevant in the indicator 2.2-HI), including those related to climate change, geological incidents and human-made hazards. The risk management plan(s) should also be **integrated** into the overall management framework of the CH site, complementing existing management plans for conservation, preservation, maintenance and visitor management, whether relevant.

The management plan(s) should also cover all aspects of risk management, including **adaptation** (preparation for future hazards), **mitigation** (reducing the risks) and **response** (addressing immediate threats). Each aspect should be clearly defined and supported by actionable strategies.

It is also relevant that the Risk Management Plan(s) are accessible and communicated to relevant stakeholders, including site managers, staff, local authorities and community members. Effective communication ensures that everyone understands their roles and responsibilities in implementing risk management measures.

The Risk Management Plan(s) should also undergo **regular review and updates** to reflect changing circumstances, new hazards, evolving knowledge and lessons learnt from past experiences. These plans should be dynamic and responsive to emerging risks.

The **resource allocation** is also a relevant aspect in the management plans. The Risk Management Plan(s) should allocate sufficient resources, including financial, human and technical resources to effectively implement risk management measures. An adequate resource allocation is essential for plan implementation and sustainability.

Ideally, the management plans should also include mechanisms in place to **monitor and evaluate** their performance. This includes tracking the effectiveness of implemented measures, identifying areas for improvement and adjusting strategies accordingly.

To the extent of possible, the management plans should also evaluate whether they **comply with relevant standards**, guidelines and best practices established by national or international heritage conservation organizations.

For the evaluation of this KPI, the following set of questions is defined in Table 54 for the cases where there is a Risk Management Plan. Then, according to the number of positive answers to the elements of the Management Plan (checklist), the scoring in the following Table 55 is given.

D3.1 – First INHERIT Assessment and Monitoring Framework

Table 54: Checklist for the evaluation of quality and effectiveness of the management plans (input to indicator 3.3-RMP, scoring table)

Evaluation of quality and effectiveness of the management plans – Checklist	
Aspect	Yes / No
1. The potential hazards and vulnerabilities addressed by the plan or plans are those relevant to the CH site and aligned with those identified in KPI 2.2-HI.	
2. The management plan or plans are integrated into the overall management framework of the CH site, complementing other existing management plans.	
3. The management plan covers all aspects of risk management : adaptation (preparation for future hazards), mitigation (reducing the risks) and response (addressing immediate threats).	
4. Besides covering the three key aspects of adaptation, mitigation and response, each of them are clearly defined and supported by actionable strategies .	
5. The Risk Management Plan is accessible and communicated to relevant stakeholders, ensuring that everyone understands their roles and responsibilities in implementing risk management measures.	
6. The Risk Management Plan is a dynamic document which envisages regular reviews , and it is updated taking into account changing circumstances, new hazards and including lessons learnt from past experiences.	
7. The management plan properly allocates sufficient resources , including financial, human and technical resources to effectively implement the risk management measures.	
8. The management plan includes mechanisms to monitor and evaluate its performance . These mechanisms track the effectiveness of the implemented measures, identify areas for improvement and adjust strategies accordingly.	
9. The management plan complies with relevant standards, guidelines and best practices established by national or international heritage conservation associations.	

Table 55: Assessment of indicator 3.3-RMP, scoring

Does the CH site have one or more management plans addressing risks, potential hazards and vulnerability, providing response, adaptation and mitigation measures?		
Answer		Score
No, there is no risk, vulnerability or hazards management plan.		1
Yes, there is at least a “formal” management plan for the relevant risks, hazards or vulnerabilities of the site, outlining strategies, protocols and procedures for identifying, assessing and mitigating risks. → evaluate it through the Table 54 and count the number of positive responses.	0 – 2 “Yes” answers	2
	3 – 4 “Yes” answers	3
	5 – 7 “Yes” answers	4
	8 – 9 “Yes” answers	5

REFERENCES

The indicator is adapted from the paper “A Review on Key Performance Indicator for Climate Change” from Schokker et al. (2022) [37], specifically, the indicator #32 under Climate Hazards category.

A4.4 Risk Impact assessment: Vulnerability and Exposure

ID: 3.4-RI_VxE

DEFINITION

It is a qualitative assessment of the risk impact of climate change, geological incidents and human-made hazards to cultural heritage buildings or sites through a matrix of vulnerability and exposure. It is also an effective way to systematically assess and prioritise the risks.

The assessment is done to each risk or hazard individually, and they are scored with a 1-5 scale, obtaining a "very high", "high", "moderate", "low" and "very low" value, which is in turn the qualitative result of the risk impact.

The **vulnerability** is the propensity or predisposition of the site to be adversely affected. It is the degree to which the CH site or building is susceptible to damage. Such predisposition is an internal characteristic of the site. The vulnerability is a result of historical, social, economic, political, cultural, institutional, natural resource, and environmental conditions and processes. So, it includes factors such as the structural integrity, the materials used, the historical value, and its current condition.

The **exposure** is referred to the presence (location) of the CH site in places that could be adversely affected by physical events and, thereby, are subject to potential future harm, loss, or damage. So, it is the extent to which the site or building is exposed to potential hazards, including the frequency and intensity of climate-related events, geological incidents and human-made hazards.

OBJECTIVE

The objective of this indicator is to qualitatively assess the risk impact of each hazard identified in **indicator 3.2-HI** of hazards identification. It then allows to prioritise the risk and prepare a risk management plan for the most relevant ones, developing the proper adaptation and mitigation strategies, as well as the response in case of occurrence.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

The indicator is easily assessed by applying the matrix below for each identified hazard. So, the result will be obtained as a qualitative value for each hazard relevant to the CH site.

The **vulnerability** can be assessed by answering the question "**How predisposed the CH site is to be adversely affected by the hazard?**". For answering such question, historical, social, economic, political, cultural, institutional, natural resource, and environmental conditions and processes of the site that make them more vulnerable to the hazard should be considered. Thus, a following criteria should be selected:

- 1. Very high** – the CH site will be affected for sure, due to historical/ social/ economic/ political/ cultural/ institutional/ environmental condition that makes it vulnerable to the hazard. *E.g. structures in poor condition, highly sensitive materials, significant historical value, limited resources for maintenance.*
- 2. High** – the CH site will be probably affected due to certain condition(s) that makes it vulnerable to the hazard. *E.g. structures with some deterioration, sensitive materials, notable historical value, some resources for maintenance.*
- 3. Moderate** – the CH site may be affected due to certain condition(s) that makes it vulnerable to the hazard. *E.g. structures in fair condition, moderately sensitive materials, average historical value, adequate resources for maintenance.*

4. **Low** – the CH site will most likely not be affected, since it does not have specific historical/ social/ economic/ political/ cultural/ institutional/ environmental conditions that makes it vulnerable to the hazard. *E.g. structures in good condition, durable materials, lower historical value, sufficient resources for maintenance.*
5. **Very low** – the CH site will certainly not be affected, since it does not have specific conditions that makes it vulnerable to the hazard. *E.g. structures in excellent condition, highly durable materials, minimal historical value, ample resources for maintenance.*

The **exposure** can be assessed by answering the question “**How much the CH site would be adversely affected by the hazard?**”. To answer this question, it should be considered if the site is subject to potential harm, loss or damage by the hazard, mainly due to the presence of people, livelihoods, environmental services and resources, infrastructure, or economic, social or cultural assets in places that could be adversely affected by physical events. Thus, the following criteria should be assessed, considering both the amount of assets (part or whole of the CH site) exposed to the hazard, and the damage that would be done to the CH site depending on the type of hazard:

1. **Very high** – the whole CH site will be affected, and damaged in a high degree. E.g. frequent and severe hazards, for example if it is located in a high-risk earthquake zone, frequent severe weather events, etc.
2. **High** – a major part of the CH site will be affected, with high damage due to the nature of the hazard. *E.g. regular hazards with moderate severity.*
3. **Moderate** – part of the CH site will be affected and damaged. *E.g. occasional hazards with moderate to low severity.*
4. **Low** – very little of the CH site will be affected, either because the site is not very exposed or because the hazard does not damage the site in a high degree. *E.g. infrequent hazards with low severity.*
5. **Very low** – almost nothing of the CH site would be affected by the hazard, mainly because it is well protected to it or because the hazard does not mean a great threat to the site. *E.g. rare hazards with minimal severity.*

The detailed matrix is included in the following Table 56.

Table 56: Impacts assessment matrix, vulnerability and exposure of each hazard identified to the CH site (KPI 3.4-RI-VxE)

Exposure \ Vulnerability	Vulnerability				
	Very high (affected for sure)	High (probably affected)	Moderate (may be affected)	Low (most likely not affected)	Very low (certainly not affected)
Very high (whole CH site affected)	Very high	Very high	High	High	Moderate
High (major part of the CH site affected)	Very high	High	Moderate	Moderate	Low
Moderate (part of the CH site affected)	High	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Low
Low (very little of the CH site affected)	High	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Very low
Very low (almost nothing of the CH site affected)	Moderate	Low	Low	Very low	Very low

The results of such matrix can be assessed through the following criteria (included also in Table 14 in the main section 3.3 – Pillar 3).

- **Very high.** Maximum → **unacceptable**: maximum threat to CH site. Implement immediate adaptation or mitigation measures/plan.
- **High.** High → **unacceptable**: large threat to CH site. Implement adaptation or mitigation measures/plan.
- **Moderate.** Medium → **acceptable**: some threat to CH site. Manage with adaptation or mitigation measures/plan.
- **Low.** Low → **acceptable**: little threat to CH site. Some management with adaptation or mitigation measures/plan necessary.
- **Very low.** Minimum → **acceptable**: no threat to CH site. Current approach is sufficient.

The results of this indicator will be several, as it should be assessed by each hazard identified in indicator 3.2-HI. In Figure 43 an **example** of how the assessment of this methodology step would result is shown.

Figure 43: Example of the results of the assessment of the risk impacts for several hazards relevant to the pilot

REFERENCES

The indicator is an own elaboration based on literature about risk assessment and hazards vulnerability and exposure, such as IPCC 2012 (Chapter 1: “Climate Change: New Dimensions in Disaster Risk, Exposure, Vulnerability, and Resilience”) [35], IPCC 2022 [32] (“Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability”), and IPCC 2023 (Synthesis Report) [36].

A4.5 Risk impact Level evaluation: Severity of consequences and Likelihood of occurrence

ID: 3.5-RL_SxL

DEFINITION

It is a qualitative assessment of the risk impact level of climate change, geological incidents and human-made hazards to cultural heritage buildings or sites through a matrix of severity of consequences and likelihood of occurrence. It is also an effective way to systematically assess and prioritise the risks.

The assessment is done to each risk or hazard individually, and they are scored with a 1-5 scale, obtaining a "very high", "high", "moderate", "low" and "very low" value, which is in turn the qualitative result of the risk impact.

The **severity of consequences** is referred to the extent of the damage or loss that a hazard could cause to the CH site. It is the assessment of how bad the CH site could get if the particular hazard materialises. It may include physical damage, loss of historical value and financial implications.

The **likelihood of occurrence** is the probability of the hazard occurring and affecting or impacting the CH site.

OBJECTIVE

The objective of this indicator is to qualitatively evaluate the risk level of each hazard identified in **indicator 3.2-HI** of hazards identification. It then allows to prioritise the risk and prepare a risk management plan for the most relevant ones, developing the proper adaptation and mitigation strategies, as well as the response in case of occurrence.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

The indicator is easily assessed by applying the matrix below for each identified hazard. So, the result is obtained as a qualitative value of risk level for each hazard relevant to the CH site.

The **severity of consequences** can be assessed by answering the question "How will be the consequences for the CH site if the hazard event occurs?" or "In which degree the CH site will be affected if the hazard event occurs?". For answering such question, the amount of damage or harm that the hazard could create to the CH site should be considered. The following criteria should be assessed:

- 1. Catastrophic** – the CH site will be (almost) completely destroyed, huge loss of cultural heritage will take place if the hazard occurs. *E.g. complete destruction or irreparable damage, significant loss of historical value, very high financial cost.*
- 2. Major** – the CH site will suffer significant damage, requiring immediate action if the hazard occurs. *E.g. major damage, substantial loss of historical value, high financial cost.*
- 3. Moderate** – the CH site will be damaged if the hazard occurs, but it could be controlled without causing too much damage to the CH site. *E.g. moderate damage, partial loss of historical value, moderate financial cost.*
- 4. Minor** – the CH site will suffer minimum damage if the hazard event occurs, and it will be easily controllable without causing almost damage to the site. *E.g. minor damage, little loss of historical value, low financial cost.*

- 5. Insignificant** – the CH site will not be damaged if the hazard event occurs. E.g. negligible damage, no significant loss of historical value, very low financial cost.

The **likelihood of occurrence** can be assessed by answering the question “**How likely or probably is the hazard to occur in the CH site?**”. The question assesses the probability of the hazard occurring and adversely affecting the site. The following criteria should be assessed:

- 1. Frequent** – the hazard will take place likely often during the life span of the CH site. E.g. the event is almost certain to occur within a short timeframe, such as yearly occurrence.
- 2. Probable** – the hazard has happened before in the CH site, and will probably happen again. E.g. the event is likely to occur within a relatively short timeframe, such as every few years.
- 3. Occasional** – the hazard is likely to occur sometime during the life span of the CH site. *E.g. the event is may occur occasionally, such as once in a decade.*
- 4. Remote** – the hazard rarely occurs in the CH site, it is unlikely to happen at the same time that it is possible to occur. *E.g. the event is unlikely to occur, such as once in several decades.*
- 5. Improbable** – it is very unlikely that the hazard occurs in the CH site that it can be assumed an occurrence may not be experienced. *E.g. the event is very unlikely to occur, such as once in a century.*

The detailed matrix is included in the following Table 57.

Table 57: Risk impact level evaluation matrix, severity of consequences and likelihood of occurrence of each hazard identified to the CH site (KPI 3.5-RL_SxL)

Severity of consequences \ Likelihood of occurrence	Severity of consequences				
	Catastrophic (huge loss, completely destroyed)	Major (major damage, requiring immediate action)	Moderate (damaged, but can be controlled without major damage)	Minor (minimum damage, easily controllable without damage)	Insignificant (no actual damage)
Frequent (likely often in the life span)	Very high	Very high	High	High	Moderate
Probable (has happened before, and will happen again)	Very high	High	Moderate	Moderate	Low
Occasional (likely to occur sometime in the life span)	High	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Low
Remote (rarely occurs, unlikely but possible to occur)	High	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Very low
Improbable (so unlikely that it can be assumed an occurrence may not be experienced)	Moderate	Low	Low	Very low	Very low

The results of such matrix can be assessed through the following criteria (included also in Table 14 in the main section 3.3 – Pillar 3).

- **Very high.** Maximum → **unacceptable:** maximum threat to CH site. Implement immediate adaptation or mitigation measures/plan.

- **High.** High → **unacceptable**: large threat to CH site. Implement adaptation or mitigation measures/plan.
- **Moderate.** Medium → **acceptable**: some threat to CH site. Manage with adaptation or mitigation measures/plan.
- **Low.** Low → **acceptable**: little threat to CH site. Some management with adaptation or mitigation measures/plan necessary.
- **Very low.** Minimum → **acceptable**: no threat to CH site. Current approach is sufficient.

The results of this indicator will be several, as it should be assessed by each hazard identified in indicator 3.2-HI. In Figure 44 an example of how the assessment of this methodology step would result is shown.

Figure 44: Example of the results of the assessment of the risk impacts for several hazards relevant to the pilot

REFERENCES

The indicator is an own elaboration based on literature about risk assessment and hazards vulnerability and exposure, such as IPCC 2012 (Chapter 1: “Climate Change: New Dimensions in Disaster Risk, Exposure, Vulnerability, and Resilience”) [35], IPCC 2022 [32] (“Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability”), and IPCC 2023 (Synthesis Report) [36].

Annex 5. Pillar 4 KPIs: Accessibility, inclusiveness, openness and socioeconomic sustainability

A5.1 Accessibility level

ID: 4.1-AL

DEFINITION

An accessibility assessment (audit) of an existing building is a way to systematically identify architectural and functional barriers and suggest cost-effective solutions to remove them. One of the goals of developing the audit methodology is to use the tool in the case of existing buildings, including buildings subject to conservation protection.

The objective value of the assessment are human needs, which we try to include in technical specifications and parameters of individual elements that influence accessibility improvement.

Whether the buildings are old or new, the purpose of the audit remains the same:

- **Having a clear way to identify actual or potential accessibility problems and identify interventions that can help remove or circumvent barriers.**

An accessibility assessment is the starting point for defining an action plan within which interventions can be undertaken to improve the building's accessibility level. It is a way of identifying problems and suggesting approaches to removing barriers, and helps check compliance with relevant building regulations and guidelines based on the principles of universal design. Accessibility assessment must take into account the various needs of users, including, for example, the functional conditions of people with disabilities (e.g. mobility disabilities, such as wheelchair users, cane users), Visual Impairments (conditions that impact vision, ranging from partial sight to complete blindness) or Hearing Impairments (hearing disabilities include partial or complete loss of hearing and can vary in degree), but also seniors and caregivers with small children, short people, obese people and atypical people with neurodiversity.

For a building subject to assessment in terms of accessibility for people with disabilities (people with special needs), an accessibility audit should be performed in accordance with the developed methodology based on the assessment of 11 functional areas of the facility and the indication of barriers (critical and difficult) and discrepancies between the parameters of individual elements and the range of reference parameters.

Accessibility assessment is based on the analysis of 11 functional areas of the building, within which zones and elements with standardized parameters are distinguished.

The functional areas to be assessed are:

- **AREA 1:** access roads, bus stops and parking lots outside the property – the maximum distance is 150 m.
- **AREA 2:** access roads, parking lots and recreational and sports areas on the premises of the entity – scope depending on the type of facility,

- **AREA 3:** elements of small architecture at the entrance to the facility – benches, bicycle parking lots, lighting,
- **AREA 4:** external entrance zone – stairs, ramps and external lifts, highlighting the entrance in the facade, contrasting marking of the entrance,
- **AREA 5:** entrance area of the building / hall
- **AREA 6:** horizontal communication – communication system on individual floors of the building;
- **AREA 7:** vertical communication – the internal layout of the building and the technical solution used to support vertical communication,
- **AREA 8:** utility/communal rooms – basic rooms consistent with the function of the facility;
- **AREA 9:** rooms supporting people with disabilities, e.g. quiet rooms, rooms for breastfeeding women, etc.;
- **AREA 10:** hygiene and sanitary rooms;
- **AREA 11:** evacuation – ensuring evacuation and survival in the building.

The assessment assumes an analysis of the access route around the property, within it and in the analysed building, in order to identify possible accessibility restrictions or architectural barriers, called the "access path", including:

- the route to the building analysed at a distance of up to 150 m outside the premises covered by the accessibility assessment - the route includes access, e.g. from the bus stop, parking lot to the entrance to the property,
- the route from the entrance to the building premises to the main entrance to the building or another entrance, if the main entrance is inaccessible, and the small architectural elements located along this route,
- the route within the building from the entrance to the building to the entrances to the rooms where publicly available services are provided, with particular emphasis on:
 - access rooms performing key functions in the facility, i.e. rooms representative of the facility's functions, e.g. resident service room, concert hall, conference room, residential premises,
 - for hygienic and sanitary rooms (including hygienic and sanitary rooms adapted to the needs of people with disabilities),

The accessibility assessment may be extended by indications by the building manager, e.g. access to rooms important for the provision of services, e.g. access to the institution's management offices, cloakrooms or changing rooms in the case of a concert hall, or e.g. waste storage in the case of residential buildings.

The accessibility level assessment indicator is defined as a percentage of the number of parameters met in relation to all those required in a standardized audit. The accessibility indicator considers the impact of architectural barriers on the ability to use the services provided in the facility.

Architectural barriers are divided into:

- critical barriers preventing the use of services or threatening the safety of these people when using the facility,

- difficulties that require increased effort or concentration when using the facility.

In audit methodology were introduced three basic concepts:

- Firstly, the emphasis is placed on the availability of building services (related to the function of the facility: department, office, concert hall, apartment, etc.), and not on the availability of separate elements (ramp, elevator, etc.); this way we have greater comfort that the user can not only enter the building, but also reach and obtain the service their need;
- Secondly, the accessibility of paths between separate service points is checked (e.g. from the entrance area to the office, from the office to the toilet) or between the building entrance to the service point (e.g. restaurant service area); it is a dynamic approach, as opposed to static control of design and drawings.
- Thirdly, zones for users: guests and customers as well as employees/residents are subject to assessment.

OBJECTIVE

Creating a comprehensive checklist and recommended interventions serves as an essential preliminary assessment tool before starting the facility modernization design process. This approach allows decision-makers to gain an overall understanding of their building stock and plan actions for buildings where intervention is feasible from a conservation protection and economic assessment perspective.

Accessibility audits should be substantive, providing fundamental data about the facility (e.g., door width). Subsequently, these audits can include subjective assessments (e.g., whether the door is easy to open) and, where appropriate, suggest specific interventions.

This assessment assists designers and decision-makers in renovating and modernizing buildings, highlighting necessary interventions to enhance the functionality for people with disabilities and the elderly.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

The assessment is done following the Table 58 below with the different questions to evaluate if applicable.

Table 58: KPI 4.1-AL assessment through the answer (yes/no) where applicable to the elements or requirements in the different areas

ID	Element/ Requirement	Guidelines/ Recommendations/ Information/ Measure
Area 1: Element 1: Public transport stop		
1.1	There is a public transport stop within 150 m from the entrance to the premises / main building.	The public transport stop should be located no further than 150 m from the tested facility.
1.1.2	The stop platform is finished with a bus stop curb.	The stop platform should be ended with a stop curb profiled to enable the departure of the bus.
1.1.3.7.1	Information from the dynamic display board is available to people with visual disabilities.	The information displayed on the passenger information board should be accessible to people with visual disabilities.
Area 1: Element 2: Pedestrian crossing (access from the stop or from the direction of the stop)		

ID	Element/ Requirement	Guidelines/ Recommendations/ Information/ Measure
1.2.1	The width of the passage has lowered curbs with a maximum height of 0.02 m.	At a pedestrian crossing, along its entire width, lowered curbs with a maximum height of max. 0.02 m.
1.2.2	There are traffic lights at the pedestrian crossing.	It is recommended to analyse the feasibility of installing traffic lights at a pedestrian crossing based on an analysis prepared by a Road Traffic Safety expert.
1.2.3	Tactile passage schemes are placed at the passage.	It is recommended that tactile crossing patterns be located on posts or buttons at pedestrian crossings.
Area 2: Element 1: Entrance to the area		
2.1.3.1	The width of the gate is min. 0.90 m	A gate with a width of at least 0.9 m.
2.1.3.2	The gate is contrasted against the background of the surroundings or fence, at a level of min. 50% LRV.	A gate that stands out in color from the background of the fence should be used - recommended color contrast of min. 50% LRV
Area 3: Element 2: Small architecture		
3.2.2.1	Bicycle racks are placed outside the edge of the obstacle-free route.	Signs and devices including: bicycle racks, blocking posts and greenery are located outside the edge of the obstacle-free route (2.0 m wide).
Area 4: Element 1: Main entrance area to the building		
4.1.3	The main entrance is accessible to people with disabilities	In accordance with the principle of equal access for all persons, it is advisable for persons with disabilities to have access through the main entrance to the building.
Area 4: Element 6.1: Stairs in front of entrance W1		
4.9	The building entrance is accessible at ground level.	It is recommended to eliminate the barrier of stairs to enable access to public spaces for people with limited mobility and wheelchair users.
4.9.1	The height of the steps is the same.	The same height and width of stair steps should be used along their entire length.
Area 5: Element 1: Main entrance vestibule W1		
5.1.4.1	The vestibule provides a maneuvering space of 1.50 m wide and 1.20 m deep + the width of each door leaf that opens inwards.	If the door opens into the vestibule, the minimum dimensions of the maneuvering space should be maintained: width 1.5 m, depth 1.2 m + width of each leaf. door that opens inwards.
5.1.5	There are no thresholds in the vestibule area.	Thresholds higher than 0.02 m in the vestibule area should be eliminated.
Area 5: Element 2: Information point/reception		
5.2	In the entrance area of the building there is an information point/reception/concierge desk.	An information point/reception desk should be located in the entrance area of the building and, in the case of small facilities, an information board.
5.2.1	The information point/reception is visible immediately after entering.	The information point/reception desk should be located so that it is visible immediately after entering the building.
5.2.6	Matte finishing materials were used at the information/reception desk and around it.	Floors and walls in the information/reception point and their surroundings should be finished with materials with matte surfaces.

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ID	Element/ Requirement	Guidelines/ Recommendations/ Information/ Measure
5.2.8.1	At the information/reception point, the top of the counter is at a maximum height of 0.90 m over a minimum length of 0.90 m.	The service point counter should be installed at a height (measured from the floor finishing level) of no more than 0.90 m (recommended: 0.70–0.80 m) over a distance of at least 0.90 m.
Area 6: Element 1: Horizontal communication		
6.1.1	The layout of communication routes is simple and clear and has central points.	It is recommended that the communication system be simple and clear, based on central points, which facilitates orientation in the building for all its users.
6.1.2	All rooms on a given floor are accessible to a person moving around using a wheelchair.	It is recommended that all rooms located on one floor (except technical rooms) are accessible to people with different disabilities.
6.1.3	The width of the corridors (between structural elements - walls) is 1.20 - 1.80 m (specify dimensions).	An obstacle-free route of at least 1.8 m wide and at least 2.2 m high must be provided. In exceptional cases, this width may be reduced to 1.2 m with extensions to 1.8 m at intervals of up to ten meters.
6.1.4	The width of corridors is more than 1.80 m and less than 4.00 m (specify dimensions).	Due to the function of the facility, it is recommended for people with visual disabilities to use an application that facilitates orientation in the building and to use C1 information invoices at the entrances to utility rooms.
6.1.6	There are no local narrowings of 1.0-1.8 m width.	A route free from obstacles must be provided, with a width of at least 1.8 m and a height of at least 2,2 m. Local narrowings with a width of not less than 1.0 m and a length of max. 0.5 m are permissible.
6.1.9.1	Elements placed on walls protrude from the wall face by a distance of no more than 0.10 m.	Items located between 0.7 m and 2.4 m high within the "obstacle-free route" must be removed if they protrude from the wall by more than 0.1 m. Obstacles must be enclosed downwards or a limiter/plinth must be used at a height of no more than 0.3 m and no less than 0.07 m.
6.1.11	Moving elements and equipment do not restrict the movement of people with visual impairments.	Equipment elements that limit the width of the corridor should be secured and highlighted in color.
Area 7: Element 1: Staircase S1		
7.1.3.1	When a flight of stairs has 4-10 steps, the edge of the first and last step is marked with a contrasting stripe (LRV not less than 70%) 0.05 m wide visible on the tread and riser.	In a flight of stairs, the edge of the first and last step of the flight should be marked with a contrasting stripe (LRV not less than 70%), 0.05 m wide, visible on the tread and riser.
7.1.7	Landings of min. length 1.5 m	Flights of stairs with more than 9 steps should be divided by landings of min. length. 1.5
7.1.10	At a distance of 0.5 m - 0.6 m from the edge of the first upper step there is a warning texture (type B) with a width of at least 0.6 m.	For people with visual impairments, stairs leading down are a particular hazard. A warning texture 0.6 - 0.8 m wide (two rows of tiles measuring 30 cm x 30 cm, 40 cm x 40 cm) should be installed 0.5 m - 0.6 m from the edge of the first upper step to avoid the risk of falling.

ID	Element/ Requirement	Guidelines/ Recommendations/ Information/ Measure
7.1.22.7.1	The handrails are contrasted with the background at a minimum level of 50% LRV	Handrails should contrast with the background by at least 50% LRV.
7.1.22.8	Handrails are round, elliptical or square in shape with rounded edges, 0.035-0.045 m wide.	Handrails should be circular, elliptical or square with rounded edges 0.035-0.045 m wide.
7.1.22.9	The handrail handles are attached from the bottom, allowing to move hand freely.	The handrails should be made in such a way that the hand grip is secure and allows the hand to move freely along the handrail. The mounting handle should be from the bottom to ensure a secure hand grip.

REFERENCES

The level of accessibility is determined by the analysis of existing technical parameters of individual elements in comparison with standardized solutions included in the Accessibility Standards developed by the Universal Design Centre of the Gdansk University of Technology based on national and European regulations (such as the one developed by the Municipality of Krakow, in Poland⁷²).

The assessment considered EN 17210:2021, 1st European standard on accessibility and usability of the built environment – Functional requirements⁷³.

Building accessibility standards for people with disabilities⁷⁴.

Individual parameters of elements affecting accessibility may vary in individual countries, which requires additional assessment and detailing of these parameters by other project partners. The objects indicated in the project are subject to conservation protection, therefore, as part of the accessibility assessment, the necessary level of preservation of the original elements and the use of possible alternative solutions that will enable the elimination of critical barriers and difficulties should be determined with the conservation services.

EXAMPLE

Pilot #5 is a multi-family residential building and part of the social housing stock of the municipality of Gdynia. The building is listed in the Municipal Register of Monuments and is under cultural heritage protection.

There are 10 flats in the building, but it lacks a lift and other facilities for people with mobility difficulties. The ground floor flats are occupied by individuals with physical and mental disabilities who are assisted by the Municipal Social Assistance Centre.

The building is located near the city centre and is in a well-connected area. Currently, both access to the building and its interior are not adapted to the needs of individuals with disabilities.

The calculated Accessibility Level is 13.64% (see also Figure 45 for such assessment calculated with the tool).

⁷²

https://bip.krakow.pl/zarzadzenie/2023/1163/w_sprawie_wprowadzenia_%E2%80%9EStandardow_Dostepnosci_dla_Gminy_Miejskiej_Krakow%E2%80%9D.html

⁷³ https://www.en.une.org/normalizacion_documentos/PT%20EN%2017210.pdf

⁷⁴ <https://www.gov.pl/web/rozwoj-technologie/standardy-dostepnosci-budynkow-dla-osob-z-niepelnosprawnosciami>

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Level : 13.64%

Questions	YES	NO	N/A
There is a public transport stop within 150 m from the entrance to the premises / main building.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The stop platform is finished with a bus stop curb.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Information from the dynamic display board is available to people with visual disabilities.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The width of the passage has lowered curbs with a maximum height of 0.02m.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
There are traffic lights at the pedestrian crossing.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Tactile passage schemes are placed at the passage.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The width of the gate is min. 0.90 m.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
The gate is contrasted against the background of the surroundings or fence, at a level of min. 50% LRV.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Bicycle racks are placed outside the edge of the obstacle-free route.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
The main entrance is accessible to people with disabilities.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The building entrance is accessible at ground level.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The height of the steps is the same.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The vestibule provides a maneuvering space of 1.50 m wide and 1.20 m deep + the width of each door leaf that opens inwards.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
There are no thresholds in the vestibule area.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
In the entrance area of the building there is an information point/reception/concierge desk.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
The information point/reception is visible immediately after entering.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Matte finishing materials were used at the information/reception desk and around it.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
At the information/reception point, the top of the counter is at a maximum height of 0.90 m over a minimum length of 0.90 m.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
The layout of communication routes is simple and clear and has central points.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
All rooms on a given floor are accessible to a person moving around using a wheelchair.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The width of the corridors (between structural elements - walls) is 1.20 - 1.80 m (specify dimensions).	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The width of corridors is more than 1.80 m and less than 4.00 m (specify dimensions).	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
There are no local narrowings of 1.0-1.8 m width.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Elements placed on walls protrude from the wall face by a distance of no more than 0.10 m.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Moving elements and equipment do not restrict the movement of people with visual impairments.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
When a flight of stairs has 4-10 steps, the edge of the first and last step is marked with a contrasting stripe (LRV not less than 70%) 0.05 m wide visible on the tread and riser.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Landings of min. length 1.5 m.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
At a distance of 0.5 m - 0.6 m from the edge of the first upper step there is a warning texture (type B) with a width of at least 0.6 m.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The handrails are contrasted with the background at a minimum level of 50% LRV.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Handrails are round, elliptical or square in shape with rounded edges, 0.035-0.045 m wide.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The handrail handles are attached from the bottom, allowing to move hand freely.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Figure 45: Example of the results of the assessment of the accessibility level using the simple tool developed

A5.2 Inclusiveness and openness level

ID: 4.2-I&OL

DEFINITION

The inclusiveness and openness level of a building refers to its design, features, and policies that make it accessible and welcoming to all people, regardless of their age, gender, ability, race, or other characteristics.

The aspects to consider when evaluating the inclusiveness and openness level of a building are accessibility, universal design, safety, community engagement, affordability or policy and practice to support diversity.

Accessibility is one of the key aspects of the level of inclusiveness of the building. It includes features such as ramps, elevators, wide doorways, and accessible restrooms that allow people with disabilities to navigate the building easily. Also, the Braille signage and tactile indicators for those who are blind or have low vision or visual alarms and signage for those who are deaf or hard of hearing, can increase the level of inclusiveness. Just as clear, simple signage and wayfinding aids, easy-to-understand instructions and information. Accessible emergency exits and evacuation plans.

Incorporating universal design principles ensures that the building can be used by the widest range of people possible, without the need for special adaptations. Appropriate size and space are provided for approach, reach, manipulation, and use, regardless of the user's body size, posture, or mobility. A building that meets the requirements of universal design can be used by people of all abilities. It should be flexible to meet different user needs. It should be easy and intuitive to use, minimise the risk of danger through misuse and should be equipped and arranged in an ergonomic way for people with different needs. Universal design goes beyond accessibility by considering the needs of all potential users from the beginning of the design process, rather than making modifications or accommodations after the fact. This inclusive approach aims to create environments that are more usable, safer, and more convenient for everyone.

An inclusive building prioritizes the safety and security of all occupants, including measures to prevent harassment, discrimination, and violence. Presence of monitoring, access control systems, clear emergency evacuation procedures and trained staff in accident procedures, assistance to disabled persons and conflict procedures, are relevant.

Buildings can foster inclusiveness and openness by providing spaces for community gatherings, events, and activities that bring people together across different backgrounds and identities. Foster a sense of community among building occupants through regular events and activities that promote interaction and mutual respect.

An important aspect of inclusivity and openness is also to ensure that the building is affordable to people of different income levels and can also contribute to inclusion by enabling individuals and families from different socio-economic backgrounds to access its facilities and services.

Inclusive and open buildings often have policies and practices in place to promote equity and inclusion among their staff, tenants, and visitors, such as anti-discrimination policies, diversity training, and inclusive hiring practices. Also, buildings can reflect and celebrate the diversity of their users through artwork, signage, and other design elements that incorporate diverse cultures, languages, and perspectives.

Evaluating the inclusiveness and openness level of a building involves considering these factors holistically and identifying areas for improvement to ensure that the space is welcoming and accessible to everyone. The result of the analysis is provided in % (where 100% means that the building has the maximum score)

OBJECTIVE

An assessment of a building's level of inclusivity identifies difficulties and enables the planning of measures leading to the creation of a welcoming environment for the maximum number of diverse users. It identifies physical, social and procedural barriers and ensures that the building is operating in accordance with regulations. An important aspect of assessing inclusiveness and openness is determining the extent to which improvements can be made to the building to better serve the needs of its users.

Activities during the design or planning process are focused on resisting accessibility, buildings safety, improving user satisfaction and increasing social cohesion. By increasing the range of people who can freely use a building, a place becomes more attractive, and society becomes more responsible.

Overall, knowing the level of inclusiveness and openness of a building allows stakeholders (building owner and building operator/manager) to create spaces that are welcoming, accessible, and supportive for all individuals, contributing to a more equitable and inclusive society.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

To assess inclusiveness and openness level following questions (Table 59) need to be answered by the building owner/ administrator with a yes/no or tick N/A in case it does not apply to the building.

Table 59: KPI 4.2-I&OL assessment through the set of questions that need to be answered (yes/no) where applicable

No.	Question	Answer
1.	Is each floor accessible for individuals using wheelchairs, individuals with mobility difficulties, and caregivers with baby strollers?	
2.	Are public restrooms adapted for disabled individuals? (lower toilet seats, handrails, manoeuvring space, sink faucets with longer handles)	
3.	Are there facilities available to assist with changing babies?	
4.	Does the building have parking spaces designated for disabled individuals?	
5.	Are there easily accessible information points in the building regarding facilities for disabled individuals?	
6.	Is there clear navigational information (tactile, auditory, assistance) for blind and visually impaired individuals?	
7.	Are there information boards with Braille writing?	
8.	Are there Braille buttons in the lift that can be pressed?	
9.	In case of fire or emergency, is there an audible alarm system with instructions on what to do?	
10.	Is the signage in the building contrastive to facilitate reading for visually impaired individuals?	
11.	Is the visual information in the building legible?	

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No.	Question	Answer
12.	Is navigation in the building clear (legibility of room signs and routes to selected functions)?	
13.	Is the building staff trained to assist disabled individuals?	
14.	Is the building staff trained in communication with individuals with communication difficulties and intellectual disabilities?	
15.	Is the building staff trained in providing first aid and handling emergency situations?	
16.	Is the building staff trained in procedures for dealing with aggression or discrimination?	
17.	Is the interior of the building designed to limit sensory stimuli?	
18.	Are there measures in the building to minimize the risk of self-harm and suicide?	
19.	Is the height and arrangement of the equipment adjusted for all users?	
20.	Is there a flexible space in the building that can change its function depending on the needs or serve multiple functions simultaneously?	
21.	Are there assistive technologies in the building, such as home automation or communication aids?	
22.	Are there solutions in the building that minimize the environmental impact?	
23.	Is the building accessible to everyone regardless of origin and status?	
24.	Are there transparent and fair procedures in the building for incidents of aggression and harassment?	
25.	Are there rooms in the building that can serve as community meeting spaces?	
26.	Does the building have surveillance?	
27.	Are there spaces in the building that support interaction and integration among users?	
28.	Does the building have clear procedures and signage for life-threatening or health-threatening situations?	
29.	Are there common work or rest areas in the building?	
30.	Is the building managed in a way that is open to the needs and suggestions of users?	
31.	Does the building offer rental apartments/premises in various price ranges?	
32.	Are there programs that provide rent subsidies for individuals in difficult financial situations?	
33.	Is the building energy-efficient?	
34.	Are there technological solutions in the building that enable the use of renewable energy sources?	
35.	Is the building located near an extensive public transportation network?	
36.	Are there basic services near the building? (shops, hospital, school, other services)	
37.	Are there rooms in the building that, through shared use, help reduce operating costs?	
38.	Does the building offer discounted tickets for children, students, seniors, large families, and disabled individuals?	

REFERENCES

In Europe, several standards, norms, and regulations are connected with the level of inclusiveness of buildings, particularly concerning accessibility and non-discrimination. Some of the key ones include:

- **European Standard EN 17210:2021**⁷⁵. This standard provides guidelines for accessibility in the built environment, covering both new and existing buildings. It includes specifications for features such as ramps, doorways, elevators, and signage to ensure accessibility for people with disabilities.
- **European Disability Strategy 2010-2020**⁷⁶. This strategy aims to promote the rights of persons with disabilities and improve their access to various aspects of life, including buildings and public spaces. It emphasizes the importance of accessibility and non-discrimination in the built environment.
- **European Directive 2010/41/EU**⁷⁷. This directive prohibits discrimination on the grounds of disability and age in the access to and supply of goods and services, including access to buildings. It requires member states to take measures to ensure accessibility and non-discrimination in the built environment.
- **Building Regulations**. Each European country has its own building regulations that govern the design, construction, and accessibility of buildings. These regulations often include requirements for features such as ramps, accessible toilets, and designated parking spaces for people with disabilities.
- **UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD)**⁷⁸. While not specific to Europe, many European countries are signatories to this convention, which promotes the rights and inclusion of persons with disabilities. It includes provisions related to accessibility in the built environment and non-discrimination.
- **Local Codes and Standards**: In addition to national and European-level regulations, local authorities may have their own codes and standards related to the inclusiveness of buildings. These may include requirements for accessibility in public buildings, commercial developments, and housing.
- **Certification Systems**: Some European countries have certification systems or voluntary schemes for assessing the accessibility and inclusiveness of buildings. These may provide incentives for developers to incorporate inclusive design principles into their projects.

Overall, the level of inclusiveness and openness of buildings in Europe is influenced by a combination of European directives, national building regulations, international standards, and local codes and practices. Compliance with these standards and regulations is essential for ensuring that buildings are accessible and inclusive for all individuals.

EXAMPLE

Pilot #5 is a multi-family residential building and part of the social housing stock of the municipality of Gdynia. The building is listed in the Municipal Register of Monuments and is under cultural heritage protection.

There are 10 flats in the building, but it lacks a lift and other facilities for people with mobility difficulties. The ground floor flats are occupied by individuals with physical and mental disabilities

⁷⁵ https://accessible-eu-centre.ec.europa.eu/content-corner/digital-library/en-172102021-accessibility-and-usability-built-environment-functional-requirements_en

⁷⁶ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=COM%3A2010%3A0636%3AFIN%3Aen%3APDF>

⁷⁷ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32010L0041>

⁷⁸ <https://www.un.org/disabilities/documents/convention/convoptprot-e.pdf>

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who are assisted by the Municipal Social Assistance Centre. One of the flats on the second-floor houses people experiencing homelessness.

The building is partially economically inclusive, as the flats are available to those who cannot afford to buy or rent their own property. However, due to the absence of energy efficiency improvements, rents and charges for energy and water heating are quite high.

The calculated Inclusiveness & Openness Level is 28% (see also Figure 46 for such assessment calculated with the tool).

Figure 46: Example of the results of the assessment of the inclusiveness and openness level using the simple tool developed

A5.3 Direct revenue from tourism

ID: 4.3-RT

DEFINITION

Direct revenue from tourism refers to the income generated by the monument or historic building through visitor-related activities. This includes revenue from entry fees, guided tours and souvenir sales directly attributable to the monument. It does not encompass indirect economic benefits or contributions from external funding sources.

OBJECTIVE

To evaluate the financial self-sufficiency of the monument. Specifically, this KPI assesses whether the monument generates sufficient income to cover its operational and maintenance (O&M) costs. This information provides a benchmark for understanding how well the monument's revenue supports its ongoing upkeep and helps identify potential financial gaps that may need addressing.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

To determine the significance of the direct revenue from tourism, the impact is categorised into three levels:

- **P (Significant effect):** if the direct revenue covers more than 50% of the total maintenance and operational costs, the monument demonstrates strong financial self-sufficiency. This level indicates that the monument is largely capable of sustaining itself through its own generated income, with only minimal reliance on external funding sources.
- **Q (Moderate effect):** when the direct revenue covers 20-50% of the total O&M costs, it suggests that the monument generates a meaningful income but still relies on additional financial support. This moderate level of self-sufficiency indicates that the monument is partially sustainable but requires supplementary resources for its ongoing operations.
- **R (Minimal or No effect):** if the direct revenue covers less than 20% of the total maintenance and operational costs, the monument shows minimal financial contribution from tourism. In this case, the monument heavily depends on external funding or alternative revenue streams to maintain its operations.

This categorization helps in contextualizing the financial viability of the monument and provides a clear framework for understanding the extent to which tourism revenue supports its sustainability.

REFERENCES

RURITAGE EU Project⁷⁹, Egusquiza et al., 2020 [58].

EXAMPLE

Consider a historic monument that generates 40,000 € per month from tourism-related activities, while its total monthly maintenance and operational costs are 100,000 €. This means the direct revenue covers 40% of the O&M costs, placing the monument in the Q (moderate effect) category. This assessment highlights that while the monument generates a substantial portion of its needed funds, it still requires additional financial support to fully cover its expenses.

⁷⁹ <https://www.ruritage.eu/>

A5.4 Indirect revenue through tourism

ID: 4.4-IRT

DEFINITION

Indirect revenue through tourism measures the economic benefits experienced by local businesses due to the popularity of a nearby monument. This includes increased customer traffic and spending at local establishments such as hotels, restaurants, and shops, which is indirectly driven by the monument's attraction.

OBJECTIVE

To assess how the monument's popularity contributes to the local economy by boosting business revenue and growth in the surrounding area. Understanding this impact helps gauge the monument's overall economic benefit to the community.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

To determine the indirect revenue from tourism, the impact can be categorised into three levels based on quality assessments, surveys and estimations of economic impact:

- **P (Significant effect):** the monument significantly boosts local businesses, leading to noticeable increases in revenue, customer traffic and potentially the opening of new businesses. this level of impact indicates that the monument is a major driver of the local economy, with strong positive effects on the community's economic welfare. A significant effect might be evident through business surveys showing a substantial percentage increase in revenue attributed to tourism.
- **Q (Moderate effect):** the monument moderately benefits nearby businesses, resulting in a steady but smaller increase in revenue and customer traffic. While the economic impact is positive, it may not be enough to spur new business openings or transformative changes in the local economy. This level of impact indicates that the monument contributes to economic activity, but additional factors or support might be needed to fully capitalise on its potential.
- **R (Minimal or No effect):** the monument has little to no noticeable impact on local businesses. Any increase in revenue or customer traffic is minimal, and there is no significant growth linked to the monument's popularity. This may suggest that other factors are more influential in driving the local economy, or that barriers (e.g. accessibility issues, lack of infrastructure) prevent the monument from having a meaningful spill over effect.

REFERENCES

RURITAGE EU Project⁸⁰, Egusquiza et al., 2020 [58].

EXAMPLE

Considering a historic monument located in a small town where the monthly revenue of local businesses averages 50,000€. The monument's presence results in only a 10% increase in local business revenue (an additional 5,000€ per month). This would be categorised as "Q" (moderate effect). The monument positively impacts the local economy, but the effect is moderate, and additional efforts might be needed to enhance this economic benefit.

⁸⁰ <https://www.ruritage.eu/>

A5.5 Increased property value

ID: 4.5-IPV

DEFINITION

Increased property value refers to the rise in the monetary value of real estate properties in the vicinity of a monument or historic building. This increase is often driven by factors such as the growing popularity of the monument, improved local infrastructure and heightened demand for property in the area due to tourism and associated economic activity. The KPI focuses on the change in property value directly influenced by the presence and attraction of the monument.

OBJECTIVE

To measure the economic impact of the monument on the surrounding real estate market. An increase in property values can be a direct indicator of the monument's success in attracting tourism and fostering local economic development. This KPI provides tangible data to assess how the monument contributes to the overall prosperity of the area.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

To assess the increase in property value, the impact is categorised into three levels based on percentage of changes in property value over time, adjusted for inflation:

- **P (Significant effect):** as significant increase in property value, indicating that the monument has a strong positive impact on the local real estate market. For example, if property values have increased by **15% or more**, this would reflect a significant effect, suggesting that the monument is a key driver of economic growth in the area.
- **Q (Moderate effect):** a moderate increase in property value, suggesting that while the monument contributes to rising property values, other factors may also be at play. A percentage increase in property value between **5% and 15%** would be classified as a moderate effect, showing a positive but not transformative impact.
- **R (Minimal or No effect):** a minimal or negligible increase in property value, indicating that the monument has had little to no impact on the local real estate market. Property value increases of **0% to 5%** would fall under this category, suggesting that other economic or market forces are more influential in driving property values.

This categorisation allows for a nuanced understanding of the monument's impact on property values, helping stakeholders to assess the broader economic implications of the monument's popularity and attractiveness.

REFERENCES

Angelakoglou et al., 2023 [59], more specifically: KPI 61 in appendix A.

Ho et al., 2021 [60].

EXAMPLE

If a monument has led to a 20% increase in local property values over several years, adjusted for inflation, this would be classified as P (significant effect). This indicates that the monument has substantially influenced the real estate market, contributing to economic growth in the area.

A5.6 Number of local jobs created

ID: 4.6-LJC

DEFINITION

The number of local jobs created refers to the proportion of employment opportunities generated by the monument or historic building that have been filled by local residents. This includes both direct jobs (e.g. staff working at the monument) and indirect jobs (e.g. jobs in local businesses that benefit from the increased tourism). The KPI measures the extent to which the monument contributes to the economic well-being of the local community by providing employment opportunities.

OBJECTIVE

To assess the monument's positive impact on the local community through job creation. By providing employment to local residents, the monument can foster a sense of inclusion and community support. If local residents are meaningfully employed, they are more likely to support and promote the monument, enhancing its reputation and sustainability. Conversely, a low percentage of local employment may lead to resentment or detachment from the monument, potentially hindering its success.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

The impact of job creation for local residents is categorised into three levels based on percentage of jobs filled by locals:

- **P (Significant effect):** a high percentage of jobs created by the monument are filled by local residents, indicating a strong positive impact on the local community. For example, if **70% or more** of the jobs are held by locals, this suggests the monument is playing a substantial role in local economic development and fostering community support.
- **Q (Moderate effect):** a moderate percentage of jobs are filled by local residents, showing a positive but not overwhelming impact on local employment. This might be a situation where **40% to 70%** of the jobs are held by locals, indicating that while the monument contributes to local employment, there is still room for improvement in engaging the community.
- **R (Minimal or No effect):** a minimal percentage of jobs are filled by local residents, indicating little impact on the local job market. If **less than 40%** of the jobs are held by locals, it suggests that the monument is not fully leveraging its potential to support the local community, which could lead to dissatisfaction or lack of local engagement.

These criteria allow for a clear assessment of how well the monument supports local employment and its broader socioeconomic impact on the community.

REFERENCES

Angelakoglou et al., 2023 [59], ore specifically: KPI 47 in appendix A.

EXAMPLE

If 75% of the jobs created by a monument are filled by local residents, this would be classified as P (significant effect). This high percentage reflects a strong commitment to local employment, fostering positive community relations and enhancing the monument's overall sustainability.

A5.7 Investment in public infrastructure

ID: 4.7-IP1

DEFINITION

It refers to the financial investments made by public or private entities in infrastructure projects that enhance the area surrounding a monument or historic building. These investments may include improvements in transportation, utilities, public spaces, or other facilities directly or indirectly driven by the monument's presence and its attraction of visitors.

OBJECTIVE

To measure the extent to which the monument stimulates broader local development through infrastructure investments. By attracting tourists and raising the profile of the area, the monument can encourage public and private stakeholders to invest in improvements that benefit both the local community and the visitors. This KPI helps to evaluate the monument's role as a catalyst for wider economic and infrastructural growth.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

The impact of the monument on public infrastructure investment is categorized into three levels, based on the scale and significance of these investments:

- **P (Significant effect):** a substantial level of investment in public infrastructure is directly linked to the monument's presence. This may involve major projects such as new roads, transportation hubs, or public amenities that significantly enhance the area's accessibility and attractiveness. For example, if infrastructure investments exceed 10 million € or cover more than 50% of all recent local development projects, this would reflect a significant effect.
- **Q (Moderate effect):** a moderate level of investment is associated with the monument, indicating that while the monument contributes to infrastructure development, the scale of investment is smaller or more limited in scope. This could involve improvements like enhanced public transportation, minor road upgrades, or renovation of public spaces. Investments between 2 million € and 10 million € or 20-50% of local projects would fall under this category.
- **R (Minimal or No effect):** minimal or no investment in public infrastructure can be attributed to the monument. In this case, any improvements are either negligible or not clearly linked to the monument's presence. If investments are under 2 million € or account for less than 20% of local projects, this would indicate minimal or no effect.

These categories allow for a comprehensive evaluation of how the monument drives infrastructural improvements, offering insights into its broader socioeconomic impact.

EXAMPLE

If a monument's presence has led to 5 million € in investments for minor road upgrades and the enhancement of local public transport, this would be categorized as Q (moderate effect). While these improvements are beneficial and contribute to the area's accessibility, they are not large-scale projects, indicating a moderate impact of the monument on local infrastructure development.

A5.8 Cultural Enrichment

ID: 4.8-CE

DEFINITION

Cultural enrichment refers to the extent to which a monument or historic building contributes to the local cultural scene, including its influence on events, festivals, and other cultural activities. This KPI measures the monument's role in enhancing local cultural identity and promoting community engagement through cultural means.

OBJECTIVE

To evaluate whether the monument positively impacts the local culture by serving as a hub or catalyst for cultural activities. A monument that enriches the local cultural scene can strengthen community ties, enhance cultural awareness, and contribute to a vibrant local atmosphere that attracts both residents and visitors.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

The impact of the monument on local cultural enrichment is categorized into three levels, based on the scale and significance of its contributions:

- **P (Significant effect):** the monument plays a major role in cultural activities, either as a primary venue for key events or as a central figure in the local cultural identity. This could involve regular, high-attendance events, strong partnerships with cultural organizations, or a significant increase in cultural offerings directly tied to the monument. For instance, if the monument is the centrepiece of several major cultural festivals or accounts for **over 50%** of cultural event participation in the area, it would be classified as having a significant effect.
- **Q (Moderate effect):** the monument contributes to the local cultural scene in a meaningful but not dominant way. This could include hosting occasional events, supporting local arts initiatives, or contributing to the diversity of cultural activities. If the monument influences **20-50%** of local cultural activities, it would be categorized as having a moderate effect.
- **R (Minimal or No effect):** the monument has little to no discernible impact on local cultural activities. In this case, it may host very few events or not be recognized as a cultural asset within the community. If **less than 20%** of cultural activities in the area are linked to the monument, it would be considered to have minimal or no effect.

These categories help assess the monument's cultural significance and its role in enhancing the local cultural environment.

EXAMPLE

If a monument is responsible for hosting a few small-scale cultural events annually, contributing to around 30% of the local cultural activities, this would be classified as Q (moderate effect). While the monument plays a role in enriching the local culture, it is not the primary driver of cultural activity in the area.

A5.9 Public perception

ID: 4.9-PP

DEFINITION

It evaluates the sentiment of the local community, and potentially a broader audience, toward a monument or historic building and its perceived impact on the local economy, culture, and daily life. This KPI captures how positively or negatively the public views the monument and its role in the community.

OBJECTIVE

To measure the overall sentiment toward the monument, providing insights into how it is perceived by those who live nearby, as well as visitors. Understanding public perception is essential for ensuring that the monument is viewed as a positive asset rather than a source of tension or conflict. The data gathered can help guide future initiatives to enhance the monument's role in the community or address any concerns. This assessment should be conducted through unbiased surveys, media analysis, and public feedback to ensure a well-rounded understanding of sentiment.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

Public perception is inherently subjective, making it challenging to quantify. However, it can be categorised into three levels based on overall sentiment:

- **P (Positive sentiment):** the majority of the public views the monument positively, appreciating its cultural, economic, or historical contributions. This sentiment might be reflected in positive survey responses, favourable media coverage, and low levels of public complaints. For example, if more than 70% of surveyed individuals express positive feelings toward the monument, it would be classified as having a positive sentiment.
- **Q (Neutral sentiment):** the public's perception of the monument is mixed or indifferent, with no dominant sentiment. Some people may appreciate the monument, while others are indifferent or have balanced views. This category is often reflected in survey results where 40-70% of responses are neutral or when positive and negative opinions are approximately equal.
- **R (Negative sentiment):** a significant portion of the public views the monument negatively, potentially seeing it as a source of nuisance or conflict, such as through increased congestion or noise. This category would be appropriate when less than 40% of the surveyed population has a positive view, or when negative feedback outweighs the positive by a significant margin.

These categories allow for a structured interpretation of public sentiment, helping to identify areas where the monument's impact can be improved.

EXAMPLE

A survey conducted among local residents and visitors reveals that 80% of respondents view the monument positively, praising its contribution to the local culture and economy. Additionally, media coverage highlights the monument's role in boosting tourism and enhancing community pride, with very few public complaints registered. Based on this data, the public perception would be classified as P (positive sentiment), indicating that the monument is widely appreciated and valued by the community.

